

I-CLAIM

Improving the Living
and Labour Conditions
of Irregularised Migrant
Households in Europe

Country report

Discourses about irregularised migrants at the EU level

*Representation and narratives in
the European Commission,
the European Parliament and civil society*

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February 2025

Funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

Funded by the European Union under Grant Number 101094373. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency or UK Research and Innovation. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Executive Summary

This I-CLAIM report examines how *'irregularised migration'* is framed within EU-level discourse across three actors: European Commission, the European Parliament, and EU civil society.

A comparative analysis reveals a nuanced landscape within EU migration discourse, where recurring themes of border control, migration and residence status, rights and employment are interpreted through divergent lenses. Using a mix of quantitative and qualitative methods, the Report explores how these lexical and discursive patterns and narratives are shaped across key topics including border control, rights, employment, gender, the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, returns, and 'crisis' narratives.

A quantitative analysis of collected data supports general statements on each of the actors studied. In the selected timeframe (2019-2023), the Commission's narratives largely emphasised policy, control, and regulated migration pathways, with a frequent focus on border security and return processes. The Parliament's discourse varied by political group, including both rights-based approaches and security- or crime-focused rhetoric. In contrast, civil society prioritised human rights concerns, often challenging securitised framings and advocating for more inclusive policies.

Nonetheless, the Report finds that these actors are by no means unitary. Significant differences can be observed both within the European Commission and the European Parliament in 2019-2023. Within the Commission, President von der Leyen displayed a stronger focus on geopolitical issues and the role of the EU in the world; Vice-President Schinas's discourse appeared to be more focused on legal and policy frameworks, border controls and 'legal' (or regular) pathways for labour migration; Commissioner Johansson, by contrast, showed a more humanitarian and rights-based approach, highlighting that migration is normal and natural, while still focused on border controls and cross-border movement, as well as measures against smugglers and traffickers. Within the Parliament, the 2019-2024 VDL I majority groups used more policy-oriented language albeit with specific divergences based on their ideological positions. Opposition groups favoured instead more emotional overtones, focusing either on racism and human rights violations or on crime, threats to sovereignty, anti-migration, and xenophobia.

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The author would like to thank Prof. Bastian Vollmer (Catholic University of Applied Sciences Mainz), Dr Markus Rheindorf (University of Vienna), Prof. Ilse van Liempt (Utrecht University) and Prof. Nando Sigona (University of Birmingham) for their guidance and comments on a previous draft of this Report. He would also like to thank Robin Morgan, former intern at CEPS, for his contribution to the data collection for this Report.

The Report's comparative analysis identifies points of difference and convergence for each EU actor's stance and narratives, and how these developed in connection to the I-CLAIM project's different topics of interest. It finds that specific statuses are tied to different themes and discussions. For example, 'irregular' status evokes notions of border management, security, and crime, while 'refugee' evokes those of rights and welfare – though progressive voices often challenge this binary by advocating for the fundamental rights of all TCNs, regardless of status. Employment-related discussions largely excluded *irregularised* migrant workers, focusing instead on labour migration for selected categories of workers that the EU 'needs'. Exceptions to this are seen among left-leaning MEPs and civil society, which stressed social rights and protections for all workers. Within the institutions, gendered narratives exclusively associated 'vulnerability' with women and children, often ignoring other specific reception and protection needs, while civil society called for more inclusive perspectives.

The analysis of Covid-19 narratives revealed a divide, with the Commission only focusing on regular third-country nationals, right-wing MEPs associating immigration with health risks, and left-leaning groups and civil society emphasising equality, social justice, and criticising discriminatory policies. Regarding returns, the Commission underscored their importance in preserving the current EU migration and asylum system, while progressive voices opposed deportation-focused policies, advocating for rights-based approaches. Migration was also often framed as a crisis and security issue, with right-wing groups emphasising the need for stricter border control and progressive actors prioritising aid, care and relief, and access to rights.

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	7
2. Methodology	7
2.1. Data sample	7
2.2. Semantic groups	9
2.3. Narratives, down-sampling, and qualitative analysis	11
3. The discursive construction of irregularity in the European Commission	12
3.1. Data sample	13
3.2. Quantitative analysis	13
3.2.1. High-frequency words	13
3.2.2. Semantic groups	14
3.2.3. Collocation analysis	18
3.2.4. VDL, Schinas, and Johansson: Keynes analysis	21
3.2.5. VDL, Schinas, and Johansson: Collocation analysis	22
3.3. Qualitative analysis	24
3.3.1. Proto-narratives	24
3.3.2. Migration and (ir)regularity	25
3.3.3. Employment	27
3.3.4. Gender	28
3.3.5. Covid-19	29
3.3.6. Return	30
3.3.7. Crisis and defence	31
4. The discursive construction of irregularity in the European Parliament	32
4.1. Data sample	33
4.2. Quantitative analysis	33
4.2.1. High-frequency words	33
4.2.2. Semantic groups	34
4.2.3. Collocation analysis	38
4.2.4. Political groups: Keynes analysis	41
4.3. Qualitative analysis	43
4.3.1. Proto-narratives	43
4.3.2. Migration and (ir)regularity (and illegality)	44
4.3.3. Employment	45
4.3.4. Gender	49

4.3.5. Covid-19	50
4.3.6. Return	51
4.3.7. Crisis and defence	52
5. The discursive construction of irregularity in civil society	53
5.1. Data sample	53
5.2. Quantitative analysis	54
5.2.1. High-frequency words	54
5.2.2. Semantic groups	55
5.2.3. Collocation analysis	59
5.3. Qualitative analysis	61
5.3.1. Proto-narratives	61
5.3.2. Migration and (ir)regularity	62
5.3.3. Employment	64
5.3.4. Gender	66
5.3.5. Covid-19	67
5.3.6. Return	68
5.3.7. Crisis and defence	69
6. Comparative insights	71
6.1. Keyness analysis	71
6.1.1. European Commission and European Parliament	71
6.1.2. European Commission and civil society	72
6.1.3. European Parliament and civil society	73
6.2. Critical assessment	75
6.2.1. Frequency and semantic groups	75
6.2.2. Thematic analysis	77
7. Concluding remarks	85
List of references	88

Table of Figures

Figure 1: Semantic group analysis for the European Commission (2019-2024) - visualised.....	17
Figure 2: Semantic group analysis for the European Parliament (2019-2024) - visualised.....	37
Figure 3: Semantic group analysis for the civil society corpus (2019-2024) - visualised	58

Table of Tables

Table 1: Semantic group analysis for the European Commission	16
Table 2: Semantic group analysis for the European Parliament.....	35
Table 3: Semantic group analysis in the civil society corpus	56
Table 4: Keyness Analysis - Commission and Parliament.....	71
Table 5: Keyness Analysis - Commission and civil society.....	73
Table 6: Keyness Analysis - Parliament and civil society.....	74
Table 7: Semantic group comparison (*migra*, irregular and refugee*)	78

1. Introduction

This Report analyses the narratives of the European Commission, the European Parliament, and EU-level civil society on *irregularised migration*. This comparative analysis reveals the nuances of the EU-level discourse on migration, where recurring themes of border control, residence status, rights and employment are interpreted through divergent lenses and with different meanings and implications.

The Report is based on a large-scale corpus analysis of text addressing irregularised migrants and migration. For each actor, data is analysed quantitatively and qualitatively to identify the frequency of specific words and themes, the correlation between different concepts, and the relevance, meaning, and implications of selected statements.

The main purpose of this Report is to analyse the ‘discursive construction of irregularity’, i.e., how different actors employ and promote specific narratives surrounding the topic of irregularity and lack of regular migration and/or residence status in Europe. In addition to this, the Report also covers broader themes related to labour migration, employment, gender, the effects of (and response to) the Covid-19 pandemic, returns, and ‘crisis’ narratives.

The Report is informed by the notion of *irregularity assemblages* (Gonzales et al., 2019; Sigona et al., 2021; I-CLAIM, 2023) whereby irregularity is not an intrinsic and fixed characteristic of some individuals but rather the result of a nexus of nested legal systems and political and public discourses on irregularity. These must be examined in the context of the specific labour market and welfare regimes unevenly impacting individuals depending on their national origin, gender, class, and belonging to racialised communities. Drawing on this and previous I-CLAIM research (Nare et al., 2024; Carrera & Colombi, 2024; Colombi et al., 2024), the Report refers to third-country-nationals (TCNs) without a regular immigration or residence status as *irregularised* people.

Section 6 on Comparative Insights presents the main findings for each actor, highlighting points of divergence or convergence across the discourses and narratives identified in the linguistic corpora built for the Commission, the Parliament, and civil society, and draws general conclusions that combine the quantitative and qualitative perspective.

2. Methodology

A detailed explanation of the methodology followed by this Report and the concurrent national ones is available on the I-CLAIM website (Rheindorf & Vollmer, 2025). This Section will be mainly limited to the relevant aspects for the EU-level analysis, as well as the deviations and adjustments for the EU context.

2.1. Data sample

The data sample includes a total of 2 223 documents – or 1 873 722 tokens. The keywords used to identify these documents were the following: ‘*migrant*’, ‘migration’ (also in combination with ‘irregular’ or ‘illegal’); ‘undocumented’; ‘clandestine’; ‘return*’; ‘expulsion*’; ‘Pact’; ‘work*’ in combination with ‘undeclared’, ‘seasonal’, ‘domestic’ and ‘platform’. The choice of these keywords is directly informed by

previous I-CLAIM research analysing the Legal and Policy Infrastructure of Irregularity in the European Commission (Carrera and Colombi, 2024) and relevant policy developments.

The data sample collected for each actor or set of actors (i.e., European Commission, European Parliament, and civil society) is described in detail in sections 3.1, 4.1, and 5.1 respectively. In line with concurrent I-CLAIM national reports', the timeframe of the EU Report is 'the 5 year period beginning 2019 to the end of 2023.

The data samples were analysed to assess: (a) the frequency of specific words and semantic groups (see below), i.e., how often they appear in the data sample in absolute terms; (b) the collocations between different words and semantic groups, i.e., how statistically likely it is for two words to appear in proximity to each other; and (c) their 'keyness', i.e., how statistically more likely is to find a word in a specific target corpus compared to a reference corpus.

Some methodological constraints must be highlighted with regard to European Parliament debates. First, the transcription of the debates held during the plenary sessions is available on the European Parliament website in the original languages spoken by the MEPs. This means that the 24 EU official languages may be represented across the different documents. To overcome this obstacle, a built-in browser translation software was used to translate multilingual documents. Using such tools does not guarantee that the nuances of each language are always captured and that the original meaning is preserved in the final English translation. Mitigation strategies, such as randomised quality checks, were adopted to ensure the highest possible level of accuracy and ensure that the analysis of the EU-level public debate was not limited to English-speaking MEPs only.

Secondly, while the availability of central databases for the European Commission and European Parliament allowed for a comprehensive—and therefore representative—collection of documents, the civil society corpus could only be compiled following a pre-selection of civil society organisations (CSOs). Due to the heterogeneity of these actors and the fragmentation of data sources, the results of the data analysis are heavily influenced by this pre-selection. Because of this, the report does not claim that the findings of this corpus are representative of the entirety of EU-level civil society discourse. Nonetheless, the prominence of the selected organisations in EU affairs, along with the inclusion of collective statements signed by hundreds of organisations who were not included in the initial pre-selection, provides valuable insights into prominent trends or perspectives within EU-level civil society, allowing for some generalisation within the scope of this analysis.

Additionally, it must be noted that the Commission and Parliament are not monolithic actors with respect to their discourses. Previous research has shown that, in the case of the Commission, disagreement can exist among Commissioners as well as among civil servants in the various Directorates-General and services (Carrera & Colombi, 2024). This EU-level report is uniquely placed to unpack the specificities and characteristics of the Commission's officials and parliamentary political groups (Sections 3.2.4 and 4.2.4). Based on quantitative analysis and its statistically significant findings, the Report does make claims concerning the discourse of these institutions as a whole, differentiating among different actors where relevant and appropriate. These claims must be understood however as a reflection of the general trends observed in the data sample collected and analysed for each actor for the purposes of this Report.

Finally, while this Report analyses the main lexical and discursive patterns and narratives of the three actors, it must be noted that the words and concepts used by the actors are not neutral and may often hide ideological positions or interests (Carrera & Colombi, 2024). The very framing of specific types of human mobility as ‘migration’ implies a securitarian and security-oriented outlook legitimising the intervention of specific institutional actors instead of others (e.g. home affairs and ‘migration’ institutional services over justice, non-discrimination, or employment institutional services) (ibid.). Similarly, the notion of ‘regular/legal pathways’ often acts as a way of delegitimising ‘unauthorised’ cross-border mobility – despite the modality of border crossing not having any effect on the validity of applications for asylum or other types of protection, or the fundamental rights of the people concerned. It may further be used to selectively legitimise the mobility of only some people instead of others, with racist, xenophobic and discriminatory undertones (ibid.). While the Report acknowledges the use of this politically-heavy yet seemingly-neutral language where appropriate, it does not do so on a systematic basis, as this would go beyond the scope of the present analysis (see Boswell, 2008; Carrera & Colombi, 2024).

2.2. Semantic groups

All significant words identified in the data sample were categorised into different semantic groups and more specific sub-groups. This systematic categorisation allows for a clearer analysis of how the different actors, the European Commission, European Parliament and civil society, engage with various thematic areas. In alphabetical order:

1. **Borders and Migration:** This group encompasses issues related to the control and management of borders, migration policies, and more generally all ideas related to the movement of people across borders. It includes terms related to visas, border management, immigration status, and residence status. The most frequent keywords include ‘migration’, ‘border’, ‘migrants’, ‘visa’, and ‘Schengen’.
2. **Crisis and Defence:** The Crisis and Defence semantic group reflects the framing of migration-related issues through a security lens, focusing on crisis management, defence policies, and the perceived threats associated with human mobility. It includes keywords such as ‘crisis’, ‘defence’, ‘risk’, ‘threats’, ‘emergency’, ‘combat’, and ‘instrumentalisation’. For the word ‘crisis’ specifically, it must be noted that the term is used with different meanings and implications, i.e., either as in ‘humanitarian crisis’ or with a security-oriented lens.
3. **Governance:** Governance refers to the structures, institutions, and policies that govern the European Union and Member States, as well as international politics. This category includes terms related to the EU’s institutions and their functioning, legislative processes, and policy frameworks. Subgroups include Policy, Legislation, Institutions, Politics and Names. Keywords here include ‘institutions’, ‘policy’, ‘legislation’, ‘governance’, and ‘EU’.
4. **IOs and NGOs:** This group focuses on the role of international organisations (IOs) and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) in the policy landscape. It includes discussions on the influence, activities, and contributions of these entities within the governance framework. Keywords in this group include ‘organisations’, ‘civil’, ‘UNHCR’, ‘IOM’, and ‘NGO’.

5. **Numbers and Quantities:** This group deals with the quantitative aspects of policy discussions, including statistical data, demographic figures, and numerical targets. Keywords associated with this group include numbers, i.e., 'one', 'million', etc., as well as more indeterminate quantities, i.e., 'several'.
6. **Obligations:** Obligations refer to the duties and responsibilities that different actors, including states and organisations, are expected to fulfil. This category is related to legal obligations, commitments, and duties within the European and international legal frameworks. Keywords include 'obligations', 'duty', 'responsible', 'obligation', and 'integration'².
7. **Policing and Crime:** This group focuses on issues related to security, law enforcement, and criminal activities. It captures discussions on public safety, counter-terrorism efforts, organised crime, and policing strategies. Keywords include 'security', 'authorities', 'crime', 'trafficking', and 'enforcement'.
8. **Return:** This group is concerned with the policies and practices surrounding the return or deportations of migrants to their countries of origin. The most frequent keywords include 'return', 'procedures', 'voluntary', 'reintegration', and 'expulsion'.
9. **Rights:** The Rights group includes terms related to fundamental rights, justice, human rights violations, and the EU founding values included in Article 2 TEU. Subgroups within Rights include Fundamental Rights, Justice, Asylum/Refugees, and Violations. Keywords such as 'rights', 'legal', 'justice', 'equality', and 'asylum' are prominent in this category.
10. **Subject:** The Subject group captures words related to social identity, lived experiences, and the representation of people. Keywords include 'their', 'people', 'children', 'family', and 'woman'.
11. **Time and Space:** The Time and Space group captures temporal and spatial elements within policy discussions. Keywords include specific locations (i.e., 'Europe', EU and non-EU countries, regions, cities), more general terms (e.g., 'countries', 'area') and time-related expressions (i.e., 'year')
12. **Welfare and Services:** This category includes terms related to social services, health care, education, housing, and social protection. Subgroups include Housing, Education, Health, Care and Relief, and Inclusion and Social Protection. Keywords include 'social', 'support', 'health', 'education', and 'housing'.
13. **Work and Economy:** The Work and Economy group encompasses issues related to employment, labour markets, and economic policies. Words in this category include 'employment', 'labour', 'economy', 'work', and 'market'.

² 'Integration' was included in this category as it is often used as a criterion for third-country nationals (TCNs) access to socio-economic rights. Previous research has underlined the exclusionary character of 'integration policies' at the EU level and the difference between 'integration' and other more inclusive notions, such as 'inclusion' (Carrera, 2009; Carrera & Colombi, 2024).

It is important to highlight that this division is only a heuristic device and, in some cases, is unavoidably arbitrary. Individual words can assume different meanings depending on their wider context and thus fall into multiple semantic groups.

Given that words are isolated from their context, any confusion was addressed on a case-by-case basis by checking the collocation value with other words (i.e., how often a word is used in conjunction with others). If the word appeared to be overwhelmingly used in only one sense, it was assigned to the semantic group most reflective of that meaning. However, if multiple possible meanings were identified, the collocation results were checked to determine how to split the word's overall frequency value across multiple semantic groups (e.g., 'procedure(s)' when combined with asylum in Rights, and with return in Return and Expulsions; 'security' with border in Borders and Migration, and with social in Welfare and Services; 'united' with nations in IOs and NGOs, and with kingdom/states in Time and Space, etc.).

2.3. Narratives, down-sampling, and qualitative analysis

Following the methodological note (Rheindorf & Vollmer, 2025), a 'narrative' is defined as a textual sequence of meaningful events that orders reality in a comprehensible way, inevitably leaving out certain things, focusing on others, and evaluating or judging aspects of reality. This 'ordering' or 'transformation' is referred to as 'emplotment'. Emplotment has been studied as a way of encoding ideology or *Weltanschauung* into even the simplest story.

The key elements of a narrative are characters (often, but not exclusively, the 'hero', 'villain', 'helper', and 'bystander'), setting or circumstance (including places, time periods), plot (the sequence of actions or events), means (tools, devices that help or hinder characters) and the moral (evaluation or judgment). This basic pattern is not always fully realised and may also be ambiguous. There are instances of discourse that – while still relevant as regards the meaning conveyed – cannot be qualified as narratives. This is the case for descriptions of states or conditions (ibid.).

Based on the collocation analysis of selected words (i.e., *migr³, irregular, refugee(s), etc.), actor-specific proto-narratives are identified in sections 3.3.1, 4.3.1, and 5.3.1. These proto-narratives are analytical abstractions based on quantitative results and seek to identify recurring patterns in the discourse of the European Commission, European Parliament, and civil society. The proto-narratives do not account for the internal fragmentation of these actors and are only used as heuristic devices.

Building on the proto-narratives and the salient themes identified, the Report then moves to a qualitative analysis. Selected excerpts from the three corpora are identified, based on their representative character, to give an overview of different themes and positions that are identifiable in the data sample. While informed by both the quantitative analysis and previous research, the choice of these statements remains to some extent arbitrary. They are analysed to further unpack the central narratives utilised by each actor, as well as their meaning and implications.

³ This includes the words *migration*, *migrants*, *migrant*, *migratory*, *immigration*, *immigrants*, *immigrant*, *migrate*, *migrating*, *emigrate*, and *emigration*.

Finally, section 6 (Comparative insights) brings together the main findings of the previous sections and, comparing the patterns identified for each actor and highlighting the significance and repercussions of the prevalent narratives in their discourse.

3. The discursive construction of irregularity in the European Commission

The European Commission plays a key driving role in the EU policy agenda-setting in areas related to migration (Carrera & Colombi, 2024). In addition to proposing new legislation, the Commission acts as the ‘guardian of the Treaties’ and must independently enforce EU law and take action against Member States in cases of non-implementation or misapplication of EU policy and its founding values (Kelemen & Pavone, 2022; Pech & Bárd, 2022)⁴. The Commission is one of the most influential inter-institutional actors at the EU level in the problematisation of relevant ‘policy issues’ and in the creation and (re)production of preferred policy solutions (Bacchi, 2012). It plays an active role in manufacturing and spreading dominant narratives and ways to speak within individual policy areas, including that of migration. The language used by the Commission is key to ‘unlocking’ specific legal competencies and, together with broader expert knowledge, acts a source of legitimisation for EU action in a given area of intervention (Boswell, 2008).

The Commission is composed of different bureaucratic services including the President, the College of Commissioners, the Commissioners’ Cabinets, the Secretariat General (SG), and the Legal Service, among others. In 2019–2024, the VDL I College of Commissioners included three Executive Vice-Presidents and three Vice-Presidents. The Commission also counts on several policy departments, called DGs, responsible for distinct policy fields. These DGs pursue different – and often competing – policy agendas, priorities, and understandings/perspectives, including on issues related to cross-border and intra-EU human mobilities (Carrera & Colombi, 2024).

In light of this internal heterogeneity, the present analysis zooms in on the discourse adopted by the highest political figures working on migration and mobility-related portfolios in the Commission. Firstly, it assess the discourse adopted by Commission President Ursula von der Leyen (VDL), who, during her first mandate, wielded substantial control over the policy direction and priorities of the Commission (ibid.).

Secondly, the Report considers the discourse of the Vice-President on Promoting our European Way of Life⁵, Margaritis Schinas, and Commissioner for Home Affairs, Ylva Johansson. The former was responsible for coordinating EU policies on migration, security, education, integration, and societal cohesion (European Commission, 2019a). Notably, his work included coordinating that of the 2024 Pact on Migration and Asylum (European Commission, 2024). Commissioner Johansson, on the other hand, was tasked with asylum, migration, and internal security. According to her mission letter (European Commission, 2019b), her responsibilities also included the Pact, reforming asylum rules, strengthening

⁴ Article 17.1 Treaty on the European Union (TEU).

⁵ The initial title of the portfolio was ‘*Protecting* our European way of life’, altered only after MEPs and civil society actors expressed their outrage. It was reported that ‘critics said [this portfolio] played into the hands of far-right extremists because the job includes management of migration and asylum policy, and might be viewed as suggesting that refugees pose a threat to the way Europeans live’ (de la Baume, 2019). At the time, the French extreme-right leader, Marine Le Pen, endorsed the title and called it an ‘ideological victory’.

external borders and ensuring a more coordinated approach to security issues such as terrorism and organised crime. Johansson was additionally charged with improving the Schengen Area, enhancing cooperation with non-EU countries on migration, and addressing both regular migration pathways and the fight against human trafficking. Johansson’s work was supported by the Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs (DG HOME) and was directly supervised by VP Schinas. Because of their portfolios, Schinas and Johansson were key figures in producing, promoting, and legitimising narratives on migration and human mobility at the EU level.

3.1. Data sample

For the European Commission corpus, 565 were public statements and press releases from the European Commission (859 351 tokens) were analysed. They were retrieved through the official website of the European Commission and relevant debates held at the European Parliament where Commission officials were represented. 298 statements are attributable to the Commission as a whole (in the form press releases, statements, and explanatory memoranda of legislative proposals set out in the selected timeframe – labelled in the qualitative analysis as *COM General*); 60 to President VDL; 39 to VP Schinas; and 137 to Commissioner Johansson.

3.2. Quantitative analysis

3.2.1. High-frequency words

The table below identifies the most frequent terms used in the European Commission’s statements included in the data sample, excluding filler words, such as articles, prepositions and modal verbs (‘the’, ‘and’, ‘that’, ‘will’, etc.).

Words	Rank	Normalised frequency
EU	9	10.133
Member	16	6.868
States	20	5.488
European	23	4.875
Our	27	4.065
Migration	28	3.938
Commission	29	3.830
Support	37	3.073
Countries	39	2.690
New	40	2.596
People	41	2.557
Union	44	2.413
Asylum	45	2.409
Need	46	2.349
Border	47	2.346
Work	50	2.266
Europe	53	2.024

Cooperation	57	1.849
State	58	1.844
National	59	1.836
Third	59	1.836
Rights	61	1.798
Directive	62	1.787
Protection	63	1.736
Return	65	1.698
Migrants	67	1.654
Country	68	1.609
Social	71	1.514
Labour	72	1.510
Measures	74	1.481

Based on the high-frequency word list, several preliminary observations can already be made. First, the presence of *EU*, *member*, *states*, *European*, *our*, *commission*, *union*, *Europe* indicates – as expected – the specific focus of the Commission on the EU as a whole and its Member States. *Directive* and *measures* further show significant attention paid to legal and policy instruments.

Second, the first non-EU-specific word is *migration*, which appears with nearly double the frequency of other terms like *asylum*, *border*, and *work*. *Migrants* is also represented as a high-frequency term, while *irregular* is not among the main results and only displays limited frequency in the data sample (0.990). *Support and cooperation* are also significant and might indicate both a focus on inter-Member States' dynamics and on EU cooperation with *third countries* (also present in this list) on migration-related issues. Other relevant words are *rights* and *protection*, which suggest the significant presence of legal and humanitarian⁶ concerns related to people on the move, as well as *return*, which may corroborate the expectation that the Commission highly favours returns as the main policy solution for TCNs without a regular immigration or residence status. Aside from *work*, other related terms include *social* and *labour*.

In the following sections, the Report will assess the frequency of these words, in relation to their specific semantic groups, to identify trends and what their high occurrence means.

3.2.2. Semantic groups

When it comes to the European Commission, the most frequently mentioned semantic word group is Governance, which has a total normalised frequency of 109.54. This group encompasses the subgroups Policy, Legislation, Politics, Institutions, and Names, with Institutions being the most notable at 45.342, followed by Policy at 38.463. The most common words in Governance are 'EU' (10.133), 'member' (6.868) and 'states' (5.488). Next is Time and Space, which includes the two subgroups Time and Geography, showing a high total normalised frequency of 44.292. Geography is particularly prominent within this

⁶ By 'humanitarian' we mean discourses centred on alleviating immediate suffering or 'saving lives', under the guise of compassion, without necessarily ensuring comprehensive human rights protections (see Moreno-Lax, 2017; see also Fassin, 2012).

group, with a normalised frequency of 27.493. 'Countries' (2.690), 'Europe' (2.023) and 'national' (1.836) are the most frequent words in Time and Space.

The Borders and Migration group follows, with a significant total normalised frequency of 39.756. The most frequent words within this semantic group are 'migration' (3.938), 'border' (2.346) and 'third' (mostly used as 'third-country nationals'; 1.836). The Rights semantic group, which includes subgroups such as Fundamental Rights, EU Values, Justice, Asylum/Refugees, and Violations, has a combined total normalised frequency of 35.033. Among these subgroups, Asylum/Refugees is the most prominent with a normalised frequency of 14.512. As regards individual words, 'asylum' (2.409), 'rights' (1.798) and 'protection' (1.736) rank as the most frequent in this semantic group.

Subject comes next, with a total normalised frequency of 25.964. This group includes discussions around Family/Household, Social Identity, Lived Experience, and People, with People⁷ being the most frequent subgroup at 12.867. 'Their' (3.513), 'people' (2.556), 'they' (2.340) and 'children' (1.164) are the most frequent words in the Subject semantic group. The Work and Economy group has a combined total normalised frequency of 23.055, split into Employment and Work, and Economy subgroups. Employment and Work is significantly more frequent at 18.444. The most frequent words in this semantic group are 'work' (2.266), 'labour' (1.510) and 'skills' (1.037).

The Welfare and Services group, which covers Housing, Education, Health, Care and Relief, and Inclusion and Social Protection, has a total normalised frequency of 20.453. Inclusion and Social Protection stands out within this group at 12.283. Among individual words, 'support' (3.073), 'social' (1.514) and 'access' (1.090) are the most frequent words. The Policing and Crime group shows a moderate level of attention, with a total normalised frequency of 13.233. 'Security', 'authorities' and 'trafficking' are the most frequent words in this semantic group at 1.147, 1.153 and 0.896 respectively.

The Crisis and Defence group has a total normalised frequency of 10.181 and encompasses words such as 'against'⁸ (0.920), 'challenges' (0.869) and 'crisis' (0.702). The Numbers and Quantities group has a total normalised frequency of 7.693, with 'one' (1.297), 'first' (1.019) and 'million' (0.891) being the most frequent words. The Returns and Expulsion group follows with a total normalised frequency of 4.665, including words such as 'return' (1.698), 'returns' (0.469) and 'voluntary' (0.447). The semantic group Obligations shows a total normalised frequency of 1.984 and includes words like integration (1.111), obligations (0.237) and responsible (0.230). Finally, the group with the lowest total normalised frequency is IOs and NGOs with a total normalised frequency of 1.453. While general terms like 'organisations' (0.406), 'civil' (0.382) and 'organisation' (0.114) are the most frequent words in this semantic group, the most frequently mentioned actors are UNHCR (0.078) and IOM (0.073).

This hierarchical presentation of frequencies highlights the varying degrees of attention given to different topics within the data for the European Commission, with Governance clearly standing out as the most discussed semantic group. A general conclusion that can be drawn from this overview is that – at least in

⁷ This semantic group includes indefinite personal pronouns (e.g., 'they', 'them'), possessives (e.g., 'their'), and words such as 'person(s)', 'individual', 'others', etc.

⁸ 'Against' was included in the Crisis and Defence semantic group because it is mostly used in combination with 'fight' (likelihood of 1078).

relation to migration – the European Commission tends to mostly speak about identified policy issues through a more technocratic and bureaucratic language (i.e., policy, legislation, etc.) and, only to a lesser extent, directly about the people that are affected by that policy issue. This is exemplified by the much lower total normalised frequency of the semantic group ‘Subject’ (25.964) as compared to Governance (109.54).

Table 1: Semantic group analysis for the European Commission

Semantic group	Subgroup	No of words	NormFreq	Total NormFreq
Governance	Institutions	56	45.342	109.54
	Policy	125	38.463	
	Legislation	46	17.274	
	Politics	37	7.171	
	Names	15	1.291	
Time and space	Geography	144	27.493	44.292
	Time	66	16.799	
Borders and migration	Status	23	14.153	39.756
	Borders	48	13.279	
	Entry	60	9.093	
	Residence	12	3.232	
Rights	Asylum/refugees	55	14.512	35.033
	Fundamental Rights	25	8.369	
	Justice	26	6.261	
	EU values	15	4.136	
	Violations	16	1.756	
Subject	People	15	12.867	25.964
	Social identity	37	6.476	
	Lived experience	23	4.638	
	Family/Household	9	1.983	
Work and Economy	Employment and work	63	18.135	22.745
	Economy	25	4.61	
Welfare and services	Inclusion and social protection	26	12.283	20.453
	Care and relief	10	4.13	
	Health	17	2.526	
	Education	6	1.095	
	Housing	3	0.419	
Policing and crime	Policing and crime	69	13.233	13.233
Crisis and defence	Defence	42	6.681	10.181
	Crisis	20	3.5	
Numbers and quantities	Numbers and quantities	25	7.693	7.693
Returns and expulsion	Returns and expulsion	18	4.665	4.665
Obligations	Obligations	7	1.984	1.984
IOs and NGOs	IOs and NGOs	13	1.453	1.453

Figure 1: Semantic group analysis for the European Commission (2019-2024) - visualised

3.2.3. Collocation analysis

The collocation analysis of the key terms – *migra*⁹, *irregular*, *refugee(s)*, and employment-related words such as *work*¹⁰, *labour*, and **employ*¹¹ – reveals distinct patterns in how migration and employment were framed in European discourse in 2019-2023. Across all categories, it is evident that the dominant focus was on borders and migration control, with significant attention paid to governance instruments and structures. Human rights and welfare issues were present but were often only secondary concerns, particularly as regards irregularised TCNs.

Migration

For collocations with **migra** terms, the semantic group of Borders and Migration emerges as the most prominent (sum likelihood of 4605.330). This indicates that terms related to cross-border movement, border control, and legal status tend to correlate among themselves, and less so with other semantic groups. The dominant collocation result is ‘*irregular*’ (2041.748) underscoring the Commission’s specific focus and preoccupation on people in a situation of irregularity compared to other types or aspects of cross-border mobility by TCNs.

The high presence of governance-related terms (3581.062), including ‘*Policy*’ and ‘*Legislation*’ suggests that, as expected, the discourse is heavily focused on the legal and policy framework for migration control (e.g. ‘*pact*’ at 939.411). The Rights semantic group, while present (1952.804), is very much limited to the Asylum/Refugees subgroup (i.e., terms such as ‘*asylum*’, ‘*refugees*’ and ‘*displacement*’) and much less or not at all linked to other subgroups, such as Fundamental Rights (78.673; including terms like ‘*right*’ and ‘*free*’¹²). Among the most prominent collocation results are ‘*asylum*’ (1625.34) and ‘*refugees*’ (165.294), which suggests an overall conflation and blurring of migration and asylum in the EU discourse – for example, in expressions such as the ‘*Pact on Migration and Asylum*’.

Migra words also show important collocations with the semantic groups Policing and Crime and Crisis and Defence with 1608.957 and 877.014 respectively. Significant results in the two groups are with ‘*smuggling*’ (1246.388) and ‘*instrumentalisation*’¹³ (244.017). Such associations suggest a discourse that problematises human mobility through the lens of criminality and geopolitics/defence, rather than through a rights-based or humanitarian perspective, and sidelines the lived experiences of the people in question.

⁹ This includes the words *migration*, *migrants*, *migrant*, *migratory*, *immigration*, *immigrants*, *immigrant*, *migrate*, *migrating*, *emigrate*, and *emigration*.

¹⁰ This includes the words *work*, *working*, *workers*, *worker*, *works*, *worked*, *workforce*, *workplace*, *workshops*, *workload*, *workable*, *workplaces*, *workshop*, *workflow*, *workflows*, *workstreams*, *workweek*, and *workwill*.

¹¹ This includes the words *employment*, *employers*, *employed*, *employer*, *unemployment*, *employees*, *employing*, *employ*, *employability*, *unemployed*, and *employs*.

¹² Mostly as ‘free movement’.

¹³ This term entered the EU migration debate around the events that took place in 2022-23 at the border between Belarus and Latvia, Lithuania and Poland and the involvement of Lukashenko’s regime in ‘facilitating’ irregular border crossing into the EU (for a critique, see Carrera et al., 2023).

Irregular

In the case of collocations with ‘irregular’, the dominance of the Borders and Migration group is even more pronounced (4049.913), with a clear focus on controlling entry into the EU and managing migration status.

The main collocation results are ‘migration’ (1230.389), ‘arrivals’ (923.004), ‘migrants’ (723.371) and ‘crossings’ (205.931). Most of the emphasis in the discourse seems to be on the specific act of crossing the border, on *preventing*, *reducing*, and *responding* to cross-border movements – as opposed to anything related to stay and residence. This is also proven by the greater prevalence of the semantic groups Crisis and Defence (466.173), particularly in relation to Defence, as well as Crime and Policing (243.150), predominantly in relation to smuggling and facilitation but also encompassing a more general idea of ‘illegal’, ‘crime’, and ‘(internal) security’. This reflects the strong securitisation of irregularised migration, its framing as a potential threat requiring defensive and preventative measures and the consistent links drawn between unauthorised cross-border movement and criminal activities.

‘Irregular’ only shows modest collocation results with the semantic groups on Rights (80.607) and Work and Economy (124.421). For the former, the main results is ‘displacement’ (62.903) and ‘exploitation’¹⁴ (17.704), which are tied respectively to forced displacement and work-related violations; for the latter, ‘employers’ (49.059), ‘employing’ (37.807), ‘workers’ (19.851) and again ‘exploitation’ (17.704). All of these words are exclusively used in relation to the Employers Sanctions Directive (2009/52/EC) and, therefore, criminal sanctions for people employing workers without regular immigration and residence status. Fairly frequent are also correlations with ‘Return and expulsion’ terms (68.812).

Refugee

The collocation analysis for the word ‘refugee’ reveals a different focus from other terms. ‘Time and Space’ emerges as the semantic group with the highest likelihood value (1249.037). The ‘Geography’ subgroup is particularly prominent, indicating that refugee discourse often focuses on the geographical origins and locations of refugees. Specific terms like ‘Turkey’ (440.845), ‘Syrian’ (251.546), ‘Venezuelan’ (147.254), and ‘Ukrainian’ (136.948) are notable within this group.

The frequent mention of Turkey, for instance, revolves around discussions about the significant number of refugees hosted there and the EU’s support for Turkey in managing these populations. This aligns with broader EU efforts to externalise refugee management, particularly through agreements like the EU-Turkey deal, thus offshoring the responsibility for large refugee populations outside of the EU’s borders. The prominence of Syrian, Venezuelan, and Ukrainian instead highlights the EU’s focus on selected events and, possibly, the higher visibility of *some* refugees compared to others across the Commission’s discourse.

Unlike for migration-related terms and ‘irregular’, the ‘Welfare and Services’ group (546.192) also plays an important role in the refugee-related discourse, with a significant focus on areas like inclusion and social protection. For example, words such as ‘support’, ‘welcome’, ‘assistance’ or ‘aid’ are significantly more

¹⁴ Exploitation is included in both the Rights semantic group (the Violations subgroup) and the Work and Employment semantic group (Employment and work subgroup).

prominent in this context¹⁵. Together with the higher sum frequency for Rights (286.319), this indicates a more rights-based approach when discussing refugees, in contrast to the securitised and control-oriented narratives often associated with irregular migrants.

Work and Employment

The analysis of employment-related terms (work*, labour, and *employ*) and their collocations also presents important insights. Here, employment and economy-related terms overwhelmingly dominate the discourse (8891.037), indicating that these words mostly correlate with other terms within the same semantic group – and not remotely as much with other semantic groups.

Among other things, this suggests that employment and migration are often treated as separate issues with limited overlap in the Commission's discourse. While there are discussions around employment policies and the economy, these are rarely linked directly to migration and even less so with irregularity. This is particularly interesting as the data sample was specifically constructed around the labour sectors analysed by the I-CLAIM project, i.e., platform work, seasonal work, and domestic work, which are highly dependent on third-country workers (see the keywords listed in Section 2). In this regard, it is important to point out that the first migration-related term among the collocation results is not 'migration' but in fact 'mobility'. In the EU legal and policy discourse, the two terms are used with vastly different meanings – the former encompassing TCNs and the latter limited to EU citizens with access to free movement within the EU or to very specific categories of TCNs (Carrera & Colombi, 2024).

Excluding 'Work and Employment', the sum likelihood for the other semantic groups appears to be more evenly spread with 'Welfare and services' at 765.863, 'Governance' at 728.282, 'Borders and Migration' at 644.102, 'Subject' at 639.413, 'Policing and Crime' at 457.217, and 'Rights' at 371.471. While possibly surprising, the presence of 'Policing and Crime' in this list is clearly due to the Employers' Sanctions Directive and related discussions on punishment for employers of irregularised TCNs.

Gender

Significant differences can be observed in how the Commission speaks about men, women, and children, particularly when focusing on migration-related discourse.

Overall, men are mentioned infrequently, with only 135 occurrences. Women are referenced nearly four times as often, with 499 occurrences, while children are mentioned 1 845 times, i.e., almost 14 times as much. Collocations for women frequently include terms like 'victims', 'vulnerable', 'exploitation', and 'violence'. These terms indicate a strong focus on women in relation to their social identity and lived experience, particularly within vulnerable or victimised contexts and through a humanitarian lens. Children, instead, appear in discussions around 'education', 'welfare', and 'protection'. These collocation results show a focus on the children's needs, particularly around family reunification and support systems, and rights.

¹⁵ While the Welfare and Service semantic group shows a likelihood of 546.192 with 'refugee', it is only at 51.719 with "migrat*" and 19.911 with 'irregular'.

As regards gender dynamics, the specific collocation results for the female-related terms and the much lower frequency of male-related terms in the corpus suggest that, when it comes to men, their gender is normally not spelt out. This implies that the attributes normally associated with the general term ‘migrant’ automatically apply to men. In other words, unless ‘female’ or ‘woman’ is specified, then a ‘migrant’ is more likely to be considered a subject to be managed, associated with policing and crime and notions related to crisis and defence (as discussed above in relation to ‘*migra*’ and ‘irregular’), than a ‘victim’ or somebody requiring protection due to gender-specific needs. This is not expressly acknowledged in the Commission’s texts themselves, and therefore is not visible in the quantitative data – it is rather an indirect product of the overall ‘silence’ around the concept of masculinity.

This reflects a pattern where the vulnerabilities and rights of women and children are central to the humanitarian discourse¹⁶ surrounding migration, while non-gender/age-related specific needs – which might still warrant subsidiary protection or other humanitarian residence permits – are completely sidelined.

3.2.4. *VDL, Schinas, and Johansson: Keyness analysis*

This section presents the results of a keyness analysis between statements by VDL, Johansson, and Schinas. This analysis identifies terms statistically more frequent or significant in a specific corpus compared to a reference corpus.

For VDL, the most prominent terms are ‘we’ (2237.756) and ‘our’ (1375.204). Terms like ‘Europe’ (575.41), and ‘world’ (327.78) also feature prominently, reflecting a geopolitical perspective. The presence of terms like ‘NextGenerationEU’ (204.287), ‘China’ (130.373), ‘industry’ (127.924), and ‘investment’ (115.636) suggests a strong emphasis on economic growth, the EU’s global standing, and future-oriented policies.

Considering that the statements were collected based on the keywords listed in Section 0, it is significant that words related to human mobility or rights (with the exception of ‘values’ – 81.851) do not show up in the top keyness results for VDL. While her statements touched upon these specific topics, otherwise they would not have been part of the data sample, VDL is statistically less likely to refer to such subjects compared to the Commission as a whole, Schinas, and Johansson. This may simply be the result of her scope of work being broader than those of individual Commissioners and her statements having a more strategic and agenda-setting character, thus covering multiple policy areas at once. As a consequence, non-mobility and non-migration-related words appear more statistically relevant because they are less prevalent in her statements than in the rest of the data sample.

For Vice-President Schinas, key terms also begin with ‘we’ (428.135) and ‘our’ (212.062). ‘Pact’ (95.689), and ‘migration’ (79.381) feature significantly high among the keyness results, reflecting Schinas’s key role in the promotion of the 2024 Pact on Migration and Asylum (European Commission, 2024). This also includes keywords related to the legislative process and specific Pact files, such as ‘proposals’ (42.979), ‘solidarity’ (35.415), and ‘returns’ (34.819). The term ‘Schengen’ appears with a keyness of 51.514, highlighting his concern with the Schengen Area and border management. ‘Croatia’, the latest Member State to join the Schengen Area, is also prominent with a keyness of 67.210. Schinas’s discourse appears to be mostly concentrated on questions of border management and defence-like considerations, as also evidenced by

¹⁶ See footnote no. 6.

the presence of ‘Evros’ (25.168) – the main land border crossing point between Greece and Turkey where tensions escalated in 2020 and again in 2022 between the Greek authorities, the Turkish authorities, and people seeking to cross the border (HRW, 2020; Euronews, 2022).

Like VDL and Schinas, Commissioner Johansson's key terms include ‘we’ (2273.463). Ranking significantly high is ‘people’ (548.033), reflecting the higher likelihood of Johansson directly referring to the asylum-seekers and refugees themselves. ‘Need’ (368.373) and ‘must’ (253.427) show the higher prevalence of obligations and necessities in Johansson’s discourse and the emphasis on decisive action and commitments by the EU and Member States on EU values and fundamental rights¹⁷. Similarly, ‘help’ shows a high keyness value (128.049).

Like Schinas, border management features highly in Johansson’s discourse as exemplified by words such as ‘Schengen’ (251.361) and ‘manage’ (198.446). Among the highest-ranking words, one can also find ‘Putin’ (145.359) and ‘Lukashenko’ (141.526), which is explained by the involvement of the two foreign leaders in displacement and mobility-related challenges following the Russian invasion of Ukraine and at the borders between Belarus and Latvia, and Lithuania and Poland. The word ‘smugglers’ is also present among the main results with a keyness value of 122.927.

The analysis of these keyness results demonstrates the distinct approaches of the three leaders. VDL's discourse is more geopolitical and broader in thematic scope. Schinas focuses on legal frameworks and agreements, primarily the 2024 Pact on Migration and Asylum, as well as border management and border control. Johansson's approach appears to be more humanitarian (i.e., focused on saving lives but not necessarily granting rights), more focused on needs and obligations and, like Schinas, on border management.

3.2.5. VDL, Schinas, and Johansson: Collocation analysis

The **collocation analysis with “*migr*”¹⁸** confirms significant differences in focus among VDL, Schinas, and Johansson.

For VDL, the collocation analysis with “*migr*” reveals a focus on the regulatory and preventive aspects of the management of irregularised migration. Key collocates include ‘irregular’ (likelihood: 166.922), ‘asylum’ (164.519), ‘pact’ (156.883), and ‘smuggling’ (88.224), indicating a strong emphasis on controlling and reducing irregularised cross-border human mobility and combatting smuggling operations. These collocations may also confirm an overall tendency to conflate migration with other phenomena (e.g., asylum or smuggling) that are normatively and qualitatively distinct¹⁹. The frequent mention of ‘manage’

¹⁷ ‘Second, in all situations, people must be treated with dignity and respect for fundamental rights. (...) We must do everything in our power to save lives in partnership with countries of origin and transit, and treat people with respect and according to their rights’. (P Johansson 04-07-2022); ‘Member States must protect the EU external borders and uphold fundamental rights’ (P Johansson 05-05-2022).

¹⁸ This includes words like *migration*, *migrants*, *migrant*, *migratory*, *immigration*, *immigrants*, *immigrant*, *migrate*, *migrating*, *emigrate*, and *emigration*.

¹⁹ Migration is not an equivocally defined term in legislation; asylum is a non-derogable human right under international and EU primary law; and smuggling is a crime against the state under international law implying ‘procurement, in order to obtain, directly or indirectly, a financial or other material benefit, of the illegal entry of a person into a State Party of which the person is not a national or a permanent resident’ (see [UN, 2000](#)). It also must be noted that, at the EU and national level, the notion of ‘smuggling’ has

(54.528), ‘management’ (45.813), and ‘managing’ (36.939), as well as ‘preventing’ (16.029), underscores VDL’s insistence on border management strategies and the alleged need to curtail irregularised cross-border human mobility.

Equally relevant collocation results are ‘challenge’ (39.416) – which is explained by VDL’s insistence on migration and its management being ‘a European challenge’ – and ‘instrumentalisation’ (19.764). The prominence of the latter suggests VDL’s tendency to read and frame human mobility through a geopolitical, defence-like and securitarian lens as opposed to a fundamental rights and justice-based approach (ibid.).

Finally, ‘employers’ (27.248) is the only employment-related term among the results. It is exclusively used in relation to the Employers’ Sanctions Directive and therefore the criminalisation of people employing irregularised TCNs. The absence of ‘legal’, ‘regular’ or equivalent terms is interesting as it suggests a lesser focus on promoting pathways compared to other aspects – or, possibly, the exclusive juxtaposition of ‘*migra*’ terms to irregularised border mobility, asylum, smuggling, border management, and foreign policy challenges, while adopting different terms when speaking of topics like pathways, regular employment, etc.

When examining collocations with ‘irregular’, the emphasis in VDL’s discourse remains consistent. Words like ‘migrants’ (likelihood: 95.788) and ‘migration’ (73.854) emerge as prominent. Other significant collocates include ‘arrivals’ (23.953), ‘departures’ (27.128), and ‘crossings’ (16.396). The presence of terms such as ‘preventing’ (21.898), ‘swift’ (19.172), and ‘stricter’ (18.08) reflects a narrative focused on stringent control of human mobility and the need for return procedures. Additionally, terms like ‘employers’ (35.429) and ‘employing’ (16.396) point to the administrative and legal measures targeting those who employ irregular migrants, in line with her emphasis on the Employers’ Sanctions Directive.

The collocation results for VP Schinas show divergent results in this case. The most prominent collocation result is, in fact, the term ‘legal’ (96.078), which Schinas mostly uses to underline the importance of ‘*legal migration*’ and ‘*legal pathways and integration*’ (sic)²⁰ for the EU and their (alleged) centrality in the 2024 Pact. Similarly to VDL, the terms ‘asylum’ (69.601) and ‘pact’ (39.757) follow suit. The term ‘irregular’ (18.325) also appears, pointing to his concern with irregularised human mobility and the measures required to ‘curb’, ‘prevent’ and ‘address’ it. Aside from ‘system’ (16.385) and ‘policy’ (16.331), which merely confirm Schinas’s focus on the EU’s migration and asylum system/policy, the presence of ‘labour’ (15.980) is worthy of note among the main collocation results, which confirms Schinas’s greater focus on regular pathways and labour mobility in response to the EU’s economy’s needs.

Regarding the term ‘irregular’, Schinas’s collocation results are limited to the words ‘biggest’ (22.736), ‘migration’ (21.443) and ‘pull’ (19.165). They are all used in the context of the problematic notion of ‘pull factor’ (see for example de Haas, 2011).

been often used in bad faith against all types of assistance, including by NGOs and individuals and without a financial or material benefit, to further restrict ‘unauthorised border crossings’, leading to more danger and violence for people on the move (see [PICUM, 2022](#)).

²⁰ In the present report, we refer to the same concepts as ‘regular’ migration and ‘regular’ pathways to avoid the legal/illegal dichotomy, in line with UN standards and the concerns raised by civil society organisations. See Carrera & Colombi, 2024; [UNGA 1976](#); and [PICUM, 2017](#).

Johansson's corpus shows a higher frequency of migration-related terms (37 results compared to Schinas's 13 and VDL's 20), reflecting her specific responsibility for this issue and consequent higher variety of juxtapositions between “*migra*” and other words. Overall, her results confirm the more humanitarian approach²¹ to human mobility identified in the keyness analysis. Like for VDL and Schinas, key results are ‘asylum’ (301.305), ‘manage’ (259.456), and ‘pact’ (181.577).

The next highest ranking result is ‘normal’ (147.890), which is explained by Johansson's consistent argument that ‘migration is (something) normal’ (for more insights, see Section 3.3). This is further proven by the presence, further down the list, of words like ‘always’ (86.785; migration described as something ‘which has *always* been there’) and ‘society’ (18.285; to underline that ‘migrants are part of society’, as well as the need for mutual support between migrants and the hosting society, and migrants' contribution to society and migration as a response to an ageing European society).

For Johansson, ‘irregular’ shows a likelihood of 128.985, ‘regular’ of 88.699, and ‘legal’ of 50.583. Border management and the need to control human mobility is once again prominent, i.e., ‘management’ (53.598), ‘managing’ (35.569), ‘Schengen’ (31.640), ‘orderly’ (25.901), and ‘reducing’ (19.022). Other significant words are ‘smuggling’ (46.893), ‘partnerships’ (32.626) – which relates both to the Talent Partnerships and partnerships with non-EU countries to ‘manage migration’ –, and ‘integration’ (18.253).

When it comes to collocations with ‘irregular’, Johansson's discourse highlights ‘arrivals’ (427.143), ‘departures’ (77.187), and ‘fewer’ (53.721), indicating a focus on cross-border movement and the need to reduce unauthorised entry into the EU. The presence of terms like ‘preventing’ (42.288), ‘prevent’ (41.466), and ‘reduce’ (38.242) aligns with her preventive approach to irregular migration, while ‘risks’ (26.028) and ‘smugglers’ (24.151) underscore her focus on the dangers of unauthorised border crossings and their modalities. The collocate ‘regular’ (22.165) is also notable as Johansson often juxtaposes the two terms to signal the need to improve regular pathways to counter irregular cross-border mobility.

3.3. Qualitative analysis

3.3.1. *Proto-narratives*

One of the key findings in the analysis of the Commission corpus is that policymakers tend to speak about social phenomena through a heavily policy- and legislation-dominated language. This pattern may be a consequence of the Commission's role as the initiator of EU legislation in this domain, and the Treaties' requirement to justify ‘more EU’ in any given policy area (value added, subsidiarity and proportionality). Even though ‘migration’ falls under shared EU-Member State competence, the Commission's role has been largely contested and controversial, including its relations with EU Member States. The predominant policy/legalistic language may reflect the Commission's caution around what and how it says what it does, and is planning to do, in these domains to legitimise its action in such a policy salient area (Boswell, 2008; see also Carrera & Colombi, 2024)

The main consequence is that the Commission's discourse does not always contain narratives (i.e., a subject, action verb, setting, or means). Rather, it more descriptive, passive, or centred around the Commission's actions, legal, and policy instruments, their purpose, functioning and implementation – i.e.,

²¹ See footnote no. 6.

'the purpose of this policy is x'; 'this proposal aims at doing y'. This also includes more normative ('must'/'have to'/'need' statements) and future-oriented language in the context of the new policy and legislation instruments put forward by the Commission in the last legislature. A moral or message is nonetheless always present.

Based on the statistical analysis, the proto-narratives below have been extracted from the more descriptive discourse. They were made more action-oriented and do not necessarily always reflect the original 'way of speaking' of policymakers and officials.

- *The European Union must strengthen border management to prevent irregular migration, ensure people's safety, including through partnerships with third countries and combat smuggling of migrants and trafficking of human beings.*
- *The EU must enhance legal pathways to attract talent and skilled workers to support innovation, competitiveness and address labour market needs.*
- *The EU is protecting the rights of refugees and asylum seekers.*
- *Effective integration policies empower migrants and refugees to fully participate in society, but require their integration and respect to our values.*
- *The EU must work on more effective returns for people who have no right to stay.*

Based on the evidence gathered through the quantitative analysis and the proto-narratives identified above, this Section will now collect and assess individual statements by the European Commission on the topics of migration and (ir)regularity, employment and gender, as well as other relevant topics such as Covid-19, returns, and crisis and defence.

3.3.2. Migration and (ir)regularity

The selected statements below show the VDL I Commission's approach on regular migration and the prevention of irregular migration:

It is very important to return irregular migrants to break the narrative of the smugglers and to send out the strong message that it is the legal pathways that will bring you to Europe, and choose them. (VDL 06-10-2023)

Creating legal pathways for migration not only has economic benefits; it can help reduce irregular and unsafe migration as well as the human and economic costs associated with smuggling and trafficking. (COM General 18-12-2022)

The better we are in legal migration, the more convincing we can be in preventing irregular migration (VDL 28-11-2023).

All three statements framed 'irregular migration' as a problem to be solved through returns and 'legal' (or better, regular) pathways. VDL's first statement emphasised that returning irregular migrants is crucial to undermining smugglers' narratives and promoting regular pathways. The framing of 'regular migration'²² as a more attractive and preferable alternative to irregular routes was repeatedly emphasised, suggesting

²² The notion of 'regular migration' is also the result of a non-neutral and restrictive framing of the broader category of 'human mobility'. Only some types of mobility are understood as 'migration' or as 'regular', reflecting underlying ideological positions, institutional 'ways of seeing things' and oft-discriminatory assumptions (see Carrera & Colombi, 2024).

that the Commission saw the establishment of ‘regular pathways’ as instrumental in controlling cross-border mobility. The statements clearly prioritised border control and deterrence over other issues, as well as a selective and utilitarian approach to regular migration.

However, this narrative is somewhat contradictory. Despite implying that the effectiveness of preventing irregular migration is directly tied to the success of regular migration frameworks, the reality is that the EU’s current legislation and policies have not substantially expanded the available regular pathways (see also Employment below), which particularly affects people from certain world regions. This approach risks marginalising those who do not fit into the ‘legal’ categories favoured by current EU policies, reinforcing a selective and exclusionary migration system.

Additionally, these statements reveal a lack of consideration for evidence showing that restrictive border and visa policies, in the absence of ‘effective regular pathways’ for labour and regular mobility for TCNs, contribute to pushing people towards ‘irregular’ routes into the EU and, therefore, increase their reliance on smugglers (see Nare et al., 2024).

Moreover, the Commission’s emphasis on ‘returns’ and ‘regular pathways’ did not sufficiently address the complex factors driving irregularised migration or question whether the policies in place are co-constitutive of this phenomenon. By focusing predominantly on control measures, the discourse overlooked human rights obligations and the rights of asylum-seekers and migrants under national, EU, and international law and reproduced discriminatory and racist assumptions behind the very label of ‘migrant’.

The statement below by Vice-President Margaritis Schinas is also indicative of how migration and integration have been seen by the Commission:

Legal migration is a two-way street. We in the European Union will allow for legal avenues, we will admit migrant workers, we will work to improve their conditions and we will struggle to give them fair access to our systems, but they should also accept our rules, our values and our model of society. This is the two-way street that we need. Those who come to Europe need to accept and respect the role of women in the family, in society and in the workplace. They should accept the need for peaceful co-existence, for religious freedom and tolerance and for full respect of the ethical rules that govern living in Europe. (Schinas 23-11-2021)

VP Schinas framed ‘migration’ as a reciprocal process, emphasising that while the EU offers legal avenues and strives to improve conditions for ‘migrants’, there is an expectation that migrants will assimilate by accepting European values and societal norms. In the statement above, he specifically focused on the role of women, peaceful coexistence, religious freedom, tolerance, and respect for the ethical rules that govern life in Europe. The underlying assumption that emerges from such a statement is that at least part of the people in question (i.e., migrant workers) do not respect these principles.

This approach is closer to assimilation than to inclusion and sheds a negative light on multiculturalism and diversity, contrasting with the EU’s commitments to equality, non-discrimination, respect for fundamental rights, as well as its founding values. By placing the onus on migrants to accept and respect European values, the discourse overlooks the barriers TCNs face, such as (oft-institutionalised and structural) discrimination or xenophobia, which can impede successful integration regardless of individual willingness (see Carrera, 2009).

3.3.3. Employment

When it comes to employment, the only correlation between irregularised TCNs and employment in the Commission's corpus appears to be 'illegal' employment, exploitation, and criminal activities.

Illegal employment also exposes migrants to risks of violation of individual and social rights, notably labour exploitation, precarious living and working conditions and limited or no access to social protection. (COM General 29-09-21)

In some cases labour exploitation can also have links to serious and organised crime, either through trafficking in human beings for labour exploitation or exploitation of irregular migrants by smuggling networks through debt bondage (...) and exploitative work conditions (ibid.)

In the statements above, there is an acknowledgement of the precarious conditions and vulnerability that might emerge in such situations, i.e., violations of individual and social rights, labour exploitation, and precarious living and working conditions. There is however no real suggestions or thought about safe and regular employment alternatives or the respect of international and EU labour standards, which protect 'all workers' – not only those with regular immigration, residence, and/or employment status.

It is significant that no real correlation emerges between irregularised human mobility and topics such as domestic, seasonal, and platform work. This shows that, even when the EU engages in discussions on labour sectors in which irregularised TCNs make up a significant part of the workforce, it does not discuss the rights and working conditions of these people.

To attract the skills and talent that we need, the EU has to build a more attractive and efficient system (COM General 27-04-2022)

Therefore, (...) attracting talent and skills from outside the EU is a way to contribute to addressing existing and future labour and skills shortages, including those linked to the green and digital transition. It also incentivises potential economic migrants to come to the EU through legal channels, which contributes to reducing irregular migration pressure. (COM General 15-11-2023)

But of course, legal migration is not only about highly-skilled workers (Schinas 19-05-2021)

The emphasis on attracting 'skills and talent' well exemplifies the European Commission's view of migration as a way to address labour and skills shortages, maintain competitiveness, and address demographic challenges. This is however only limited to the specific workers that *the EU needs*, when and if it needs them, and through selective instruments, such as the Talent Partnerships. The last statement by VP Schinas thus appears particularly contradictory – especially in light of the overall approach of the Pact on Migration and Asylum and the lack of new effective regular pathways. Both the Pact and broader EU migration policy remain heavily focused on attracting 'talent' and 'skills', inherently sidelining blue-collar workers (Carrera & Colombi, 2024).

This selective focus on 'high-skilled' migration reinforces the exclusion of all other workers from the benefits of regular migration channels, revealing a persistent gap between rhetorical inclusivity and policy realities. This is further compounded by the fact that irregularised TCN workers who are already employed in the EU are excluded from the personal scope of existing instruments, such as the Seasonal Workers Directive (2014/36/EU) and the Platform Workers Directive (2024/2831).

Furthermore, the Commission's discourse did not acknowledge the essential contributions of irregularised migrants in sectors facing significant labour shortages, such as agriculture, care work, and hospitality (see also Section 3.3.5 on Covid-19). By not addressing the need for regularisation mechanisms or broader legal pathways for low-skilled workers, the EU risks perpetuating exploitative labour practices and undermining the rights of a substantial segment of the workforce.

3.3.4. Gender

When looking at the European Commission's statements, it is clear they focus heavily on women and gender-specific vulnerabilities, especially regarding human trafficking.

Trafficking is a crime against women and girls. Women and girls, who are manipulated. Women and girls, who are exploited. Women and girls, who are treated as a product. As a commodity. Who are bought and sold. Women and girls, who are forced into prostitution. Forced to have sex. Women and girls, who are raped. Because most victims, are women and girls. 72 per cent of victims. And most trafficking is about sexual exploitation: 60 per cent. And 92 per cent of victims exploited for sex, are women and girls. As I said, nearly three quarters of victims are women. And more than two thirds of perpetrators are men. So we need to talk about gender. Traffickers force, pressure or trick vulnerable girls into prostitution. Imagine a young girl, insecure and vulnerable. Maybe growing up in a home with problems. With parents absent, or with alcohol or drug problems. She's young. Maybe she still believes a bit in fairy tales. Like Belle and the Beast, the story of the monster, who turns into prince charming. Only here it's prince charming, who turns into a monster. A smooth talking boyfriend, who seeks her out – perhaps after grooming on Internet. He showers her with attention, gifts and promises of a new life abroad. And then forces her into prostitution, abuses her, beats her. Isolates her from friends and family. Until she is a prisoner. Working together in Europe, we are taking action against these crimes. (Johansson 12-10-2021).

This statement by Commissioner Johansson highlighted the specific dangers faced by women and girls, framing trafficking as a serious crime that predominantly impacts them. It pointed out that these women and girls are not just manipulated and exploited, but are treated like commodities. In the statement, 'a young girl, insecure and vulnerable girl' who believes in fairytales is exposed to a 'smooth talking', 'prince charming' turned-monster boyfriend. The statements sought to emphasise the harsh realities young, vulnerable girls face when traffickers prey on their insecurities and the consequent exploitation and gender-based violence that might ensue.

Another statement, also by Johansson, dug deeper into the challenges migrant women face:

I would like to focus on women because women are the most important part here, I think. When migrant women do well, their children are more likely to do well too. But at the same time, we know that migrant women are facing bigger obstacles than migrant men. And Nicolas also spoke about this. Migrant women are more likely to be in a part time job or a vulnerable job or temporary job. Migrant women are more likely to be employed at too low a level, far below their competence level. And they're also more likely to be without jobs. Too often we see migrant women stay at home to take care of children, the household or sick or disabled family members. And that means migrant women do not really take part in society to the extent that they should. (Johansson 30-11-2021)

The statement recognised that migrant women often encounter greater obstacles than men, finding themselves in part-time, temporary, or vulnerable jobs for which they are overqualified, or else unemployed. This brings to light not just gender disparities but also how socioeconomic status and caregiving duties disproportionately affect migrant women, holding them back from fully participating in society (see Kofman et al., 2000; Teodorescu, 2024).

As previously noted, attention on women is coupled with an emphasis on children:

The EU should provide smuggled migrants, in particular vulnerable groups such as children and women, with assistance and protection. (...) Smuggled migrants are at great risk of losing their lives or experiencing harm during their journey. Their fundamental rights are often gravely violated through abuse and exploitation. Providing protection and assistance to smuggled vulnerable migrants is key, with a particular attention to children and women, including within the framework of the EU strategies on victims' rights 2020-2025 and on Combatting Trafficking in Human Beings 2021-2025, as well as the EU Strategy on the rights of the child. (COM 29-09-2021)

This last statement, from the Commission's renewed EU action plan against migrant smuggling (2021-2025) (European Commission, 2021), highlighted the urgent need for support and protection for 'vulnerable groups', especially women and children. It underscored the dangers they face during their journeys, including serious human rights violations. The Commission seemed to be pushing for gender-sensitive approaches in EU strategies on victims' rights and combating trafficking. Nonetheless, this approach again essentialised the notion of 'vulnerability' to women and children, paying less attention to other equally-valid criteria and concerns, such as physical and mental health status, being part of the LGBTIQ+ community, etc. The overall absence of other categories of people underscores a troubling narrative that reduces femininity to victimhood – and vice versa – and perpetuates a gendered and age-specific perception of vulnerability that might take away agency from women and children and exclude other valid grounds for protection and special reception needs (see Hyndman & Giles, 2011; Turner, 2019; Sachseder et al., 2024).

3.3.5. Covid-19

In the timeframe examined (2019-2023), a key topic for exploration was the Covid-19 pandemic and, more specifically, the relationship between the pandemic and irregularised TCNs; their rights, wellbeing, and living and working conditions as featured in the data sample.

The pandemic hit migrants and refugees disproportionately. (...) Migrants are not 'them', they are part of 'us'. And I think this was very obvious in the pandemic. (Johansson 29-10-2022)

Covid shows migrants are part of society. But also shows, that ours is not an equal society. And Covid is deepening these inequalities. (Johansson 31-03-2021)

Commissioner Johansson's discourse prominently featured discussions about migrants and the impacts of the pandemic on them. Her rhetoric positioned migrants as integral to the fabric of European society and essential to its economy, but portrayed them primarily as contributors to economic growth rather than as rights-holders.

There was a considerable absence of any mention of irregularised or undocumented migrants. The focus was predominantly on the general category of migrants, with a specific emphasis on regular migration, particularly in the context of global talent, skills shortages, and entrepreneurial capacity (see above). Despite this, Johansson did acknowledge issues of inequality, suggesting some awareness of the broader social challenges facing TCNs in Europe.

In the same statements, Johansson also referenced the Action Plan on Integration and Inclusion (European Commission, 2020), which is a clear example of the omission of irregularised migrants. It notably excludes any explicit mention of TCNs without regular immigration or residence status, despite directly referencing an OECD study (2020) that does explicitly address—albeit minimally—the situation of irregularised migrants. In previous occasions, Commission officials justified such lack by referring to the Treaties' legal bases and their limiting the scope of such discussions within EU policy frameworks (Carrera & Colombi, 2024).

3.3.6. Return

As outlined from the high-frequency-word list, 'return' is one of the most highly-frequency terms in the Commission corpus. Despite this, it only featured in a very limited manner in the semantic groups and collocation analysis. Previous research has shown that return is often presented as the key policy option to respond to irregularised migration (Carrera & Colombi, 2024). Because of this, narratives around return need to be further explored.

Ensuring the return of irregular migrants is essential in order to enhance the credibility and sustainability of the EU and Member States' policies in the field of migration. (COM General 23-09-2020)

Irregular migrants who have no protection needs, or no intention to apply for international protection should be quickly channelled into the return procedure. (COM General 23-0-2020)

The statement that ensuring returns is essential for the credibility and sustainability of EU and Member State policies highlights the VDL I Commission's conviction that effective return mechanisms are vital to maintaining public trust and legitimising the broader migration framework. This approach suggests that without robust enforcement, other aspects of migration policy, such as legal pathways or protection measures, might be viewed as lacking legitimacy, integrity, or effectiveness.

However, this focus on returns does not take into account the reality that the majority of irregular migrants cannot be returned (Carrera & Colombi, 2024). The challenges of implementing returns, including legal, logistical, and diplomatic barriers, are clearly overlooked in such policy statements. Moreover, the insistence that irregular migrants without protection should be swiftly channelled into return procedures ignores the existence of other alternatives within EU law: most importantly, the possibility under Article 6 of the Return Directive (2008/115/EC) of granting residence permits on humanitarian grounds to non-returnable TCNs. Despite their availability, alternatives are not uniformly implemented and enforced across Member States, further complicating the EU's approach to managing irregular migration (ibid.).

Despite this, returns are consistently portrayed by the Commission as the most desirable solution to irregularised migration. This has in turn sidelined all discussions around the rights and living and working conditions of TCNs who are already in the EU.

3.3.7. Crisis and defence

The Commission's discourse reflects a securitisation of migration, particularly in the context of geopolitical tensions with neighbouring countries like Belarus and Turkey.

We are very concerned about the situation at the borders with Belarus. We consider the behaviour of the Belarus government as a hybrid attack. The people used by Lukashenko are victims. We must help them. No one's life should be used for political issues. This is an instrumentalisation of migration – to put political pressure on the European Union. (VDL 22-10-2021)

The situation at our border is not only Greece's issue to manage. It is the responsibility of Europe as a whole. And we will manage it in an orderly way, with unity, solidarity and determination. Those who seek to test Europe's unity will be disappointed. We will hold the line and our unity will prevail. Now is the time for concerted action and cool heads and acting based on our values. Turkey is not an enemy and people are not just means to reach a goal. We would all do well to remember both in the days to come. I thank Greece for being our European ασπίδα [English: shield] in these times. (VDL 03-03-2020)

Following the European Council conclusions of 24-25 May 2021 and in response to the increasing role of State actors in facilitating irregular migration and using human beings to create pressure at the EU's external borders, the EU and its Member States have expressed their strong determination, and have acted jointly, to respond to these threats and effectively, protect the EU's external borders against the instrumentalisation of migration for political purposes. (COM General 29-0-2021)

President VDL characterised the actions of the Belarusian government as a 'hybrid attack', framing migration as a tool of warfare or political coercion. The TCNs affected were acknowledged as victims in this scenario. Yet, the primary focus remains on protecting EU borders and responding to perceived threats, with the 'victims' turning into pawns controlled by a foreign agent and that must be stopped. Similarly, in the case of Turkey, Greece was thanked for being the 'shield' of Europe – i.e., for protecting Europe from an external threat (see Carrera et al., 2023). VDL suggested that, while these third countries were trying to test Europe's unity, the EU would be able to respond in a concerted way respecting the EU's values. Similar points were reiterated in the last statements by the Commission as a whole.

When it comes to the notions of 'crisis' and 'threat', Commissioner Johansson seemed to adopt softer tones with less of a security framing:

'(...) migration is not a threat. Migration is something that we need, but we need to manage migration and we need to welcome people on legal ways, but we need to prevent irregular arrivals and the risk of people's lives'. (Johansson 23-11-2022)

We should be proud Europeans. We should act in line with our values. We should act as global leaders. Migration is normal. Of course, it has to be managed, and to be able to do so we need to agree on a common European migration policy. To be able to agree on a common migration policy we need to de-dramatise migration policy. The EU is not in a migration crisis, but some migrants are in crisis. But we are policymakers, and you are legislators, and we are able to give support and respect the dignity and rights of people. (Johansson 17-09-2020)

Johansson noted that migration itself is not a threat and emphasised the need for managed, regular migration. An insistence on curbing 'irregular arrivals' remained, with the aim of reducing risks for the

TCNs affected. Her second statement, instead, emphasised that the EU was not in a migration crisis, but that ‘some migrants’ were in crisis, shifting the focus towards more rights-centred concerns. Johansson remarked that EU actions in this area should follow EU values, and the discussion surrounding migration should be ‘de-dramatised’, i.e., the crisis narrative should be toned down. According to her, migration should be managed collectively to ensure necessary support and respect the dignity and rights of TCNs.

Even when acknowledging the unsafety and danger TCNs are exposed to during their journeys, the quantitative data and overall sample of statements reveal that the overarching narrative continued to prioritise border protection and control. This approach risks reinforcing the perception of TCNs as threats to be stopped, security risks or pawns in geopolitical struggles, or as a crisis to be resolved, rather than as individuals with rights and needs. The emphasis on ‘instrumentalisation’, ‘threats’, and ‘crisis’ overshadowed the EU’s obligations to provide assistance and protection to those arriving at its borders – and this translated into problematic legislative proposals (Carrera et al., 2023).

4. The discursive construction of irregularity in the European Parliament

As the only directly elected EU institution, the European Parliament plays a significant role in shaping migration policy within the EU, primarily through its legislative and oversight functions. While it cannot initiate legislation, the Parliament co-legislates with the Council of the European Union under the Ordinary Legislative Procedure. The Committee on Civil Liberties, Justice, and Home Affairs (LIBE Committee) is central to this process as it scrutinises and suggests amendments to proposals related to migration, asylum, and border management²³. Moreover, the Parliament also acts as a platform for public policy, including on migration, with different political groups promoting distinct narratives.

For the 2019–2024 legislature, the political groups, in order of size, were the European People’s Party (EPP – centre-right); the Progressive Alliance of Socialist and Democrats (S&D – centre-left); Renew Europe (centre); the Greens/European Free Alliance (Greens/EFA – green/centre-left); the European Conservatives and Reformists (ECR; far-right); Identity and Democracy (ID; extreme right); and the Left (GUE/NGL; left-wing).

It must be noted that these political groups are not homogenous, as they include national parties with relatively different political leanings and priorities. While selected MEPs may speak on behalf of their political party as a whole in the parliamentary debates, the Report does not claim that the statements analysed in the qualitative analysis always exemplify the line taken by their respective political group. They are used only as examples to discern individual narratives adopted by policymakers with different political orientations. In referring to ‘progressive’, ‘conservative’, ‘moderate’, or ‘far right/left’ positions, the author refers to the general ideological orientation commonly associated with the political group in the European Parliament, despite recognising possible internal variations.

²³ Since the Lisbon Treaty, the European Parliament acts as a full co-legislator and shares decision-making authority with the Council in the Area of Freedom, Security and Justice (AFSJ), which includes justice, rule of law, fundamental rights and migration, among others. Within the EP, the Committee on Civil Liberties, Justice and Home Affairs (LIBE) plays a central role in these areas. Previous research (Carrera et al., 2011) has shown that LIBE’s assertive stance has often led to a perception of it being too ‘liberal’ or ‘radical’. Research indicates a more nuanced picture, with LIBE often adopting more ‘security-friendly’ and ‘less confrontational’ positions as a sign of self-legitimacy ([ibid.](#); see also [Ripoll Servent, 2011](#)).

4.1. Data sample

For the European Parliament, the data sample includes 1 380 documents (799 618 tokens): 1 365 statements from individual Members of the European Parliament (MEPs) and 15 press releases from the Parliament as an institution. These documents were retrieved from the official website of the European Parliament and include speeches, debates, and press releases covering migration-related topics from 2019 to 2023.

The MEPs' statements in the debates were grouped based on their respective European political groups. This allows for analysis of the prevailing language used by each political group and the identification of differences across the whole political spectrum.

4.2. Quantitative analysis

4.2.1. High-frequency words

The table below identifies the most highly frequent terms used by the European Parliament, excluding filler words, such as articles, prepositions, and modal verbs ('the', 'and', 'that', 'will', etc.).

Words	Rank	Normalised frequency
We	8	16.804
European	18	7.266
Our	25	5.087
People	27	4.187
President	28	4.086
Union	35	3.691
They	37	3.633
Europe	39	3.305
Their	50	2.650
EU	53	2.579
States	54	2.546
Need	56	2.482
Member	58	2.436
Us	60	2.337
Rights	61	2.189
Migration	69	1.961
Countries	70	1.926
Border	72	1.902
Commission	78	1.767
Human	79	1.738
Borders	82	1.675
Time	83	1.601
Asylum	84	1.593
Right	87	1.538
Citizens	89	1.484

Commissioner	90	1.447
Years	96	1.369
Against	98	1.353
Law	101	1.301
Parliament	102	1.292

The list of high-frequency words for the European Parliament indicates again a specific focus on the EU as a whole and its Member States (*we, European, our, union, EU, states, member, us*), as well as on inter- and intra-institutional relations (*president, commission, commissioner, parliament*). *Migration, borders, and asylum* appear with similar frequency in the whole data sample, but are slightly less frequent than *rights*. The focus on rights is also reinforced by the presence of *human* and *right* among the results. *Need* might also further support the emphasis on rights, but may at the same time indicate the prevalence of normative statements in parliamentary debates (i.e., *we need* to strengthen our borders). The presence of both first-person (*we, our, us*) and third-person pronouns (*they*) suggests a focus on actors external to the Parliament but may also indicate some type of opposition – which is further reinforced by *against*. Finally, *law* confirms the expectation of the Parliament’s focus on its role as co-legislator, and terms like *time* and *years* shows preoccupation with the passing of time or the urgency of policy action.

In the following sections, the Report will assess the frequency of these words, in relation to their specific semantic groups, to identify trends and what their high occurrence means.

4.2.2. Semantic groups

As for the Commission, the most frequently mentioned group by the European Parliament is Governance, with a total normalised frequency of 69.807. Within this group, Institutions (35.526) and Policy (15.376) are the most highly represented subgroups, followed by Legislation (6.717) and Politics (5.500). The most prominent words in Governance include ‘European’ (7.266), ‘president’ (4.086), and ‘union’ (3.691). Next is Time and Space, with a high total normalised frequency of 51.341. This group includes Geography (29.174) and Time (18.385). Key terms in Time and Space are ‘Europe’ (3.305), ‘countries’ (1.926), and ‘time’ (1.600).

The Rights semantic group has a combined total normalised frequency of 35.262, split between Asylum/Refugees (12.136), Fundamental Rights (9.768), Justice (5.473), and EU Values (4.271). The words ‘rights’ (2.189), ‘human’ (1.738), and ‘asylum’ (1.593) are frequently mentioned in Rights. Subject comes next, with a total normalised frequency of 27.717, driven by the prominence of the People (14.946) subgroup, followed by Social Identity (5.900) and Lived Experience (3.717). Notable words in Subject are ‘people’ (4.187), ‘they’ (3.633), and ‘their’ (2.650).

The Borders and Migration group follows, with a significant total normalised frequency of 23.698. The subgroups Borders (8.932) and Status (6.956) have the highest frequency, while Entry (5.987) is also notable. Frequently occurring words in Borders and Migration are ‘migration’ (1.961), ‘border’ (1.902), and ‘borders’ (1.675). The Welfare and Services group has a total normalised frequency of 13.858, with Inclusion and Social Protection (5.736) and Care and Relief (4.720) as the most prominent subgroups. Common words in Welfare and Services are ‘support’ (1.118), ‘help’ (0.792), and ‘social’ (0.598).

The Crisis and Defence group has a total normalised frequency of 11.487, with Defence (7.362) and Crisis (2.577) as the key subgroups. Keywords in Crisis and Defence include ‘against’ (1.353), ‘war’ (0.784), and ‘security’ (0.649). The Numbers and Quantities group has a total normalised frequency of 12.571. Frequently mentioned terms in this category include ‘one’ (1.903), ‘first’ (1.013), and ‘million’ (0.891). The Policing and Crime group shows a moderate level of attention, with a total normalised frequency of 7.905. Words like ‘illegal’ (0.817), ‘security’ (0.649), and ‘order’ (0.598) are most prevalent in Policing and Crime.

The Work and Economy group has a combined total normalised frequency of 7.255, split into Employment and Work (4.643) and Economy (2.107). Important words in Work and Economy are ‘work’ (1.153), ‘labour’ (0.810), and ‘skills’ (0.093). The Returns and Expulsion group has a total normalised frequency of 1.527. ‘Return’ (0.388), ‘procedures’ (0.265), and ‘relocation’ (0.118) are the most frequent words in this group. The Obligations group has a relatively low total normalised frequency of 1.103. The terms ‘integration’ (0.249), ‘responsible’ (0.220), and ‘duty’ (0.189) stand out in Obligations. Finally, the group with the lowest total normalised frequency is IOs and NGOs, with a total normalised frequency of 1.078. Common words here include ‘ngo’ (0.051), ‘organisations’ (0.065), and ‘civil’ (0.045).

This hierarchical presentation of frequencies highlights the varying degrees of attention given to different topics within the European Parliament’s discourse. ‘Governance’ and ‘Time and Space’ stand out as the most discussed semantic groups, indicating a strong focus on institutional matters, policy discussions, and geographical considerations.

Table 2: Semantic group analysis for the European Parliament

Semantic group	Subgroup	No of words	NormFreq	Total NormFreq
Governance	Institutions	66	35.526	69.807
	Policy	107	15.376	
	Legislation	35	6.717	
	Politics	52	5.500	
	Names	12	1.571	
Time and space	Geography	141	29.174	51.341
	Time	69	18.385	
Rights	Asylum/refugees	51	12.136	35.262
	Fundamental Rights	24	9.768	
	Justice	26	5.473	
	EU values	14	4.271	
	Violations	26	2.444	
Subject	People	16	14.946	27.717
	Social identity	35	5.900	
	Lived experience	45	3.717	
	Family/Household	8	0.893	
Borders and migration	Borders	47	8.932	23.698
	Status	20	6.956	
	Entry	51	5.987	
	Residence	7	0.919	

Welfare and services	Inclusion and social protection	29	5.736	13.858
	Care and relief	12	4.720	
	Health	17	1.807	
	Education	5	0.603	
	Housing	3	0.229	
Numbers and quantities	Numbers and quantities	44	8.999	12.571
Crisis and defence	Defence	51	7.362	11.487
	Crisis	21	2.577	
Policing and crime	Policing and crime	59	7.584	7.905
Work and economy	Employment and work	36	4.643	7.255
	Economy	22	2.107	
Returns and expulsion	Returns and expulsion	11	1.527	1.527
Obligations	Obligations	8	1.035	1.103
IOs and NGOs	IOs and NGOs	11	1.078	1.078

4.2.3. Collocation analysis

The collocation analysis of key terms – *migra**, *irregular*, *refugee(s)*, and employment-related words such as *work**, *labour*, and **employ** – reveals distinct patterns in how migration and irregularity are framed by the European Parliament, as well as unique patterns that reflect the diverse political and ideological perspectives of its members.

While this section mainly analyses the discourse of the Parliament as a whole, Sections 4.2.4 and 4.2.5 will unpack the differences between the individual political groups.

Migration

The collocation analysis of the key term **migra** reveals a clear focus on governance, illegality, and border control in the European Parliament's discourse. The semantic group 'Governance' stands out with a likelihood value of 1899.260, particularly in relation to Policy (707.783) and Legislation (1044.903). Among the main words in this category are 'pact' (690.041), 'policy' (575.595) and 'legal' (354.862), which clearly reflect the work of the Parliament over new legislation files, including the Pact.

Policing and crime-related terms also show prominence, with a likelihood value of 1800.64. The high sum likelihood value is essentially attributable to one single term: 'illegal' (1715.192). Notably, 'illegal' happens to be the single word with the highest likelihood value among all collocation results for **migra**. In other words, within the data sample, the ensemble of the statements in the data sample are significantly more likely to define (im)migration or (im)migrants as 'illegal', instead of 'irregular' or any other term. This is also confirmed by the frequency of the two terms in the whole data sample, with 'illegal' showing a normalised frequency of 0.817 and 'irregular' of 0.139. The extremely high likelihood value for 'illegal' highlights the tendency of particular political groups within the EP to link migration with issues of criminality, (in)security, and law enforcement-related matters.

The 'Borders and Migration' semantic group follows closely with a sum likelihood of 1466.628, showing that discussions around border control, entry (529.962), and legal status (442.239) are highly prevalent. In this case, the terms most likely to be associated with **migra** are 'irregular' (389.571), 'flows' (332.43), and 'routes' (139.623). The 'Rights' semantic group has a likelihood value of 906.223, with a heavy emphasis on asylum and refugees (768.375), rather than fundamental rights or violations. This is mostly due to the frequent juxtaposition of **migra** terms with 'asylum' (621.450) and 'refugees' (103.005) in expressions such as 'asylum and migration policy', 'Pact on Migration and Asylum' or in general discussions surrounding human mobility. The 'Crisis and Defence' semantic group follows with a likelihood of 526.212 and words such as 'crisis' (179.469) or 'pressure' (132.412).

With a sum likelihood of 529.859, the semantic group 'Numbers and quantities' is particularly prevalent among these collocation results. Among the individual words in this group, it is worth highlighting that a majority indicate abstract or figurative quantities, i.e., mass, flow, wave, flood, and even those that are more specific (i.e., thousands, hundreds) are used in indefinite ways and not to indicate specific quantities – e.g. 'there are hundreds/thousands of people at the borders'.

Irregular (and illegal)

As already mentioned above, the term ‘irregular’ only appears with a normalised frequency of ‘irregular’ of 0.139, while ‘illegal’ is at 0.817. The discourse around *irregular* migration in the European Parliament is predominantly focused on border control and the legal status of migrants. The ‘Borders and Migration’ group dominates with a sum likelihood of 519.207, particularly focused on entry (96.096; including words like ‘crossings’, ‘arrivals’, ‘routes’ and ‘flows’) and status (367.808; including words such as ‘(im)migration’, and ‘(im)migrants’). The focus is largely on controlling and preventing irregular entry into the European Union – i.e., ‘reduce’ and ‘fight’ respectively at 29.289 and 15.875, with little discussion about the social or economic conditions of irregular migrants post-entry.

Much richer are the collocations with the term ‘illegal’, showing a clear preoccupation with securitisation and criminalisation but also, much less prominently, with fundamental rights violations. The ‘Borders and Migration’ semantic group shows a high sum likelihood of 2137.323 with a focus on border control (81.302) and entry (215.286), as well as migrant status (1840.735). The Rights semantic group comes next with 273.175, exclusively concentrated in the Violations subgroup with terms such as ‘pushbacks’ (121.437 as a single word; ‘push’ at 70.750 and ‘backs’ at 64.810²⁴). This clearly shows the two ways ‘illegal’ tends to be used across the political spectrum.

Collocations within the ‘Crisis and Defence’ group also reflect a strong focus on security and defence, with a likelihood of 237.646, primarily concerning defensive measures (237.646) and therefore with words such as ‘against’ (50.320), ‘prevent’ (37.955) or ‘invasion’ (24.843). Policing and crime are likewise prominent, with a sum of 169.548, particularly in relation to smuggling and trafficking.

Refugees

For the term *refugee*, the European Parliament’s discourse shifts somewhat, with the ‘Time and Space’ semantic group showing the highest likelihood (732.807), particularly in relation to geography (732.807). This reflects the EP’s focus on specific countries of origin, events or agreements with third countries – specifically, Ukraine (95.818 , plus ‘Ukrainian’ at 326.278), Syria (20.851; ‘Syrian’ at 124.969), Afghanistan (‘Afghan’ at 51.812), Turkey (38.971), Moria in Greece (36.803) and Venezuela (‘Venezuelan’ at 21.072).

The category of Rights is much more central in the discussion surrounding refugees, with a likelihood value of 531.576, but is mostly made up of terms related to asylum (504.293), such as ‘camp(s)’ (114.270 in the plural form and 60.123 in the singular form), ‘convention’ (54.535) and ‘Geneva’ (47.177). There is also a moderate focus on welfare and services (76.31), particularly on care and relief (52.137), inclusion (24.173), and crisis and defence (128.958 total; ‘war’ at 81.723). This suggests that, compared to other groups of TCNs, refugees are discussed more in terms of their need for social services and protection, reflecting a more rights-based approach.

Work and Employment

Employment-related terms, such as *work**, *labour*, and **employ**, show a strong focus on economic aspects. The ‘Work and Economy’ group has a sum likelihood of 1128.629, with the bulk of the attention on

²⁴ The software used for the analysis divides words if they contain a hyphen. In this case, ‘push-backs’ is divided as ‘push’ and ‘backs’, as two distinct words.

employment and work (1092.205). This indicates that discussions around employment are heavily internal to economic policy and work-related matters, with little connection to migration. The most prevalent terms in this group are 'market' (417.47), 'skilled' (175.748), 'shortages' (65.869), and 'seasonal' (63.916).

The 'Borders and Migration' group only has a moderate presence with a sum likelihood of 112.431, indicating a limited overlap between discussions on migration and employment. 'Migration' is the word from this semantic group with the highest likelihood value at 46.033. More prevalent are the semantic groups of Welfare and Services (323.778) and Governance (201.143).

Gender

Women and gender-related terms are frequently discussed in the EP's migration discourse. With 615 occurrences, women are a central focus, particularly in relation to other words related to social identity (2074.836 likelihood in the 'Subject' group). Women are often discussed in vulnerable contexts, with collocations focusing on lived experiences (151.559), particularly exploitation, violence, and other forms of gender-based harm. This indicates that women are framed largely as victims in migration contexts, requiring gender-specific protection and support. This is also visible from the significant attention to rights violations against women, with the Rights semantic group showing a sum likelihood of 435.68, mostly split between violations (227.511) and fundamental rights (191.043).

In contrast to women, men are mentioned far less frequently, with 197 occurrences. When men are discussed, it is mainly in relation to other words from the Subject semantic group (784.796 likelihood), including 'women' at 436.310 and 'children' at 173.772. This means that words such as men or male are mostly used in an explicit way in expressions such as 'men, women and children' and not by themselves. An exception is the word 'young' (121.465), which is used to speak about 'young men' and carries a different connotation (see Section 6). Unlike women, men are rarely framed as victims, and the discourse does not emphasise their vulnerabilities to the same extent.

Among the three, children dominate the data sample with 1036 occurrences. The EP's discourse emphasises the social identity of children (1452.158 likelihood in the 'Subject' group) and their lived experiences (856.366). This suggests a strong focus on children's rights, particularly in terms of protection, education (223.393), and inclusion (45.007). The 'Welfare and Services' group also has a significant presence, indicating that the EP prioritises children's access to services and their overall well-being in migration contexts. This reflects an approach more focused on children's need, protection, family reunification, and support.

Different nationalities are more likely to be associated with the three categories of terms: among women, Afghans and Ukrainians; among men, Syrians; among children; Ukrainians and – to a lesser extent – Palestinians from Gaza.

4.2.4. *Political groups: Keynes analysis*

The keyness analysis reveals significant differences in the way the different political groups within the European Parliament speak about migration. Below a summary of their main key points emerging from the statements collected in the data sample (ordered left to right based on their position in the hemicycle):

- The Left focuses on social justice, mobility rights, and critical views on border policies.
- S&D emphasises binding agreements, European unity and solidarity, and social justice.
- Greens/EFA highlight human rights issues.
- Renew Europe stresses collaboration, regulation, and mutual trust.
- EPP focuses on European integration, border management, and digital innovation.
- ECR emphasises national sovereignty, criminality, and critical views on policies.
- ID prioritises migration control, criminality, national issues, and national sovereignty.

Some of the most significant words for each political group reflect their internal national composition and the higher representation of MEPs from specific Member States over others (i.e., 'Polish' in ECR, 'France' in ID, etc.).

The Left (GUE/NGL)

The Left's discourse is characterised by terms that highlight issues of social justice, human rights, and criticism of EU migration policies. Key terms include 'fortress' (59.041), 'policies' (47.266), 'racist' (45.274), 'pushbacks' (40.702), 'coast' (36.694), 'operation' (36.346), 'racism' (35.583), 'rights' (35.414), 'people' (32.619), 'refugees' (31.177), and 'detention' (29.537). These terms indicate a focus on criticising restrictive migration policies ('fortress', 'pushbacks'), advocating for human rights ('racist', 'racism', 'rights', 'refugees'), and addressing issues related to the treatment of migrants ('detention', 'operation'). The Left's language is more emotive and activist, reflecting their position as a progressive opposition group challenging the status quo.

The Progressive Alliance of Socialists and Democrats (S&D)

The S&D group emphasises terms related to policy-making and humanitarian considerations. Key terms include 'binding' (64.046), 'european' (48.539), 'humanitarian' (43.088), 'measures' (33.35), 'directive' (33.101), 'solidarity' (32.88), 'rights' (27.144) and 'values' (23.895). The S&D's discourse focuses on legislative action ('binding', 'directive'), European integration and solidarity ('european', 'solidarity', 'values'), and humanitarian and legal concerns ('humanitarian', 'rights'). Their language is policy-oriented and advocates for collective European solutions to migration challenges, reflecting their centre-left position and alignment with mainstream EU policies.

The Greens/European Free Alliance (Greens/EFA)

The Greens/EFA group shows key terms such as 'people' (52.458), 'rights' (41.088), 'urge' (31.196), 'dignity' (29.056), 'rescue' (25.652), 'humanitarians' (24.709), 'climate' (24.464), 'suffering' (22.453), and 'distress' (22.438). Their discourse focuses on human rights ('people', 'rights', 'dignity'), humanitarian action and non-governmental organisations ('humanitarians'), the treatment of migrants, asylum-seekers and refugees ('rescue', 'suffering', 'distress'), and environmental concerns ('climate').

Renew Europe (RE)

Renew Europe's key terms are rather limited and include 'renew' (127.601), 'colleagues' (59.892), 'citizens' (23.317), 'controls' (23.239), and 'trust' (22.599). Their discourse is characterised by formal address and institutional focus ('renew', 'citizens', 'controls'). The more limited results for Renew Europe indicate the political group's adherence to the dominant discourse, with no significant outliers demonstrating a Renew-specific focus or approach. Overall, the language is more neutral and technical, reflecting their centrist position and their being part of the governing coalition at the EU level.

European People's Party (EPP)

The EPP focuses on terms like 'european' (152.224), 'schengen' (150.596), 'union' (75.767), 'must' (56.931), 'need' (35.334), 'citizens' (35.216), 'movement' (34.417), 'security' (24.279), and 'our' (29.096). Their discourse is centred on the European Union ('european', 'union'), free movement ('movement'), border management ('Schengen'), and security concerns ('security'). In migration-related discourse, Schengen/border security and free movement seem to be pitted against each other – with the health of the former described as a pre-condition to preserving the latter. The EPP's language is formal and institutional. Despite being the largest and most influential political group, EPP language seems to offer more keyness results compared to, for example, Renew Europe. This might hint at the wider gap between the EPP and the dominant discourse of the Parliament as an institution, as well as its greater insistence on the above-mentioned topics.

European Conservatives and Reformists (ECR)

The ECR has key terms such as 'illegal' (197.389), 'poland' (182.397), 'immigrants' (74.979), 'hypocrisy' (40.361), 'illegally' (36.093), 'russia' (34.234), 'nation' (29.185), 'nations' (28.37), and 'immigration' (25.327). Their discourse is confrontational ('hypocrisy'), focuses on migration as a crime ('illegal', 'illegally', 'immigrants', 'immigration') and emphasises national sovereignty ('poland', 'nation', 'nations'). The ECR's language reflects a securitised and nationalistic approach to migration, challenging EU policies and advocating for stricter border controls.

Identity and Democracy (ID)

The ID group emphasises terms like 'immigration' (206.439), 'migrants' (135.609), 'illegal' (74.258), 'italy' (73.122), 'france' (70.352), 'immigrants' (59.717), 'africa' (54.754), 'borders' (34.63), 'mass' (37.097), 'sovereignty' (38.103), and 'muslim' (35.603). Their discourse is heavily focused on migration as a crime and anti-immigration sentiments ('immigration', 'migrants', 'illegal', 'immigrants', 'mass'), national sovereignty ('sovereignty', 'italy', 'france'), and reveals a particular insistence against African and Muslim people, revealing a xenophobic approach ('africa', 'muslim'). The language is emotive, confrontational, and reflects a strong opposition to migration and multiculturalism.

Analysis

The keyness analysis shows that political groups closer to the centre of the political spectrum (and therefore to the status quo), such as the EPP, Renew Europe, and S&D, use more neutral and technical language, focusing on institutional terms ('european', 'union', 'schengen', 'citizens') and policy discussions. They emphasise European integration, security, and collaboration. The limited keyness results for Renew might attest to its centrist position, but clearer ideological positions transpire for the EPP and S&D. While

remaining more technical and institutional than other groups, the EPP emphasises questions of border control and security concerns, while S&D gives particular attention to humanitarian issues, solidarity, rights, and values.

In contrast, groups that were not included in the official von der Leyen I majority, i.e., The Left, the Greens/EFA, ECR, and ID, tend to use more emotive and polarised language. The Left and the Greens focus on human rights, social justice, and humanitarian concerns, using terms like 'rights', 'people', 'dignity', 'rescue', 'racism', and 'fortress' to challenge existing policies and advocate for more rights-based approaches. The ECR and ID use language that depicts migration as a crime, emphasise national sovereignty, and criticise current EU policies, with terms like 'illegal', 'immigrants', 'nation', 'mass', 'borders', and 'sovereignty'. Their discourse is securitarian and nationalistic, reflecting their opposition to the EU's migration policies, but also often xenophobic, reflecting their opposition to any type of diversity.

4.3. Qualitative analysis

4.3.1. Proto-narratives

As for the Commission, statements from the Parliament tend to use policy and legislation-oriented language which may not always include proper narratives. However, given the nature of the parliamentary debates, the more partisan and openly ideological nature of the statements, and their overall context, this is less prominent in the Parliament case.

The proto-narratives below are based on the quantitative data for the Parliament as a whole and do not account for the internal differences of the political groups. As such, they reflect polarisation in the political discourse around migration and may be contradictory with each other, exemplifying the different ways of seeing and talking about migration across the different political groups.

- *The EU must strengthen its external borders to prevent irregular migration and increase returns of those without the right to stay.*
- *The EU must enforce strict measures against illegal migration to protect national sovereignty, the integrity of European borders and prevent crime.*
- *Safe and legal migration pathways are needed to address labour market needs and ensure migrant workers' rights are protected.*
- *The EU must protect refugees' rights, ensure effective reception systems and their integration into European societies.*
- *Shared solidarity and responsibility between member states are essential to address migration challenges and ensure fair asylum systems.*
- *The EU must combat NGOs involved in facilitating illegal migration, holding them accountable for their role in trafficking networks.*

Based on the evidence gathered through the quantitative analysis and the proto-narratives identified above, this Section will now collect and assess individual statements by the European Parliament on the topics of migration and (ir)regularity, employment and gender, as well as other relevant topics such as Covid-19, returns, and crisis and defence. They were selected as reproducing or going against the specific narratives identified above and for offering a broader overview of the ideological positions within the Parliament.

4.3.2. Migration and (ir)regularity (and illegality)

The statements below exemplify a number of different narratives and ideological positions discernible across the data sample.

Yes, we need to protect the external borders better. Yes, we need to tackle human smugglers more fiercely. Yes, we must promote the return of irregular migration. But above all we must work on a real European asylum and migration policy. (Renew 12-09-2023)

We have the obligation to provide guarantees to those who need international protection, but we must also protect our borders from external threats that endanger the safety of our citizens. For this reason, a political migration policy is efficient, coherent and comprehensive. And to do this, the European Union must use all the instruments at its disposal, not only domestic policy, but also development cooperation or commercial policy, conditioning agreements with our neighbours and partners on their collaboration for the return of irregular migrants and the fight versus the mafias. (EPP 10-05-2023)

First of all, as underlined in the collocation analysis, ‘irregularity’ was mainly connected to external border crossings, entry into the EU territory, and arrivals of TCNs. Both the Renew and EPP statements above insist on external border controls. Specifically, the Renew MEP paired border controls with the fight against human smuggling and the promotion of returns. The EPP MEP combined it with the protection of ‘our citizens’ from ‘external threats’, cooperation and commercial agreements with neighbouring third countries to facilitate returns, and the fight against criminal activities (‘the mafias’). While both of these statements emphasised the commitment to ‘a real European asylum and migration policy’ and ‘guarantees to those who need international protection’, the overall focus was on irregularised migration as something that is inherently connected to criminality – sometimes with the migrants themselves as victims and sometimes as perpetrators – and on returns as the one desirable solution to the ‘issue’ at hand.

Clear differences emerge with the statement below from a MEP from the Greens:

The cost of the EU's ways of combating irregular migration is high – human rights, human dignity, and even human lives. But the EU is willing to pay that price, giving up any pretension of upholding its values at the borders. The external borders are common borders and this comes with a common responsibility to share the numbers of asylum seekers and ensure that people can flee persecution. They must be rescued and protected. And when some of my EPP colleagues call for solidarity, they often mean fences, deterrents, criminalisation of humanitarian aid. That is not solidarity, that's being partners in crime. (Greens 18-04-2023)

The MEP in question openly criticised the current migration and asylum policies of the EU, including the insistence on harshening controls at the external EU borders. Human rights, human dignity, and human lives were described as the main victims of the EU’s fight against irregularised migration – with EU values being directly undermined by such actions. Emphasis was put on the obligation to rescue people, ensure protection, and effectively share responsibilities across the EU in a genuine way. In this case, there was a direct attack to the EPP and, specifically, the alleged use of ‘solidarity’ as a way to push for stricter border controls, including the construction of fences, deterrence, and the criminalisation of civil society actors. Crime was associated with policymakers and their being complicit in people’s deaths due to their support for stringent policies. The statement in question effectively illustrates the inherent contrast between non-derogable fundamental rights and EU values and the current policies adopted by the EU.

Diametrically opposite are the statements below by MEPs from ECR and ID:

You did realise that eight out of ten migrants are men. Where did your gender equality go, hon? Shouldn't there have been some ratio? This misconstrued tolerance, I conclude, Madam President, and misconstrued solidarity have led to attacks, threats and assassinations. This needs to change. (ECR 19-01-2021)

The human smuggling NGOs bring tens of thousands of illegal immigrants to Europe. (ECR 18-10-2022)

While we are experiencing a real migratory submersion, which would require strong measures, Commissioner Johansson still refuses to finance walls and barriers at Europe's borders, under the pretext that the European Union does not have funds to spend for that. However, the Commission is much less careful about financial resources when it comes to subsidizing certain associations and promotional campaigns on the future of Europe with the Islamic veil. What credibility can be given to the measures announced by Mrs. von der Leyen to deal with the migration crisis, while at the same time she maintains a pro-immigration position? By wanting to intensify the corridors described as 'humanitarian' to encourage mass immigration and by wishing to attract more supposedly qualified workers, Brussels continues to create air calls, suction pumps, which many candidates for migration will follow. The European Union must, however, control its borders, stop funding water taxi NGOs for migrants, stop legalizing illegal immigration, send back to their countries of origin all those who must leave and no longer give a euro to States who would not take back their nationals. This is a vital question for the future of Europe. It is high time to show common sense and firmness because, if Europe cannot be turned in on itself, it must protect its nationals, its businesses, its identity. Europe will only be strong if the States that make it up are. The exact opposite is happening. We resolutely oppose it. (ID 01-02-2023)

The first statement linked migration to crime, gender equality, and physical violence at the same time. As underlined in the collocation analysis, men and masculinity are more likely to be associated with physical violence and criminality. The MEP seems to be arguing in favour of gender quotas for entries into the EU. They directly linked the higher percentage of male migrants to indefinite episodes of violence, using this to critique other groups' calls for tolerance and solidarity. The second statement also shows a prevalence of crime-related themes – specifically, the association of NGOs with human smuggling and of border crossing with 'illegality'.

Criticisms against NGOs (referred to as 'water taxis') and the association of migration with 'illegality' are also visible in the statement by the ID MEP. In this case, the MEP in question did not only attack irregularised migration, but also humanitarian corridors and labour mobility for qualified workers. Referring to human mobility as 'migratory submersion' and mentioning 'the future of Europe with the Islamic veil', the statement depicted migration as an existential threat to European identity, sovereignty, and security ('Europe will only be strong if the States that make it up are'). They attacked the Commission for being too 'pro-migration' in its approach ('air calls' or 'suction pumps') and emphasised the need for 'common sense', 'firmness', and increased returns to countries of origin.

4.3.3. Employment

Similar polarisation is discernible with regard to employment and labour mobility, with distinct differences identifiable across all political groups.

Europe is a rapidly aging continent: our working population is shrinking and will continue to shrink in the foreseeable future. And we already see today all over Europe that employers are faced with significant labour shortages. So it's good that also at the European level, we look for innovative ways to increase the attractiveness of our Union to talent from third countries. And, yes, it could also help us creating effective partnerships with third countries on the external dimension of migration. And this is crucial, as we all know, in our wider efforts on the Pact of Migration. There are two principles that should be leading, in my opinion.

First, that it is, and it should remain the sole competence of the individual Member State to decide on labour migration from third countries, taking into consideration the very specific circumstances of the different national labour markets. And at the European level we need to make sure that there are no loopholes to circumvent this principle. And I am particularly concerned about intra-EU posting of third country nationals in this regard.

Second principle: focusing on attracting talents from third countries must never come at the expense of our efforts to activate our own citizens that are currently not in employment. Labour migration can be a part of the solution, but it can never be the only solution. Not when 14% of our European youth is still facing unemployment, not when people are over the age of 55 that want to work still have huge difficulties to find employment, not with the current labour shortages and not when we stumble at the moment, as in my country, from one scandal to the next, when it comes to housing or working conditions for labour migrants that are already in the EU. Yes, employers are in need of workers, and we need to help them. But they also need to make an effort themselves to go the extra mile to employ people that want to work but need a little bit of help. In a social market economy, we can't only always focus on the quickest, the easiest or the cheapest solution; we need a long-term solution that puts human dignity in the centre. (EPP 08-06-2022)

The EPP MEP statement reflected a cautious approach to labour migration, acknowledging the need for migrant workers to address Europe's shrinking working population and labour shortages. The discussion was limited to attracting 'talent', including through partnerships with third countries, but only as long as this does not conflict with the employment of European citizens. The MEP stressed that labour migration must remain the sole competence of Member States, and that EU involvement should remain limited to circumventing loopholes.

While not openly opposed to labour migration, the statement strongly hinted that migration can conflict with the economic security, wellbeing, and even human dignity of European citizens. It associated migrant workers with the idea of 'cheating' the system, be it in the context of social benefit 'scandals' or by exploiting existing loopholes. In other words, the statement suggested that, while acceptable and potentially positive, migration needs to be managed by Member States (and not the EU) – or else migration is in opposition to the wellbeing of European citizens.

Also part of the von der Leyen I majority, the statement below by a S&D MEP shows a different approach to labour migration and migrant workers:

Permit me to thank the thousands of third-country workers across the Union and in my country, from professional nurses and doctors fighting the pandemic, some of whom arrived on our shores in flimsy dinghies, to the most humble street sweepers. Together, we are strengthening our Union. President, Commissioner, who determines what is economically necessary, why are there shortages in the labour

market and why is the large-scale exploitation of migrant workers by employers in logistics, agriculture, the meat industry and the temporary employment sector not being tackled?

As long as workers are exploited, we must ensure that labour migration from third countries is allowed on the basis of skills rather than qualifications. We must not give in blindly to the lobby of the employment agencies. After all, we don't want people in our labour markets to get burned out and be discarded. People deserve good working conditions, fair pay and decent shelter. We must guarantee this in the first place in order to create a Europe that works.

(...) As a consequence of our efforts to foster new avenues for legal labour migration into the EU, we need to make sure that anti-discrimination laws and policies are present in all Member States. Not only on paper, but in practice. Dignity and equality are matters of basic human rights, but also have a significant economic dimension.

Madam President, with the forecast of the loss of around tens of millions of people of working age in the coming decades and what this entails in terms of loss of skills and competitive capacity, it is easy to understand the risk involved in delaying the construction of a true immigration policy by the European Union. Creating channels for regular immigration is the only effective way to combat trafficking and immigrant exploitation networks. Guaranteeing access to the labour market and integration that respects human dignity for everyone is a matter of decency.

We need men and women seeking the European Union, with medium or low qualifications and not just the highly qualified Blue Card eligible. We cannot continue to waste the regenerative potential that immigrants bring to our societies, condemning them, so often, to death on avoidable routes. (S&D 19-05-2021)

The statement starts by thanking migrant workers for their contribution to their host countries, including both healthcare professionals working during the Covid-19 pandemic (see below for more) and TCNs involved in more blue-collar activities (i.e., street sweepers), recognising how their presence contributes to strengthening the EU. The statement critiques the exploitation of migrant workers in industries such as agriculture, logistics, and the meat sector, highlighting a gap between the EU's efforts to promote labour migration and its failure to address widespread exploitation in these sectors. Advocating for 'good working conditions, fair pay, and decent shelter' and the need for anti-discrimination laws and policies and their effective implementation, the statement suggests the labour migration policies should be grounded in the respect for fundamental rights and international labour standards, i.e., human dignity and equality.

Furthermore, labour migration pathways were acknowledged as 'the only effective way' to address human trafficking and exploitation networks. Unlike the previous statement, the S&D MEP did not limit themselves to 'talent' and highly-skilled workers but advocated for easier mobility for TCNs with medium or low qualifications. Additionally, the EU was recognised a central role in facilitating and harmonising labour migration, and the speaker actually lamented that this has lagged. Overall, it is evident that, instead of an opposition between Europeans and migrant workers, this statement describes the latter as a strengthening force for Europe, emphasising the respect for human dignity and decent labour standards.

Similar insights can be drawn from the statement below from a MEP from The Left:

The current European Union framework places too much emphasis on high-skilled workers and not enough on middle- and lower-skilled workers and pathways of labour mobility for migrants of all skill levels are crucial. However, we believe it's time to stop seeing labour migration only as a solution to

current socioeconomic problems based only on the immediate needs of employers. We must understand this in a broader system which takes into account a number of criteria. Also, in the case of asylum seekers and undocumented workers, they must have access to employment and the same labour rights, ensuring swift action to regularise their status and prevent exploitation at their place of work. Creating safe and legal pathways is the only way to reduce reliance on unsafe and irregular routes. It's essential to protect and prioritise vulnerable groups such as children, women and LGBTIQ persons, as it is these groups who suffer the most. We need real, actual and ambitious policies to make the Union strong and a place where human rights matter. (Left 3-11-2021)

The main point of critique here was also the existing limitation of labour migration policies to highly-skilled workers, and the exclusion of other categories of migrant workers. Unlike the other statements, however, the speaker made explicit reference to asylum-seekers and undocumented workers, advocating for their access to employment, labour rights, swift action to regularise their status, and the prevention of labour exploitation. Furthermore, the statement highlights the need for migration policies that go beyond meeting the immediate demands of employers, calling for a broader system that factors in human dignity, equity, and the protection of vulnerable groups – specifically children, women, and LGBTIQ persons. The Left MEP saw these principles as preconditions to maintaining the strength of the EU and upholding human rights.

The statement from an ECR MEP below significantly contrasts with the former:

Considering that this report concerns low- and medium-skilled labour migration, that sounds like EU speak for legalising illegal migration. Is the European Parliament's solution to Turkey and Morocco opening the floodgates? Let them in? To Belarus, weaponising migrants? Let them in? Now, hundreds of millions of people wish to come to Europe if given the opportunity. Such volumes will only exacerbate unemployment, stagnant wages, not to mention that migrants with incompatible cultures will bring about even less social cohesion. It's not just last night in Sweden, it's last night in Amsterdam, it's last night in Paris. European leaders seem to have finally smelt the coffee. They realise that we're losing control. President Michel has called for EU funding of external border barriers. President von der Leyen praised Greece for being Europe's shield. Even Commissioner Johansson acknowledged that Lithuania's border barrier is a good idea. (ECR 23-11-2021)

Low- and medium-skilled labour migration was presented as legalising 'illegal migration' and as a possible way for third countries to threaten the EU, i.e., by 'weaponising migrants' à la instrumentalisation. According to the MEP, making labour pathways more accessible to these categories of workers would attract 'hundreds of millions of people' – highlighting the recurring theme of 'indefinite' large numbers and quantities. Once again, the opposition between migration and the wellbeing and social rights of European citizens comes back, particularly by purportedly causing unemployment and lowering wages. TCNs and their culture were described as inherently incompatible with Europe and as undermining social cohesion. The MEP seemed to welcome the approach taken by EU policymakers, specifically Council President Charles Michel's calls for funding for external border barriers, President von der Leyen's praising Greece for being Europe's shield, and 'even' Commissioner Johansson's characterisation of Lithuania's border barrier as a good idea. The overall moral is that EU's policymakers are finally waking up to what the right-wing political groups have been arguing i.e., the alleged dangers of migration, the need to physically protect EU borders, the inherent incompatibility of TCNs with Europeans, and the need for Parliament to refrain from pushing for new labour regular pathways.

4.3.4. Gender

Interesting insights also emerge when looking at excerpts related to gender dynamics:

Well, Ukraine is our own region. This is where we must fulfil our humanitarian mission to the fullest. Millions of real war refugees, women, children and vulnerable people are on the run. Hungary is already hosting 200 000 people, Poland as much as one million. Just as both countries recently protected us from the illegal invasion of single young men from mainly African and Arab countries, they are now opening their hearts and their borders and offering shelter to real war refugees. (ID 08-03-2022)

This statement by an ID MEP draws a stark contrast between Ukrainian refugees, including ‘women, children and vulnerable people’, and the ‘single young men’ from African and Arab countries. The statement frames Ukrainian refugees as more deserving (or as ‘real’) based on their mainly being women, children, and vulnerable people, while delegitimising male refugees from other regions and portraying them as threats (‘illegal invasion’) rather than victims. As such, Europe should open their hearts and offer shelters to the former and should protect itself from the latter. This gendered rhetoric intersects with racism and xenophobia against racialised people and depicts men as non-deserving of protection or as pretending to be refugees – unlike white, largely female Ukrainians.

Below offers another example of a similar narrative:

According to the media, women and children came to Finland as well, but I personally went there to see at the border: 500 people a day, I counted them. All were young men. In the evening, the media told us that women and children came here. My eyes don't lie. I think that journalists and the media have some kind of lens on their head. Who takes responsibility for the fact that such an illegal immigrant ripped open the throat of a young woman now in Finland? Who among these will take responsibility? (ID 12-02-2020)

In this case, the speaker, also from an ID MEP, focused on the Finnish border and claimed to have personally visited and observed only young men crossing, despite media reports of women and children arriving. The statement seems to suggest that the media is deliberately lying in line with some political agenda and links the arrival of ‘young men’ to the violent killing of a woman in Finland. This clearly shows the association of masculinity with crime and violence, portraying men as non-deserving of protection.

The association of vulnerability with ‘women and children’ and other categories is not limited to right-wing political groups:

Creating safe and legal pathways is the only way to reduce reliance on unsafe and irregular routes. It's essential to protect and prioritise vulnerable groups such as children, women and LGBTIQ persons, as it is these groups who suffer the most. We need real, actual and ambitious policies to make the Union strong and a place where human rights matter. (Left 23-11-2021)

Unlike the previous statements, however, the statement above does not completely deny the possibility for men to be deserving of protection or have special reception needs; it rather accentuates the higher ‘vulnerability’ or possible exposure to danger and/or discrimination by specific categories, i.e., children, women, and LGBTIQ people.

This gender- and age-specific focus is less prominent in other statements:

Mr President, we are once again discussing the lives of thousands of men, women and children who every day attempt the perilous journey across the Mediterranean, fleeing conflict and unsustainable lives. (S&D 17-07-2019)

The report also contains necessary references, more generally, to the really atrocious situations at those borders, where pushbacks, horrific abuse and violence are a daily reality for men, women and children who seek asylum in Europe. (Left 06-07-2021)

Women, children and men die at our borders every day, without seeming to move European leaders in the slightest. (Greens 18-01-2023)

In all of these cases, left-leaning MEPs emphasised the life experiences of men, women, and children and their reasons for leaving their country of origin, the danger and violence they experience at the borders, and their deaths.

4.3.5. Covid-19

With regard to Covid-19, two distinct and opposite narratives can be identified. The first one couples the arrival and presence of TCNs in the EU with the Covid virus and related health hazards:

As far as immigration is concerned, Italy, thanks to the unworthy government, supports the arrival of thousands of immigrants, many of whom have tested positive for Covid. The European Union doesn't care. There is no common assistance, there is no distribution of refugees, there is no solidarity. In short, there are borders for everyone except for Italy, which is forced to new health risks. (ID 15-09-2020)

The ID MEP clearly equated 'the arrival of thousands of immigrants' with 'new health risks'. This was used as a criticism against the then-Italian government, against the lack of distribution and solidarity mechanisms for refugees – which has been a divisive topic within right-wing political groups –, and the perceived undermining of national borders due to the too-lax approach on arrivals.

The statement below, instead, shows increased attention to rights and welfare-related questions:

This pandemic has demonstrated that the disease does not discriminate between borders, nationalities or social status. Only a global response, which leaves no one stranded, will make it possible to eradicate it, but this also encourages us to really review our policy. The Covid-19 health crisis has been a pretext for certain States to suspend the fundamental rights of asylum seekers and their reception in Europe. It is time to expand legal pathways to the European Union by introducing humanitarian visas for both people who need international protection and those who aspire to a better future. (Greens 07-10-2021)

Starting from the idea that the virus does not discriminate between people on legal grounds, the Greens MEP underlined that Covid-19 should push for a rethinking of EU policies. According to the statement, Member States used Covid-19 as a way to 'suspend the fundamental rights of asylum seekers', and, instead, the desired solution would be to expand legal pathways both for asylum-seekers and other categories of TCNs, i.e., 'those who aspire to a better future'.

4.3.6. Return

When it comes to return, similar levels of polarisation can be identified.

We must do everything in our power to strike new agreements with third countries to counter irregular migration and increase returns, including by using our trade and visa policy as leverage. (Renew 01-02-2023)

The statement above from a Renew MEP exemplifies the overall dominant narrative surrounding return. New agreements with third countries were portrayed as a necessary solution to ‘counter irregular migration’ and increase the number of deportations, by also linking other policies such as trade and visas. Overall, the statement pushed for return through a seemingly ‘neutral’, or policy-centred, language.

This strongly clashes with the intervention below from an ECR MEP:

In this respect, it would be a good start, as suggested, to set up asylum centres outside of Europe and to link development aid to the implementation of return agreements - which, by the way, we have been calling for years. But to really solve the migration crisis, it takes more than that. Just last week, I completed a new asylum concept and presented the solutions to save Europe. Important measures include an immediate entry ban and a deportation offensive to return the millions upon millions of culturally alien and largely unqualified migrants. Not a single asylum seeker is allowed to set foot in Europe anymore. (ECR 18-10-2023)

While the theme is, again, arrangements with third countries, in this case, the MEP did not only call for linking development aid with asylum and migration policies, but also for the establishment of asylum centres and an ‘immediate entry ban’ for all TCNs regardless of legal categories (‘not a single asylum seeker is allowed to set foot in Europe anymore’). They strongly advocated for a ‘deportation offensive’ to return ‘the millions upon millions of culturally alien and largely unqualified migrants’. This statement interestingly brings together defence language, the ‘incompatibility’ of TCNs with Europeans, and their alleged lack of qualifications or grounds for asylum.

On the other side of the hemicycle, different narratives are more prominent:

The Commission and the Council cannot focus their attention exclusively on return. Of course, those who have been expelled from their country have the right to return to their land. But the return requires the end of wars, the defeat of terrorism, the birth of inclusive societies. The criminalization of NGOs and the construction of walls promoted by the right and the ultra-right will never be able to erase the most visible trace of our reality. The societies of today and tomorrow are and will always be diverse. Cultural and religious diversity is an unalterable reality, a reality that can and must be compatible with respect for the values of the host countries. We cannot change the diversity of our societies, but we can change the management of migratory flows. (S&D 01-02-2023)

This statement from an S&D MEP indicates disapproval for the Commission and the Council’s insistence on returns as the main solution in this area. It is further noted that, for return to be feasible, conditions like peace, the end of terrorism, and more inclusive societies must be achieved first. Disapproval is also expressed regarding the far-right but also more moderate right-wing parties criminalising the activities of NGOs and pushing for the construction of external border walls. These policies – the MEP maintained – will not be able to erase diversity in European societies, which they defined as ‘the most visible trace of our

reality’ or as an ‘unalterable reality ... that can and must be compatible with respect for the values of the host countries’. The MEP further called for a change in migration management policies.

Unlike the previous statement, diversity was not presented in a negative light or as an existential ‘clash of cultures’. It was rather described as a positive achievement of our times, which is currently under threat by right-wing political parties. While the idea that TCNs must respect ‘our’ values remained, this was presented as both a possibility and an obligation (‘can and must’).

4.3.7. Crisis and defence

Crisis and defence-related statements were mostly linked to discussions regarding the events that unfolded in 2022-2023 at the Latvian, Lithuanian, and Polish borders with Belarus.

Particularly interesting is the statement below from an EPP MEP during a debate on ‘Building of a wall on the Polish-Belarus border in the Białowieża primeval forest’:

Mr President, by being consistent with ourselves, we sometimes forget what kind of aggressive and uncontrollable force we have to defend ourselves against. When sending illegal migrants to the territories of European Union countries, neither the Belarusian regime nor the Russian regime behind it thinks either about the environment or about the conservation of animal species. It may sound cynical, but they think about the extermination of people – entire nations, which is nothing more than genocide. Of course, even in wartime conditions, we must not forget the environment, but we must not forget that illegal migration through Belarus is an instrument of hybrid warfare, so, above all, security is a priority, and we can only consider the possibilities of additional funding in order to reduce the burden on those EU members that are directly bordering Belarus. (EPP, 05-05-2022)

The MEP in question clearly described unauthorised border crossings from Belarus as an instrument of ‘hybrid warfare’. Irregularised migration was framed in geopolitical terms, as a deliberate and aggressive tactic devised by the Belarusian and Russian regimes to destabilise the EU. It is seen as a threat to security, as well as the very existence of European nations (‘extermination’ or ‘genocide’). This framing sought to justify increased EU funding and resources to support Member States bordering Belarus as a matter of survival and national security. There is no mention of the TCNs affected in these situations. Particularly interesting is the premise that, by being consistent with itself (i.e., with its founding values and priorities such as environmental protection), the EU fails to address the ‘aggressive and uncontrollable force’ it should defend itself against – which manifests itself in the form of human mobility. Overall, the statement depicts irregularised migration in existential terms, as a threat to the foundation of European nations, and implies that other considerations should be foregone in favour of increased security.

On the opposite side of the spectrum is the statement below from a MEP from the Left:

Mr President, the truth is that I am not going to focus on denouncing the humanitarian situation on the border between Belarus and Poland, where women, men and children are being treated as if they were real waste. I will confine myself to expressing my deepest rejection of the role of the Commission and the Council, their terrible statements about the so-called hybrid war and the support they are giving to the Polish far right in their repression of migrants, including supporting the separation of families at the border. The same thing that Trump did and this same Parliament has already condemned. They are

authorizing and legitimizing the most reactionary, racist, and dehumanizing version of migration that can be had. That is precisely what we mean when we accuse the grand coalition that governs the European Union of buying into the discourse of the far right. Enough of imposing their migratory necropolitics. We don't need an army on the border, we need humanitarian aid. Enable legal and safe pathways to enter Europe. (Left, 23-11-2021)

The MEP from the Left recalled the dire situation at the border between Belarus and Poland and emphasised that people there were treated as if they were ‘real waste’. The main point of the statement is to criticise the Commission and Council’s approach to the unfolding events, their war-dominated framings of the situation, and their support for the then-Polish far-right government. Strong criticisms are made against the separation of families at the border – resembling US President Trump’s border policies previously condemned by the European Parliament –, the support for ‘the most reactionary, racist and dehumanising version of migration’ [policies?] and the overall normalisation and acceptance of far-right rhetoric. The speaker denounced this with the term ‘necropolitics’, which is clearly tied to the idea of death. They went on to state that, instead of providing military responses, the EU should prioritise the provision of humanitarian aid and improve ‘legal and safe pathways’ for TCNs.

5. The discursive construction of irregularity in civil society

5.1. Data sample

The data sample for civil society includes a total of 278 documents (214 753 tokens). These documents are public statements signed either individually or collectively by 16 non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and social partners active at the EU level. These include both network-based NGOs and social partners representing organisations within the different Member States and international non-governmental organisations (INGOs) with a more transnational focus. The particular scope of action of the selected organisations varies: six of them specifically focus on migrants, refugees, and asylum-seekers’ rights²⁵, ten on wider questions of human rights, equality, and non-discrimination²⁶, two have a specific focus on digital rights²⁷, and two are European trade union federations focusing on labour rights and working conditions²⁸. No ‘un-civil’ society actors or anti-migrant rights organisation was identified at the EU level.

²⁵ The Platform for International Cooperation on Undocumented Migrants (PICUM), European Council on Refugees and Exiles (ECRE), the Danish Refugee Council (DRC), the International Catholic Migration Commission (ICMC) Europe, the SHARE Network, and the Churches’ Commission for Migrants in Europe (CCME).

²⁶ The European Network Against Racism (ENAR), Amnesty International, Human Rights Watch (HRW), Oxfam, the International Rescue Committee (IRC), Save the Children, Médecins Sans Frontières (MSF), Equinet, Equinox, and Statewatch.

²⁷ AccessNow and European Digital Rights (EDRI).

²⁸ The European Trade Union Confederation (ETUC) and the European Federation of Food, Agriculture and Tourism Trade Unions (EFFAT).

5.2. Quantitative analysis

5.2.1. High-frequency words

The table below identifies the most highly frequent terms used by civil society, excluding filler words, such as articles, prepositions and modal verbs ('the', 'and', 'that', 'will', etc.).

Words	Rank	Normalised frequency
EU	9	10.305
People	13	6.789
Rights	19	5.122
Their	20	5.113
European	22	4.782
Asylum	24	4.535
Migration	27	4.233
Children	28	3.995
They	29	3.800
Human	32	3.455
Europe	33	3.385
Migrants	34	3.190
International	35	3.115
Refugees	37	2.999
States	39	2.929
Border	40	2.906
Member	44	2.570
Countries	48	2.300
Protection	50	2.221
Detention	52	2.175
Greece	60	1.877
Them	62	1.830
Authorities	63	1.779
Support	64	1.774
Law	65	1.728
Borders	66	1.704
Country	67	1.653
Access	69	1.630
Greek	70	1.625
Commission	71	1.583

Civil society's high-frequency-word list reveals, as expected, a more marked emphasis on rights and violations (*rights, asylum, human, protection, detention, support*). As with the Commission and the Parliament, civil society also focuses on the EU, its Member States (*EU, European, Europe, states, member, commission*), and their *borders*. Unlike the former two, however, the *international* dimension is more

significant, as well as specific EU countries such as *Greece*. *Asylum* and *migration* are among the main results, together with *children*, *migrants*, and *refugees*. Moreover, the list does not include any first-person pronouns but only third-person ones (*their*, *they*), showing that civil society mostly focuses on TCNs or other third actors (e.g., *authorities*).

For the civil society corpus, it must be noted that specific words might be overrepresented in the results of the quantitative analysis. This is mainly due to their being included in the names of specific NGOs who are signatories of individual or joint statements (e.g., Human Rights Watch, Save the Children, Greek Refugee Council, etc.).

In the following sections, the Report will assess the frequency of these words, in relation to their specific semantic groups, to identify trends and what their high occurrence means.

5.2.2. *Semantic groups*

Unlike for the European Commission and the European Parliament, the most frequently mentioned group in civil society discourse is Rights, with a high total normalised frequency of 70.951. This group encompasses subcategories such as Asylum/Refugees (30.612), Fundamental Rights (19.595), Violations (11.814), Justice (5.928), and EU Values (3.003). Frequently occurring terms include ‘rights’ (5.122), ‘asylum’ (4.535), and ‘human’ (3.455). This is closely followed by the Governance group, with a total normalised frequency of 70.448. This group covers Institutions (32.479), Policy (23.227), Legislation (9.793), Politics (4.289), and Names (0.661). Key terms in Governance include ‘EU’ (10.305), ‘European’ (4.782), and ‘states’ (2.929).

Next in prominence is the Time and Space group, with a total normalised frequency of 64.395. This group includes Geography (45.080) and Time (19.315). Commonly mentioned words in this category are ‘Europe’ (3.385), ‘international’ (3.115), and ‘countries’ (2.300), followed by ‘greece’ (1.876), ‘libya’ (1.411), ‘sea’ (1.271), and ‘years’ (0.866). The Subject group comes next, with a total normalised frequency of 42.914. This group discusses topics such as People (21.047), Social Identity (11.432), Lived Experience (8.833), and Family/Household (1.602). Common terms are ‘people’ (6.789), ‘their’ (5.113), ‘children’ (3.995), ‘they’ (3.799), ‘men’ (0.754), and ‘women’ (0.875).

The Borders and Migration group has a total normalised frequency of 36.530. This includes Status (13.383), Borders (11.599), Entry (9.113), and Residence (2.435). Frequently used words include ‘migration’ (4.233), ‘border’ (2.906), and ‘migrants’ (3.190). Welfare and Services is another key group, with a total normalised frequency of 21.932, covering Inclusion and Social Protection (10.067), Care and Relief (5.634), Health (4.708), Education (0.964), and Housing (0.559). Common terms include ‘support’ (1.774), ‘access’ (1.630), ‘needs’ (1.085), and ‘health’ (0.722).

The IOs and NGOs group, with a total normalised frequency of 14.519, features terms such as ‘Amnesty’ (0.959), ‘organisations’ (0.843), and ‘council’²⁹ (0.834). The Work and Economy group holds a normalised frequency of 13.020, split into Employment and Work (11.152) and Economy (1.867). Prominent terms

²⁹ While also employed as ‘Council of the European Union/EU’, in the civil society corpus, the word ‘council’ is overwhelmingly used in the name of INGOs, e.g., the Greek Council for Refugees and the European Council on Refugees and Exiles, and IOs, i.e., the Council of Europe.

include ‘workers’ (1.010), ‘work’ (0.880), ‘labour’ (0.838), and ‘skills’ (0.587). Policing and Crime is a moderately focused group, with a total normalised frequency of 12.922. The most prominent words are ‘detention’ (2.175), ‘authorities’ (1.779), and ‘police’ (0.838).

The Numbers and Quantities group has a normalised frequency of 12.088, featuring terms such as ‘many’ (1.192), ‘one’ (1.136), and ‘number’ (0.740), reflecting a statistical or numerical dimension to migration discussions. The Crisis and Defence group, with a normalised frequency of 11.190, includes Defence (7.683) and Crisis (3.506). Frequently used terms like ‘against’ (1.169), ‘risk’ (1.080), and ‘violence’ (1.215) reveal a focus on crisis management and defensive measures in migration contexts. The Returns and Expulsion group, with a relatively low normalised frequency of 2.729, focuses on terms like ‘return’ (0.545), ‘returned’ (0.335), and ‘returns’ (0.289), reflecting discussions on return policies and expulsions. Finally, the Obligations group, with a total normalised frequency of 2.249, includes terms such as ‘integration’ (0.773), ‘responsibility’ (0.671), and ‘obligations’ (0.242).

Table 3: Semantic group analysis in the civil society corpus

Semantic group	Subgroup	No of words	NormFreq	Total NormFreq
Rights	Asylum/refugees	78	30.612	70.951
	Fundamental Rights	39	19.595	
	Violations	56	11.814	
	Justice	34	5.928	
	EU values	16	3.003	
Governance	Institutions	48	32.479	70.448
	Policy	100	23.227	
	Legislation	40	9.793	
	Politics	34	4.289	
	Names	10	0.661	
Time and space	Geography	165	45.080	64.395
	Time	78	19.315	
Subject	People	18	21.047	42.914
	Social identity	42	11.432	
	Lived experience	54	8.833	
	Family/Household	7	1.602	
Borders and migration	Status	24	13.383	36.530
	Borders	53	11.599	
	Entry	55	9.113	
	Residence	10	2.435	
Welfare and services	Inclusion and social protection	29	10.067	21.932
	Care and relief	21	5.634	
	Health	24	4.708	
	Education	7	0.964	
	Housing	5	0.559	
IOs and NGOs	IOs and NGOs	76	14.519	14.519

Work and economy	Employment and work	51	11.152	13.020
	Economy	16	1.867	
Policing and crime	Policing and crime	54	12.922	12.922
Numbers and quantities	Numbers and quantities	42	12.088	12.088
Crisis and defence	Defence	40	7.683	11.190
	Crisis	18	3.506	
Returns and expulsion	Returns and expulsion	15	2.729	2.729
Obligations	Obligations	14	2.249	2.249

Figure 3: Semantic group analysis for the civil society corpus (2019-2024) - visualised

5.2.3. Collocation analysis

The collocation analysis of key terms – *migra**, *irregular*, *refugee(s)*, and employment-related words such as *work**, *labour*, and **employ** – reveals distinct patterns in how migration and irregularity are framed by civil society organisations.

The data indicates a strong emphasis on human rights, legal protection, and humanitarian assistance. Unlike the more control-oriented and securitarian discourse observed in institutional narratives, civil society focuses on the rights and lived experiences of TCNs, advocating for their welfare.

Migration

For collocations with **migra** terms, the semantic group Rights emerges as highly significant, with a sum likelihood of 641.425, almost entirely within the Asylum/Refugees subgroup. The most prominent collocates are 'asylum' (263.877), 'refugees' (226.217), and 'seekers' (104.541). The semantic group Governance follows suit with a total sum likelihood values of 633.022, mostly split between the subgroups Policy (289.674), Legislation (248.811), and, less prominently, Institutions (94.537). Among the terms in this group, 'pact' has the highest likelihood value (225.896), followed by 'policies' (130.055), and 'policy' (101.959).

The semantic group Borders and Migration is slightly less but still significantly prominent in the collocation results with a sum likelihood value of 589.311, mostly split between Status (315.076) and Borders (192.198). Among the most relevant terms are 'irregular' (93.280), 'management' (86.662), and 'undocumented' (66.159). The semantic group IOs and NGOs comes fourth with 449.232 and includes both the name of the specific organisations who have signed the collected statements and the name of individual experts, executives, and advisors from those organisations. Worth noting is also the relatively substantial likelihood value of the semantic groups Subject (115.187) and Work and Economy (114.184).

Unlike the European Commission's discourse, which often centres on border control and migration management, civil society focuses more on human rights and the protection of mobile TCNs, while still paying attention to the policy and legislative landscape in which they operate.

Irregular

Despite showing a significant likelihood value with **migra** (see above), the word 'irregular' does not appear often in the overall data sample: 70 times overall and only in 35 documents out of the total 278. More often than not, 'migrants' or 'migration' is not juxtaposed to any adjective defining their (ir)regularity, except in the case of direct quotes from legislative and policy documents or when advocating for 'regular/legal' migration pathways.

Because of this, the collocation results for 'irregular' are not numerous and are mostly comprised in the Borders and Migration semantic group (221.357), i.e., 'entry' (81.138), 'migration' (63.641) and 'stay' (48.319). The only other two represented semantic groups are Policing and Crime (56.770) – which is fully attributable to 'facilitating' – and Crisis and Defence (18.559) – due to the presence of 'prevent'. Both words are used in direct quotes of legislative proposals or to refer to the EU's or Member States' current policies or practices – thus, used indirectly as a critique of other actors' ways of speaking and not directly to describe reality from a civil society perspective.

Refugee

The collocation analysis for 'refugee*' shows that Borders and Migration has the highest sum likelihood of 717.664, mainly within the 'Status' subgroup (509.742) and almost totally due to the word 'migrants' (431.843). With 554.608, the semantic group IOs and NGOs comes next with terms such as 'Council' (128.853), 'Jesuit' (107.527) and 'Danish' (68.904) – which is clearly due to the word 'refugee' being included in the name of several organisations (i.e., Jesuit Refugee Service Europe and the Danish Refugee Council).

Time and Space shows a sum likelihood value of 467.976, entirely ascribable to the Geography subgroup. Among the key collocation results, 'Syrian' (114.892), 'global' (57.887), 'Ukraine' (54.113), and 'world' (47.729). The semantic group Rights follows with 513.826–481.968 for the subgroup for Asylum/Refugees and 31.858 for Justice. The main words in this group are 'resettle' (124.573), 'resettled' (92.563), 'resettlement' (61.394), and 'GCR' (i.e., the Global Compact on Refugees; 45.030). Moderate correlation is also noticeable with the semantic groups on Welfare and Services (223.586) and Governance (106.508)

Work and Employment

For civil society too, employment-related terms – 'work*', 'labour', and '*employ*' – mostly correlate with words in the Work and Economy semantic group (1432.987). Key collocation results include 'market' (359.705), 'shortages' (150.691), 'skills' (102.65), and 'workers' (95.988). Among the results, specific labour sectors are identifiable – namely, sex work ('sex' at 85.541), seasonal work ('seasonal' at 57.668), agriculture ('agricultural' at 55.326), domestic work ('domestic' at 35.746), and platform work ('platform' at 31.357) – as well as 'exploitation' (60.365)³⁰.

Borders and Migration is the second most likely semantic group at 474.086, with 'migrant' being the second most likely word associated with the employment-related terms, after 'market'. Other key terms include 'permit' (65.382), 'mobility' (61.109), 'mobile' (49.335). Overall, the disparity in likelihood between Work and Economy and Border and Migration is starkly lower than for the Commission and the Parliament, showing more correlation between employment-related concepts and human mobility.

More moderate but still significant correlation can be observed with the semantic groups Welfare and Services (116.712), particularly in relation to Inclusion and Social Protection (64.648) and Rights (98.299), with 'exploitation' falling in the Violations subgroup.

Gender

Significant differences are observed in how civil society addresses family and gender in the context of migration. Frequency data shows that women-related terms ('women', 'girls', 'woman', 'female', 'girl') appear 246 times, while men-related terms ('men', 'man', 'boys', 'boy', 'male') appear 264 times. Children-related terms are far more frequent, appearing 985 times.

The collocates for 'women' and related terms are predominantly within the Subject semantic group (1063.395), especially the subgroup on Social Identity (793.228) and Lived Experience (197.873). Significant collocation results include 'men' (312.168), 'children' (202.914), 'pregnant' (142.929), and 'girls' (93.808).

³⁰ Exploitation is included in both the Rights semantic group (the Violations subgroup) and the Work and Employment semantic group (Employment and work subgroup).

Outside of the Subject semantic group, an individual term that shows a high likelihood value is 'Nigerian' at 100.546.

For 'men' and related terms, the collocates also fall mainly within Subject (827.366) and, more specifically, the Social Identity subgroup (783.588). Key collocates include 'women' (298.962), 'old' (124.325), and 'children' (90.747). Like for women, specific nationalities are also among the main collocation results, i.e., Syrian (119.362) and, to a lesser extent, Pakistani (34.662). The semantic group on Crisis and defence shows a significant likelihood value (251.423) and includes words such as 'armed' (98.115), 'masked'³¹ (46.594), 'civilian' (42.271), and 'uniforms' (38.631). It must be noted that all of these words appear to be used in contexts of violence against TCNs, i.e., 'men' carrying arms, wearing masks and uniforms attacking TCNs within Europe, at the borders, or in third countries.

Children are a major focus in civil society's discourse, with the Subject group showing a sum likelihood of 1,547.131, particularly within 'Lived Experience' (792.38) and 'Family/Household' (218.991). The most significant collocation results include 'unaccompanied' (634.145), 'women' (241.276), 'families' (163.063), 'men' (115.398), 'vulnerable' (78.28), and 'young' (35.114). 'Save' is the single word with the highest likelihood value but is entirely due to the name of the INGO Save the Children. Rights and Borders and Migration show modest correlation at 157.125 and 132.792 respectively.

5.3. Qualitative analysis

5.3.1. Proto-narratives

Based on the quantitative data, the proto-narratives below were identified as statistically representative samples for the civil society corpus.

- *Regular migration pathways are needed to avoid the risks associated with irregular migration.*
- *The EU is failing to address human rights violations and abuses in its border policies.*
- *Border authorities commit human rights violations through unlawful pushbacks and arbitrary detention of migrants.*
- *Member States must prevent the exploitation of migrant workers in agriculture, food processing industries and domestic work.*
- *The EU must ensure safety and protect the rights of all people on the move and all migrant workers, regardless of their status.*
- *Employers benefit from migrant labour but often perpetuate exploitation, especially in low-wage sectors.*

Based on the evidence gathered through the quantitative analysis and the proto-narratives identified above, this Section will now collect and assess individual statements by the European Parliament on the topics of migration and (ir)regularity, employment and gender, as well as other relevant topics such as Covid-19, returns, and crisis and defence.

³¹ 'Masked' refers specifically to the act of wearing a mask to conceal one's identity in violent settings – not wearing a mask for health-related purposes.

5.3.2. Migration and (ir)regularity

As noted in the collocation analysis for ‘irregular’, the notion of irregularity in the civil society corpus is not so frequent. When it is present, it is either a direct quote or reference to EU and/or Member States’ policies and mostly relates to Borders and Migration and Policing and Crime. Accordingly, for this section, the scope was widened to encompass these themes and see how civil society differs from the other analysed actors.

Overall, all the statements collected and analysed emphasise the same aspects: humanitarian issues at the EU’s external borders, the inadequacy and counter-productive nature of EU policies, fundamental rights violations, arbitrary detention at the borders, and the criminalisation of civil society actors engaged in search and rescue at sea or offering assistance at the land borders.

There is an acute and pressing humanitarian imperative to offer assistance and protection to all people on the move, irrespective of their status. To enable this, the EU should encourage and enable the establishment of humanitarian service points – places that provide a welcoming and safe environment for all migrants to access services, without fear of being arrested or reported to the authorities. This would be an important step to help protect the life, dignity and rights of every individual on the move. In recent years, EU actions aimed at countering irregular migration have undermined migrants’ rights and humanitarian needs. The suffering witnessed at Europe’s sea and land borders is a stark reminder that states should reintroduce a human rights-based approach to border governance.

While it is important to address the humanitarian consequences of smuggling and trafficking, disproportionate focus on border control and externalisation measures have undermined migrants’ wellbeing within the EU and along increasingly dangerous migratory routes. For many, the services of smuggling and trafficking networks are the only option to reach safety and security. With European countries approaching a precarious tipping point where established human rights approaches enshrined in EU and international law are in danger of being irreversibly eroded, we call for migrants’ fundamental rights to be upheld, in line European values and standards. Looking beyond restrictive border management responses in the name of deterrence policy, attending to migrants needs and rights is a task of global solidarity. (Red Cross 17-12-2021)

The statement by the Red Cross above clearly exemplifies most of these preoccupations. The starting point is that there is an ‘acute and pressing’ humanitarian imperative to assist and protect all people on the move, regardless of their immigration or residency status. The main narrative is that EU policies aiming to counter ‘irregular’ migration have resulted in fundamental rights violations, human suffering at the external borders and ‘fear of being arrested or reported to the authorities’ for civil society actors providing assistance. Border control and externalisation policies have made all types of human mobility to the EU increasingly dangerous, fostering people’s reliance on smuggling and trafficking networks. More broadly, the Red Cross highlights the ongoing erosion of international law, international and EU human rights standards, and EU values, urging policymakers to go beyond restrictive border management responses and ensure that protection and assistance are provided to all people on the move, irrespective of their status.

In the statement below, Amnesty International also emphasises similar aspects, with a specific focus on the criminalisation of civil society:

Civil society organizations have also been targeted and harassed through the misuse of criminal law. In Croatia, non-governmental organisations (NGOs) Are You Syrious and the Centre for Peace Studies have been harassed, intimidated and prosecuted for ‘facilitating irregular migration’ after documenting and reporting on people being pushed back with excessive force by police at the borders with Bosnia and Herzegovina and Serbia. In Italy, rescuers who save the lives of those making the journey to Europe on unseaworthy boats have been subjected to smear campaigns, criminal investigations, forced to follow a code of conduct which can delay rescues, and left stranded at sea without a safe port to disembark the people they rescue. Since August 2017, the Italian authorities have impounded NGO vessels on multiple occasions, leaving fewer boats available for rescue operations even as the rate of deaths at sea increased in 2018 and 2019.

We volunteered to assist those in need. We could spend 25 years in jail for aiding survivors, but if you ask me now if I would change anything, knowing that my life could be turned upside down as a result, I am telling you that I would do the exact same thing. (Amnesty International 03-03-2020)

The excerpt focuses on the misuse of criminal law against multiple civil society actors. In relation to Croatia, they specifically mention the accusation of ‘facilitating irregular migration’ for two NGOs who were reporting pushbacks and violence at the borders with Bosnia and Herzegovina and Serbia. A second example is humanitarian workers in Italy who were subjected to ‘smear campaigns’ and were forced to abide by a strict code of conduct constraining their ability to save people stranded at sea and exposing them to further danger. Italian authorities are accused of impounding NGO vessels, limiting the number of search and rescue actors in the Mediterranean and leading to more deaths. Despite these events, the speaker says, civil society is determined to continue assisting ‘those in need’ regardless of all penalties they might face, including long-term prison sentences.

In this case, civil society actors emphasises that the notion of ‘irregularity’ and the rhetorical link with criminality are used by European national authorities to frame civil society as ‘facilitators’ or ‘smugglers’ and punish them for aiding people in need or facing danger at the EU borders (see [PICUM, 2017](#); [PICUM, 2024](#)).

Other statements are more focused on the dangers TCNs are exposed to in third countries, and the complicity of the EU:

In Niger, European pressure to criminalise smuggling and detain migrants has forced more migrants towards perilous underground migration routes. UN reports indicate that authorities in the desert region between Niger and Libya are responsible for over 60 percent of physical abuse against migrant women. Nonetheless, the EU channels funds - earmarked for aid - to these authorities for migration purposes despite their dismal human rights track record. (OXFAM 21-09-2023)

This statement by OXFAM emphasises that ‘European pressure to criminalise smuggling and detain migrants’ forces people to rely on more unsafe ways to move and exposes them to further dangers, for example gender-based violence perpetrated by official authorities against women between Niger and Libya. The speaker highlights that these are the same authorities who are receiving compensation from EU funds, regardless of the evidence of violence and their human rights violations.

While in Section 4 the notion of ‘complicity’ was used by specific MEPs against civil society, in this instance, civil society is employing it to hold EU authorities accountable for their financing and support of third-country officials accused of violence and human rights violations. EU policies aiming at countering ‘irregular migration’ and, by extension, ‘criminalising smuggling and detaining migrants’, are identified as the factor enabling this violence.

5.3.3. *Employment*

In the realm of employment, the collected civil society statements deploy similar narratives and emphasise analogous aspects – namely, improving migrant workers’ rights, ensuring equal treatment and protection regardless of migration status, addressing exploitation and discrimination in the labour market, and advocating for regularisation as a key measure to reduce vulnerability and enhance social inclusion.

The statement below by ETUC takes a critical stance on the overall approach dominating current EU migration policy:

Spending EU funds on border fences would cross an ethical red line, take us further away from the social Europe that would deliver for working people and be a criminal misuse of public money. Stopping migration is simply not the priority of working people, who are struggling to put food on the table, pay the rent and heat their homes because of obscene corporate profits which are driving inflation. The people causing real problems for working people travel in private jets not inflatable boats. Regularisation of migrants would do more than any other measure to help working people, both migrant and local, by stopping employers from exploiting undocumented migrants to undercut wages. But there isn’t a single mention of regularisation and increasing regular migration routes in the conclusions, which shows leaders are more interested in dog whistles than real solutions. (ETUC 10-02-2023)

ETUC underlines the disconnect between the priorities identified by the EU and Member States (i.e. ‘EU funds to border walls’) and the objective of a social Europe that works for working people. They underline that stopping migration is not the priority of working people, but rather addressing the cost of living crisis, corporate exploitation, and the need for better labour protections for all workers. A distinctive narrative in this statement is that ‘the people causing real problems for working people travel in private jets not inflatable boats’. Regularisation programmes are described as the most effective and desirable solution for all workers – regardless of status – because they would prevent the labour exploitation of migrants and lower wages for local workers. The absence of these considerations lead ETUC to believe that leaders are not interested in ‘real solutions’. Overall, the main message is that the interests of workers – local or migrant – are aligned and not opposed. The ‘real problem’ is exploitative employers and ineffective national leaders.

In the statement below, EFFAT, the European Trade Federation representing workers in the Food, Agriculture, Tourism, and Domestic Work sectors, focuses on the centrality of mobile and migrant workers in the European labour market:

EFFAT sectors significantly depend on the work of millions of mobile and migrant workers in Europe. They are the backbone of a thriving European agriculture, a flourishing food processing industry, and a rampant hospitality sector. As many are domestic workers, they even allow millions of working people to enjoy improved work-life balance and come back to a clean house. Yet, and despite their essential role in

society, many of them are subject to evident discrimination in the labour market and even labour exploitation. Unregulated labour intermediaries, abusive subcontracting and lack of inspections are behind some of the major hardships for migrant workers, with many of them unable to report any violation of their rights without risking retaliation or deportation. (EFFAT 31-05-2023)

The statement specifically mentions the important role and contribution of these workers in Europe's agriculture, food procession, hospitality, and domestic work. Despite their essential role, EFFAT highlights, they are subject to discrimination in the labour market and labour exploitation, often due to the lack and inadequacy of regulations and protections. One of the main difficulty experienced by migrant workers is the constant risk of retaliation and deportation, which makes them unable to report rights violations.

In the following excerpt, PICUM also focuses on abusive employers and exploitation:

In this case our strawberries were being picked literally at gunpoint. In others, the gun might not be there but similar coercion is felt by workers – if standing up for your rights might lead to your arrest... and nothing else – minimal chance of actually getting the wages you are owed or the person being held to account. What we need is for labour rights to mean something in the fields – that they are actually enforced, and enforceable for all workers, without any risk of denunciation or deportation. (PICUM 04-09-2020)

Starting from a specific case of agricultural migrant workers held at gunpoint in a strawberry field, PICUM underlines the violence and coercion experienced by migrant workers and their inability to report injustices and reclaim their rights for fear of being reported. They also emphasise the need for the effective enforcement of labour rights in the agricultural sector for all workers (irrespective of status) without the risk of their reported to immigration authorities and/or being deported.

Finally, Save the Children emphasises questions related to the households of migrant workers:

This report tells us that workers exploited in agriculture, in addition to being direct victims of this condition, are also parents, mothers and fathers of 'invisible' children who grow up in our country without essential rights. This serious dimension of exploitation has too often been ignored up to now. It is essential to recognise the existence of these children, to ensure that each of them has registered residence, enrolment in the health service and school and the support services essential for growth. Save the Children is calling on the Ministry of Labour and Social Policies in Italy to use its Three-Year Plan to combat labour exploitation in agriculture and illegal hiring with a specific programme for the emergence and care of the children of agricultural workers. (Save the Children 26-7-2023)

On top of being workers – and often being subject to exploitation, migrant workers have families and children. Save the Children specifically pays attention to the condition of these 'invisible children', who grow up in Europe without essential rights. This is described as a direct consequence of the exploitation that their parents experience and often translates into lack of registration and access to healthcare and education, which are essential to children. Thus, the main message is that national authorities (in this case Italy's) must effectively address the exploitation of migrant workers and ensure that their children receive the care and rights that they need and deserve. This household dimension is missing in most of the other statements (particularly of the other institutional actors) – where the employment dimension is completely siloed from household/family issues.

5.3.4. Gender

As already mentioned in Section 5.2.3, when it comes to gender dynamics, the civil society corpus differs from that of the Commission and Parliament. The statement below shows that – to some extent – women and children are once again more likely to be associated to the notion of victimhood and vulnerability:

There are currently estimated to be more than 5,000 migrants and refugees trapped in these centres, including women and children who are particularly vulnerable and in need of protection. (IRC 17-06-2021)

The 199 people we recently rescued, including pregnant women and babies, were forced to travel around 1,300 km to disembark, although other Italian ports were much closer. (MSF 13-07-2023)

Furthermore, individuals with specific vulnerabilities, such as people with disabilities or those experiencing trauma, may need adjustments or special assistance. Women and girls require access to specific services and safe spaces, and children need individual measures of protection. (DRC 18-03-2021)

Many unaccompanied children and children traveling with their families are amongst those trapped at the EU's borders, at great risk of human rights violations and in urgent need of humanitarian assistance and access to asylum procedures. Around half of all asylum claims from unaccompanied children in the EU are from Afghan nationals. A 9 December position paper issued by the civil society organizations states that many more Afghan children are traveling 'under the radar' as they attempt to join family members already living in EU countries. (ICMC 16-12-2021)

These four statements highlight the precarious conditions faced by 'vulnerable' groups within migration contexts. The first statement by IRC specifically focuses on 5 000 people in detention centres; the second one by MSF on people rescued at sea and forced by national authorities to disembark in distant ports; the third one speaks more generally of people experiencing trauma and requiring specific types of assistance; and the fourth one is more focused on children on the move (both unaccompanied and traveling with their family) and the risks that they face. All four underline that the centrality of special reception and protection needs, primarily gender and age-specific ones.

Unlike the other actors, however, the attention dedicated to these issues does not come hand in hand with a total silence surrounding masculinity:

Greece has become a dumping ground for the men, women and children that the European Union has failed to protect. (...) Those sheltering outside the camp include at least 79 unaccompanied children, as well as pregnant women, elderly people, people with chronic health conditions, including acute mental illnesses such as psychosis, and survivors of torture and sexual violence. (MSF 18-03-2019)

MSF has repeatedly denounced Moria camp as a human tragedy driven by government policies. This situation makes it clear, once again, that the migration policies generated by the EU-Turkey deal of 2016 are creating unnecessary suffering and putting many lives in danger. 'Children, women and men are paying the unjust price of migration policies based on deterrence (...) Denying children suffering from serious diseases access to healthcare is just the latest cynical move, and it is truly beyond belief. (MSF 23-12-2020)

The numbers alone are outrageous, but behind the statistics are real children, women and men, who experienced danger, fear, perilous journeys and multiple rights abuses, from humiliating and degrading treatment, to being deprived of their belongings or exposed to physical and psychological abuse (...). And

*often, these people have had not one, but multiple such experiences, at the same or different borders.
(DRC 23-07-2021)*

These statements acknowledge the physical and psychological abuses, violence, and fundamental rights violations experienced by men, women, and children in reception/detention camps in Greece or along their journey. By acknowledging that ‘men’ are also subjected to such experiences, civil society does not limit itself to a gender and age-specific understanding of protection or vulnerability. Instead, it recognises that, while gender and age-specific needs deserve specific attention, these are not the only grounds that warrant protection and dedicated measures. Grounds for protection and special needs are ultimately the result of the social identity and lived experience of individuals and might affect any individual.

5.3.5. Covid-19

As regards Covid, civil society is mostly concerned with the impacts of the pandemic on already disadvantaged groups, including irregularised migrants:

As the struggle to contain the virus seems to mainly protect the most privileged, we need to rethink a system that is failing to deliver equality and justice for the most marginalised and refocus on solidarity to tackle the deep challenges ahead of us. No one is immune to the Covid-19 crisis, but it impacts refugees at the borders, undocumented people, low income families, homeless people, elderly people, women, people with disabilities or a chronic illness—including many racialised people—more. They have less or no access to health services, many already in precarious work will have even less job security with restriction measures in place across Europe, and some don't even have homes. (ENAR 19-03-2020)

ENAR, for example, focuses on the uneven public policy responses to the pandemic and the need to uphold equality, justice, and solidarity for the most marginalised groups within the European society. Undocumented people are included within a wider group of people experiencing sub-par services and care discrimination (i.e., refugees, low-income families, homeless people, etc.), which shows the attempt to shift the focus to broader questions of discrimination, racism, and social justice, rather than treating the situation as a mere ‘migration’ issue. Given the context of the pandemic, particular attention is devoted to access to healthcare, decent working conditions, and housing, as well as underlying the existing obstacles under current policies.

Other statements focus on the impact of Covid on the external EU borders and the reception of asylum seekers in Europe:

While we acknowledge that extraordinary measures taken by European countries are needed to address the ongoing pandemic, they cannot be used as an excuse to avoid responsibility towards people in desperate need of safety. In the wake of Covid-19, solidarity with the most vulnerable is more crucial than ever before. Closing the ports is not the answer. Temporary solutions, such as deploying special ships to screen and quarantine people rescued at sea, can be successfully implemented to protect public health in the countries at the forefront or arrivals, and ensure that no lives are put at risk. But the emergency created by the Covid-19 pandemic resulting in Malta and Italy closing its ports is also a stark reminder that a sustainable and fair disembarkation mechanism in the EU is urgently needed. (IRC 20-04-2020)

The IRC, for example, recognises the effort of national governments to put in place extraordinary measures to face the pandemic, but urges them to not use these measures as an excuse to forfeit their

responsibilities towards ‘people in desperate need of safety’. They argue that solidarity is more important than ever, given the context at hand, and that solutions such as ‘deploying special ships to screen and quarantine people rescued at sea’ can be effective at preventing further public health risks and saving lives at sea and must be preferred to the closure of national ports. Finally, they cite the cases of Malta and Italy closing their ports to advocate for effective EU-wide solidarity mechanisms.

5.3.6. Return

On returns (and deportations), civil society clearly relies more than the other actors on narratives emphasising the injustice and fundamental rights violations experienced by the migrants affected, as well as on the problematic aspects of agreements with third countries to contain and return people.

In liberal democratic states, deportations should be considered a matter of ultimate last resort. The plans of the EU and its member states point in the other direction – less rights for individuals and more powers for the authorities, making expulsions simpler and swifter. In the context of a global pandemic and a worldwide movement for racial equality, it is high time for some fresh thinking on migration, rather than increasingly punitive, expensive and ultimately unworkable measures. (...) Frontex frequently stretches its mandate to the limit, overstepping legal boundaries until a new regulation is introduced legitimising its activities. Accountability mechanisms included in the texts are insufficient, both in scope and functionality, to keep up with the agency's increased role and influence. That the monitoring of Frontex's deportation operations will now be organised and financed by the agency itself is a primary example of these deficiencies. (Statewatch 21-08-2020)

In this statement, Statewatch focuses on the EU and Member States’ current approach on return, highlighting that – despite deportations being an ultimate resort in liberal democracies – there have been increasing efforts at making returns ‘simpler and swifter’ at the expense of individuals’ human rights. It highlights the risks of this approach, particularly in a global context where there is increasing awareness of racial inequality and systemic injustices. Frontex is cited as an example of overreach, with concerns about its scope of action and lack of accountability. In light of its track record, Frontex’s self-monitoring of its own deportation operations further proves the insufficient checks and balances in place. The statement calls for an overall re-evaluation of EU return policies.

Similar criticisms are identifiable in the joint statement below:

By incentivising states to adopt new bilateral agreements, and proposing a new internal transfer procedure, the Commission's proposal promotes the proliferation of exceptional procedures, which are outside the framework set by the Return Directive and the asylum acquis, and circumvents the procedural safeguards included in the Dublin Regulation. The proposed provisions undermine the substantive and procedural guarantees for third country nationals, such as the right to request asylum, the respect of the principle of non-refoulement, and the right to an effective remedy. As mentioned above, several national-level courts have ruled on the unlawfulness of readmissions carried out under formal and informal agreements, which often led to instances of chain-refoulement. There is a serious risk that readmission agreements, if they remain a part of the current legislative proposal, could be further abused to perpetrate chain refoulement and collective expulsions, which are in violation of Article 4 of Protocol No. 4 to the European Convention on Human Rights and Article 19 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union. (Joint Statement 20-04-2022)

This statement – dealing with the 2022-2024 revision of the Schengen Borders Code – critiques the Commission's proposal encouraging member states to enter into bilateral agreements and the implementation of a new intra-EU transfer procedure. It argues that these initiatives lead to the creation of exceptional procedures that operate outside established legal frameworks, i.e., the Return Directive and the Dublin Regulation. Consequently, this undermines critical protections for TCNs, including their right to asylum, the principle of *non-refoulement*, and the right to an effective remedy. The signatories stress that previous national courts' rulings against unlawful readmissions highlights the risk of facilitating chain-refoulement, where individuals are deported to countries where they may face further danger. The statement raises serious concerns about the legality and human rights implications of these readmission agreements, warning that they could result in violations of fundamental rights protected by regional human rights law and EU law. The joint statement emphasises the need for adherence to established legal safeguards within the EU's migration framework.

5.3.7. Crisis and defence

When it comes to crisis and defence, civil society tends to criticise the framing of mobility-related occurrences through this lens and focuses rather on the humanitarian aspects of crisis.

A clear example is the Joint Statement below:

As European civil society and professional organisations working on asylum, migration, humanitarian assistance and human rights, we are shocked by the continuing humanitarian crisis at the borders between the EU and Belarus which causes immense suffering and has led to the deaths of at least ten people. (...) While the people in the middle of the crisis are being used as parties in the conflict between the EU and Belarus which has a security dimension, the people themselves are not a security threat, and should neither be referred to nor be treated by either side as though they were a weapon. Indeed, all accounts suggest that there are many highly vulnerable groups among those caught up in these events, including pregnant women, families with young children and people who are elderly or injured. Among them are people who have fled war and persecution from Syria, Yemen, Afghanistan and Iraq, and who, in the absence of safe and legal pathways, had no alternative way to reach safety. We also note that despite the serious tensions that exist between the states involved, the situation, like many others at the EU's borders, is manageable, and should be approached with a sense of perspective. Globally, many countries in very fragile situations face complex displacement challenges, with geo-political and security dimensions and involving far larger numbers of people. What is needed is a clear-headed response that includes a firm defence of the right to asylum, and of EU and international law. (Joint Statement 26-11-2021)

This statement expresses profound concern about the 'humanitarian crisis' at the EU-Belarus border, emphasising the loss of life and suffering of the people affected, including vulnerable groups. As with the previous statements shown, civil society organisations explicitly mention that the people affected are caught in the midst of a crisis – rather than constituting one. The statement above highlights that people should not be treated as security threats, weapons, or instruments of political conflicts. It critiques the EU's response to these events (the so-called instrumentalisation of migrants³²) as disproportionate and overly militarised and underlines that most of those affected have fled war and persecution but, due to the lack of safe and regular pathways, had no viable alternative to reach safety. The statement further sustains that

³² See Carrera et al., 2023.

the situation at the EU's external border is in fact manageable, particularly when taking into account the wider local displacement context. The signatories advocate for a 'clear-headed' response grounded in EU and international law, rather than a reactionary and punitive approach.

The statement below by ETUC is on the same topic:

The EU's militaristic approach to the humanitarian crisis on its border has played into the hands of Lukashenko's regime and rewriting fundamental rights under pressure would only serve to further encourage hostile actors to weaponise the lives of vulnerable people to exert pressure on Europe. The suspension of media freedom is also setting Europe on a slippery slope – it is more important than ever too that journalists are given free access to the area. The EU's and member states' response to the arrival of migrants cannot be the deployment of border guards, walls and razor wire, and their detention or deportation. The EU should do what it should have done from the start - organise the reception of these people in respect of their rights and support them in applying for asylum or international protection and relocate them among all member states. The EU's panicked response to this manageable problem shows once again the need to adopt a coherent migration policy based on human rights and shared responsibility. Rather than building the walls of fortress Europe higher and higher, we need more legal routes to labour migration which ensures rogue employers can no longer exploit undocumented migrants. (ETUC 01-12-2021)

This statement critiques the EU's militaristic response to the events at its border with Belarus, arguing that such an approach exacerbates the situation, empowers authoritarian regimes, and puts the fundamental rights framework at risk of being undermined. ETUC specifically mentions the limitations imposed on journalists and media freedoms as a sign of danger. Instead of responding with border guards, walls, razor wire, detention, and deportation, the response should be more organised reception of these people, support for their asylum applications, and effective EU-wide relocations and responsibility-sharing. The statement contraposes the image of an ever higher fortress Europe to additional regular and safe pathways, which would also ensure that abusive employers would not be able to exploit undocumented migrants.

The statement of ICMC below, instead, addresses the development of the migration-crisis narrative:

In the first phase, migration was presented as a humanitarian crisis, and migrants were depicted merely as victims. This phase was followed by a more negative portrayal of migrants, with the media beginning to use terms such as 'Muslim invasion' and 'worrying numbers'. The final phase involved a polarization of opinions within the media, with the emergence of fear and conspiracy theories on the one hand, and publication of success stories on the other. This tendency towards sensationalist reporting of the migrant influx is not limited to Romania. Participants shared similar examples from across Europe. (ICMC 30-07-2019).

This statement focuses on the evolution of the public discourse surrounding migration. It notes a significant shift from portraying migrants as victims in a humanitarian crisis to framing them negatively as threats or burdens, relying on xenophobic messaging or alarmist indefinite quantities. According to them, this was then followed by increasing polarisation, with fear and conspiracy theories on one side and success stories on the other, and this phenomenon was observable all across Europe – not only in Romania, which is the main focus of the statement.

6. Comparative insights

Building on the analysis of the three corpora presented in the previous sections, the following Section will first identify how the three actors' preoccupations and specific thematic focuses compare and contrast with each other. Following this keyness analysis, the evidence collected will be examined and critically assessed to identify key comparative findings.

6.1. Keyness analysis

The keyness results are helpful to identify the distinct linguistic patterns and thematic concerns of the European Commission, the European Parliament, and civil society organisations. In each of the subsections below, the three corpora are compared to identify which words the individual actors are statistically more likely to use.

6.1.1. *European Commission and European Parliament*

When one compares the European Commission's discourse with the European Parliament's, clear patterns and divergences emerge. See Table 4: Keyness Analysis - Commission and Parliament below:

Table 4: Keyness Analysis - Commission and Parliament

Commission	Likelihood	Parliament	Likelihood
EU	3970.729	Government	437.075
Member	1819.25	Question	397.202
Labour	1004.202	European	396.091
Residence	963.767	Talking	387.929
Directive	935.173	Illegal	359.342
States	912.882	Polish	357.416
Third	836.636	Problem	334.233
Platform	790.565	People	331.884
Visa	782.982	Unfortunately	312.929
Support	782.791	Poland	280.785
Skills	758.288	Now	268.536
Talent	745.808	Human	259.553
Nationals	744.237	Europe	259.334
Return	730.602	Certificate	257.894
Management	653.189	NGOs	237.468

The Commission is more likely to speak about the EU as a whole (or at least use the acronym) and Member States. It is also possible to notice the higher likelihood for the Commission to focus on specific legislative files ('directive'). On a more substantial level, questions related to employment and the labour market, residence rights, visa policy, return and (migration, border, asylum and crisis) management are highly relevant. As regards employment, one can notice the Commission's higher reliance on the notions of

'talent' and 'skills' in the realm of human mobility and migration – which tends to be limited to highly-skilled workers and to exclude blue-collar migrant workers.

For the Parliament, a majority of the initial results were related to the specificities of parliamentary debates, their language, procedures, and customs ('mr', 'president', 'madam', 'colleagues', 'commissioner', 'ladies' and 'gentlemen'). While they are indicative of the institutional, formal, but also conversational tone used in the Parliament, they were screened out to give priority to more substantive terms. Among these, the one with the highest probability is 'government', indicating the MEPs' likelihood of commenting on specific EU or third-countries' governments' policies. It is followed by 'European' and, more distantly by 'Europe', which may indicate the use of these two words as a peculiarity of the MEPs' language—as opposed to the Commission's higher likelihood of using 'EU'.

A more substantive finding is the presence of words such as 'illegal' and 'Polish'/'Poland'. As already explained in Sections 4.2.3 and 4.3.2, 'illegal' appears more frequently than 'irregular' in the data sample for the Parliament with respect to migration, particularly for far-right political groups. This appears to be a peculiarity of this institution—at least in comparison with the Commission. The high likelihood of 'Polish' and 'Poland' may suggest greater outspokenness by certain national groups of MEPs, higher criticism targeted at national migration and asylum policies, as well as Poland's heightened exposure to the impacts of the Russian invasion of Ukraine, including the resulting human displacement.

Other results might be tied to the specific type of discourse used in the Parliament. 'Problem' is used by MEPs from all political groups to advance their specific concerns and priorities. The likelihood of 'people' can be explained by its frequent use in the spoken language and the higher propensity of the Commission to use specific legal categories to speak about individuals, instead of general terms like 'people'. 'Now' might also appear highly likely due to the more conversational/spoken nature of the Parliament's way of speaking, as well as by a propensity to speak about immediate matters and/or highlight their urgency to advance specific concerns. 'Unfortunately' is also likely to display high levels of likelihood due to its higher frequency in the spoken language. Finally, the likelihood value for 'certificate' (as in the EU Digital Covid Certificate) is a result of mentions of this Certificate in the data sample (and lack thereof in the other data samples), while 'NGOs' shows a specific heightened focus on issues related to the aid and support offered by civil society organisations at the border.

6.1.2. *European Commission and civil society*

The comparison of the European Commission and civil society³³ corpora reveal even starker divergences. See Table 5: Keyness Analysis - Commission and civil society below:

³³ For civil society, individual words that were clearly the names of specific NGOs (i.e., Amnesty, MSF, Oxfam) were excluded from the table and the following discussion. The higher statistical prominence of the names of organisations within their own statements is not a significant finding. It must be nonetheless noted that the names of other NGOs could not be removed entirely (e.g., Human Rights Watch, Save the Children, Greek Refugee Council, etc.) which may lead to the overrepresentation of specific words in the results of the quantitative analysis.

Table 5: Keyness Analysis – Commission and civil society

Commission	Likelihood	Civil society	Likelihood
We	882.918	Detention	1058.136
Our	811.72	People	760.825
Member	643.397	Human	675.19
Visa	404.62	Children	644.975
Schengen	364.351	Rights	641.109
Directive	341.616	Seekers	601.804
Commission	306.137	Libya	578.315
States	257.404	Refugees	546.655
Citizens	234.707	Greek	491.471
Cooperation	233.031	Refugee	476.173
Residence	231.781	Greece	468.526
Union	227.03	Violations	412.557
Together	202.51	Violence	404.726
Work	200.042	Libyan	375.292
Return	194.213	Sea	356.315

The top two results for the Commission in terms of statistical likelihood are ‘we’ and ‘our’. This shows a tendency for the Commission to speak both about itself and collectively in the name of the EU. ‘Member States’ and the word ‘Commission’ are also included in the main results, together with ‘cooperation’ and ‘together’. Overall, the remaining words are similar to the results examined in the previous Section 6.1.1: as with the Parliament, compared to civil society, the Commission’s main preoccupations relate to visa policy, the Schengen area (and therefore border control and internal free movement), specific legislative files (‘directive’), residence rights, ‘citizens’, ‘work’, and ‘return’. The presence of ‘citizens’ among the main results is interesting, which shows the higher centrality of the notion of citizenship in the Commission’s discourse and, consequently, the lower importance given to it by civil society in its own discourse.

The civil society actors under examination, instead, are more likely to focus on individuals and specific categories of people (‘people’, ‘refugee(s)’, ‘children’), human rights and their violations (‘detention’, ‘human’ and ‘rights’, ‘violations’, ‘violence’), as well as the geographical areas where these take place (‘Libya’ and ‘Libyan’, ‘Greece’ and ‘Greek’, and ‘sea’). Overall, it emerges that the predominant civil society discourse is more directly linked to the lived experience of TCNs, particularly those experiencing degrading treatment, while the Commission’s is more confined to a more policy- and legislation-centric discourse.

6.1.3. European Parliament and civil society

Finally, similar insights can be drawn from the keyness analysis between the European Parliament and civil society³⁴. The results are displayed in Table 6: Keyness Analysis - Parliament and civil society below:

³⁴ See previous.

Table 6: Keyness Analysis - Parliament and civil society

Parliament	Likelihood	Civil society	Likelihood
We	3313.417	Eu	1941.669
Our	1130.643	Detention	1030.229
Union	553.569	Children	767.756
Citizens	376.778	International	590.115
Commissioner	320.735	Asylum	555.718
Schengen	290.076	Resettlement	529.586
Now	288.475	Rights	448.274
Question	205.599	Seekers	443.284
European	169.087	AI	386.273
Problem	143.918	Authorities	379.891
Certificate	133.493	Migrants	362.348
Today	112.402	Refugee	361.935
Debate	110.649	Libya	350.716
Believe	104.697	Organisations	339.462
Putin	98.266	Refugees	322.294

On the Parliament side³⁵, the main two results for the Commission in terms of statistical likelihood are ‘we’ and ‘our’, which shows a higher likelihood for MEPs to speak using first-person pronouns compared civil society, that is, about themselves, collectively as an institutions and in the name of the EU. ‘Union’ and ‘European’ might indicate a higher likelihood for MEPs to focus on the EU and its institutions, as opposed to the more international focus of NGOs. As for the Commission, the presence of ‘citizens’ among the main results shows the higher centrality of the notion of citizenship in the Parliament’s discourse and, consequently, the lower importance that civil society gives to it in its own discourse.

‘Commissioner’ reflect the presence of Commission officials in selected parliamentary debates and therefore the higher likelihood for MEPs – at least based on the current data samples – to directly confront Commission officials compared to civil society. More substantive is the presence of the word ‘Schengen’, which underlines the higher preoccupation of the Parliament with border control and intra-EU free movement. It can also be assumed that ‘question’ is more statistically relevant for the Parliament than civil society because of parliamentary procedures. Similarly, ‘problem’, ‘now’, ‘today’, and ‘debate’ are part of the distinctive language used in the Parliament, with political groups engaging in debates, advancing their specific concerns and priorities, focusing on the present and/or marking the urgency of specific measures. ‘Believe’ also suggests a higher likelihood to find personal opinions and normative statements in the Parliament’s sample. Finally, MEPs seem to be more likely to speak about ‘Putin’, presumably in relation to geopolitical matters.

When it comes to civil society, a number of different topics jump out. Once again, these refer to specific categories of TCNs (‘children’, ‘asylum’, ‘seekers’, ‘migrants’, ‘refugee(s)'), human rights-related issues

³⁵ Once again, most of the initial keyness results were linked to its procedures and way of speaking (i.e., ‘president’, ‘mr’, ‘madam’, ‘colleagues’, ‘commissioner’, ‘gentlemen’ and ‘ladies’), and were therefore screened out.

(‘detention’), geographical locations (‘Libya’), resettlement and ‘authorities’. Artificial intelligence (AI) also appears as one of the key results for civil society, which is likely due to the presence of statements by data protection and AI-focused NGOs in the data sample. As noted before, this confirms the higher attention of civil society for the lived experience and fundamental rights of people, as opposed to the more institutional, policy-oriented language that characterises the Parliament.

6.2. Critical assessment

The quantitative and qualitative analysis of the three EU-level linguistic corpora for the European Commission, the European Parliament, and civil society reveals distinctive characteristics for each actor, as well as several commonalities.

The sections below will first compare the frequency of individual words and the specific weight of the semantic group for each of the three actors; and, secondly, the Report will identify the main commonalities and divergences in how each actors speaks on migration, irregularity, employment, gender, Covid-19, returns, and crisis and defence.

6.2.1. Frequency and semantic groups

The first difference lies in the high-frequency-word lists for each actor. The European Commission and Parliament use first-person pronouns more frequently (*we, our, us*) compared to civil society’s focus on third parties (*people, their, they*). This indicates a greater internal focus – both on their own actions and work as institutions, but also on Europe, its citizens, and Member States. CSOs, on the other hand, given their mission and the topic at hand, show greater attention to TCNs, their rights and lived experience, and to other third parties like national authorities, as well as on the more ‘international’ dimension – both in terms of geography and as a source of legal obligations. The Parliament seems to speak about human rights more often than the Commission does, albeit less than civil society.

Some of the terms included in the high-frequency lists (Sections 3.2.1, 4.2.1 and 5.2.1) only appear for one specific actor, showing some degree of uniqueness:

- For the Commission, the terms include *work, cooperation, state, national, third, directive, return, social, labour and measures*;
- For the Parliament, *we, president, us, human, time, right, citizens, commissioner, years, against and parliament*;
- For civil society, *children, international, refugees, detention, Greece, them, authorities, access and Greek*.

The specific weight and sequence of the semantic groups for each actor also differs. The semantic group Governance ranks first for both the European Commission and the European Parliament. For civil society, instead, the semantic group Rights occupies the first position – albeit by a minimal margin – over Governance, which comes second. This proves the overall dominance across all EU-level actors of technocratic and bureaucratic language and of legislation, policy, and procedures. Even civil society organisations, which mostly focus on Rights, are forced to operate within the same frameworks and speak the same language as the institutions to have an impact on EU policy and legislation. As Kohler-Koch and Quittkat (2013) noted, while civil society organisations are critical of EU governance, their engagement with the discourse is often constrained by the ‘official’ language and procedures. These barriers can limit

inclusivity in the civil society space, and rather than challenging the technocratic discourse and narratives set by EU institutions, may inadvertently reinforce them.

The semantic groups Rights and Subject rank respectively fourth and fifth for the Commission, third and fourth for the Parliament, and first and fourth – though with significantly higher normalised frequency – for civil society. This may suggest an EU-level tendency to speak more about policy issues and social phenomena through the lens of legislation and policy, rather than speaking directly about the people affected and involved, their rights and lived experience – with civil society being a positive outlier when it comes to Rights. Additionally, as noted for the Commission’s proto-narratives, the official institutional discourse does not always contain narratives (i.e., a subject, action verb, setting, or means). Instead, it is more descriptive, passive, or centred around the Commission’s actions, legal and policy instruments, their purpose, functioning and implementation, and combined with normative (‘must’/‘have to’/‘need’ statements) and future-oriented language. Given the nature and goal of the statements, this is less prominent in the Parliament and civil society corpora, where more distinct narratives (people or things doing things) can be identified in the broader discourse.

The semantic group Borders and Migration is significantly more prominent for the European Commission than for the other two actors – particularly as regards the Status subgroup. This indicates the Commission’s a higher degree of preoccupation with the specific immigration and residence status of TCNs compared to the Parliament and civil society. For the Commission, the dominant focus is on borders and migration control, with significant attention paid to governance instruments and structures. On this subject, it is important to highlight that, within the Parliament, right-wing and far-right political groups tend to define (im)migration as ‘illegal’, which is not included in Borders and Migration but in the Crime and Policing semantic group. On the other hand, more progressive political groups and civil society are more likely to not specify the specific status of a person or refer as often to (ir)regularity, which means that they resort to using the Border and Migration terms to a lesser extent and less frequently than the Commission. The preference for terms other than ‘irregular’, or the silence around this topic, contributes to the lower overall normalised frequency of the Borders and Migration semantic group for the Parliament and civil society.

The Work and Economy semantic group ranks higher (sixth out of 13) for the Commission than the other two. It is especially low for Parliament (ten out of 13), with only one third of the normalised frequency of the Commission. Civil society falls in between the two in terms of frequency (eight out of 13). Welfare and services, instead, ranks sixth out of 13 for both the Parliament and civil society, and seventh for the Commission. However, the Commission and civil society show a similar frequency value – which is higher than the one displayed by the Parliament.

The semantic groups with the lowest frequency across the different actors are: Obligations, which includes ‘integration’ and other non-rights-related duties and ranks twelfth out of 13 for both institutions and last for civil society; IOs and NGOs, which ranks last for the institutions but is significantly more prominent for civil society (seventh out of 13); and Returns and expulsion, which ranks eleventh for both EU institutions and twelfth for civil society. This last aspect is particularly surprising given that ‘return’ is one of the most frequent and statistically likely terms for the Commission. This might be explained by the fact that, excluding ‘return’ itself, the words included in the Return and expulsion semantic group are few and do not appear frequently. Yet ‘return’ alone remains highly frequent and significant.

6.2.2. *Thematic analysis*

Migration, irregularity, and refugees

Across all three corpora, ‘migration’ and ‘irregularity’ are mainly discussed in relation to the external borders and their crossing. Issues related to TCNs residing within EU territory without a regular immigration or residence status come up only in a more limited manner, and mostly in the civil society corpus in relation to employment.

The collocation analysis demonstrates that different categories of TCNs are associated with distinct linguistic patterns. For example, when looking at “migra*” terms, which encompass (im)migration and (im)migrant(s) among others, the Commission overwhelmingly uses terms from the Borders and Migration and Governance semantic groups, followed by Rights and Policing and Crime with similar likelihood values. In the data sample for the Parliament, language related to Governance and Policing and Crime dominate, followed by Borders and Migration and – much less prominently – Rights. For CSOs, instead, (im)migration and (im)migrant(s) mostly correlate with Rights, followed by Governance, Borders and Migration, and IOs and NGOs.

When it comes to ‘irregular’, the ensemble of the Commission’s statements overwhelmingly uses terms tied to Borders and Migration as well, but followed distantly by Crisis and Defence, Policing and Crime, and Governance – with the other semantic groups virtually absent. Given the more limited use of the term ‘irregular’ (111 times for the Parliament and 70 times for CSOs), the situation is different for the other two actors, both of whom associate ‘irregular’ with Borders and Migration. Within the Parliament, ‘illegal’ is also mainly tied to Borders and Migration – followed distantly by Rights (e.g., ‘illegal pushbacks’ included in the Violations subgroup), and Crisis and Defence.

The collocation analysis of ‘refugee(s)’ reveals further differentiation. For the Commission, ‘refugee’ most commonly co-occurs with terms related to Time and Space, and (only less), with Borders and Migration, Welfare and Services, and Governance. The European Parliament also places emphasis on Time and Space, followed by Rights, Numbers and Quantities, Borders and Migration, and Crisis and Defence. The collocation results for CSOs, by contrast, highlight the intersection of ‘refugee’ with Border and Migration (e.g., migrants and refugees), IOs and NGOs, Rights, Time and Space, and Welfare and Services.

Across all three actors, one can notice that the likelihood of finding terms related to Welfare and Services significantly grows in the discussions surrounding refugees, compared to those on migration or irregularity. So does the likelihood of Rights-related terms in the European Commission and European Parliament’s corpora. Inversely, in migration- or irregularity-related discussions, the prominence of Borders and Migration (mainly ideas related to ‘managing’, ‘flows’, etc.), Policing and Crime, and Crisis and Defence significantly increases compared to discussions around refugees.

Table 7: Semantic group comparison (*migra*, irregular and refugee*)

Concept	Commission	Likelihood	Parliament	Likelihood	Civil society	Likelihood
migra	Borders and migration	4605.330	Governance	1899.260	Rights	641.425
	Governance	3581.062	Policing and crime	1800.640	Governance	633.022
	Rights	1952.804	Borders and migration	1637.920	Borders and migration	589.311
	Policing and crime	1609.957	Rights	902.223	IOs and NGOs	449.232
	Crisis and defence	877.014	Crisis and defence	555.461	Subject	115.187
	Subject	395.996	Numbers and quantities	529.859	Work and economy	114.184
	Time and space	190.68	Work and economy	299.922	Time and space	96.746
Irregular	Borders and migration	4049.913	Borders and migration	519.207	Borders and migration	221.357
	Crisis and defence	466.173	Numbers and quantities	20.971	Policing and crime	56.770
	Policing and crime	243.150	Governance	15.875	Crisis and defence	18.599
	Governance	206.386	Crisis and defence	14.070	-----	-----
	Work and economy	124.421	-----	-----	-----	-----
	Numbers and quantities	108.166	-----	-----	-----	-----
Refugee(s)	Time and Space	1249.037	Time and space	732.807	Borders and migration	593.091
	Borders and migration	617.489	Rights	515.564	IOs and NGOs	554.608
	Welfare and services	546.192	Numbers and quantities	395.997	Time and space	467.976
	Governance	507.834	Borders and migration	237.026	Rights	513.826
	Numbers and quantities	342.867	Crisis and defence	128.958	Welfare and services	223.586
	Rights	286.319	Welfare and services	161.410	Governance	106.508

In addition to the different weight of semantic groups, specific places or nationalities are more likely to be associated with different statuses. For migrants, the quantitative analysis shows a correlation with ‘Venezuelan’ and ‘UK’ – with the latter mainly coming up with regard to post-Brexit cooperation on migration management. Nationalities such as ‘Syrian’, again ‘Venezuelan’, and ‘Ukrainian’ are frequently mentioned by the European Commission when it comes to refugees. Turkey is also mentioned but as a key third country partner for the containment of Syrian refugees. In the data sample for the European Parliament, the main geographical collocation for (im)migration and (im)migrants is ‘Africa’. For refugees, instead, it also shows a specific focus on Ukrainian refugees, with right-wing political groups explicitly contrasting female and minor Ukrainian refugees to male refugees of African and Arab descent (see

section on Gender below). For civil society, (im)migration and (im)migrants only correlate with locations like Libya, Greece, and the Balkans, which reflect some of the main areas under scrutiny for human rights concerns and violations. Syrian and Ukrainian are instead the most commonly mentioned nationalities for refugees.

The qualitative analysis on migration and irregularity confirms most of the findings above. Overall, the VDL I European Commission mostly looked at ‘migration’ through the lens of geopolitics and defence, and its discourse surrounding irregularity was securitarian, focused on *reducing, countering* and *fighting* unauthorised border crossings, and the need for preventative measures. The statements analysed for the Commission clearly show an emphasis on fighting against smugglers and traffickers and the need for regular migration pathways. Considering the overall lack of existing regular pathways, this may suggest an inherent contradiction between the Commission’s discourse and the reality of current EU policies. There is also the expectation that TCNs must adapt to European values, particularly as regards gender equality, peaceful coexistence, religious freedom, and tolerance. These statements reveal the presumption that TCNs do not or cannot respect these ‘values’, while EU institutions, governments, and societies in the Union do. There is also disregard for issues such as institutionalised discrimination, racism, and xenophobia, which might act as obstacles for the integration and inclusion of TCNs in the EU.

The 2019–2024 European Parliament shows significantly different narratives. Moderate and conservative political groups emphasised the need for ‘effective’ border control, link – more or less explicitly – migration to illegal activities, and portrayed returns as the only desirable policy option to ‘solve the issue’. Among progressive political groups, there was more criticism against current EU policies, particularly as regards their contrast with non-derogable fundamental rights and EU values. The far right, instead, often described migration as ‘illegal’, tying it with crime, violence, and xenophobic ideas on ethnic or cultural replacement, and extending their hostility to NGOs who are seen as ‘smugglers’.

Civil society was mainly concerned with how current EU and national migration and asylum policies erode international and EU law, human rights standards, and EU values. They emphasised – often in more moral/humanitarian terms rather than with direct reference to the law – the legal imperative to provide assistance to all people in distress, regardless of their status, the ongoing criminalisation of assistance by civil society, and the complicity of the EU and its Member States in exposing people to unnecessary danger, violence, and human rights violations.

Furthermore, the keyness analysis performed for the Commission and Parliament showed that these institutions are not monolithic when it comes to their discourse. Specific differences can be observed in the way individual officials or political groups speak about migration and irregularity. Within the Commission, President VDL, VP Schinas, and Commissioner Johansson’s discourses displayed distinctive characteristics that differentiated one from the other. VDL displayed a stronger focus on geopolitical issues and the role of the EU in the world (partially due to her scope of work being broader and thus migration and mobility-related words being less statistically significant), Schinas’s discourse appears to be more focused on legal and policy frameworks, border controls, and ‘legal’ (or better, regular) pathways for labour migration. Johansson, instead, showed a more ‘humanitarian’ and rights-based approach, often highlighting that migration is normal and natural, but was still focused on border controls and cross-border movement, as well as measures against smugglers and traffickers. Previous research has however noted that this type of humanitarian discourse may act as another securitising device: behind the emphasis on ‘saving lives’ or keeping people alive and safe, there may be no explicit mention or

commitment to legal obligation and protection but, rather, a further attempt at curtailing the only available (unsafe) mobility pathways ('rescue-without-protection'; Moreno-Lax, 2017; see also Pallister-Wilkins, 2022; Walters, 2011).

As expected, the Parliament shows even more fragmentation in its discourse. Overall, the three main political groups in the 2019-2024 VDL I majority, i.e., EPP, S&D and Renew, show a more policy and legislation-oriented language. Their ideological leanings are still discernible: the EPP emphasised border control and security concerns; S&D integration, solidarity, rights, and humanitarian concerns; and Renew mutual trust and cooperation. On the other hand, the political groups who were not part of the ruling coalition display more emotional and confrontational language: the Left focused on social justice, mobility rights and strongly criticised current policies for their racism and fundamental rights violations; the Greens on the fundamental rights of migrants, asylum seekers, and refugees, and human rights obligations; ECR on migration as a threat to national sovereignty and its alleged links with crime; and ID on anti-immigration and xenophobic sentiments, opposition to multiculturalism, crime, and national sovereignty.

Employment

Across the three corpora, the correlations between Borders and Migration and Employment and Economy are rather limited. When looking at the correlations for the “migrat*” terms and for employment-related words, the sum likelihood for the other category is low across all three actors. This suggests that, within the data sample, there are constricted theme-specific bubbles: a discussion on migration and migrants will mainly talk about borders, possibly governance, rights, and crisis and defence, or policing and crime but rarely about employment, labour rights, and welfare and services. On the other hand, a discussion about employment will mainly encompass employment-related terms, welfare and services, and governance, but rarely migration and migrants. The only exception to this rule appears to be employment-related statements by civil society, which show high collocation values with Borders and Migration.

When it comes to employment-specific findings, for both the Commission and the Parliament, ‘talent’, ‘skilled’, ‘skills’, and ‘shortages’ are highly prominent terms. This confirms a higher degree of attention on ‘highly-skilled’ workers, with TCNs seen as a way to fill in existing gaps in the EU labour force. This is in stark contradiction with civil society’s focus on particular sectors, i.e., sex work, seasonal work, agriculture, domestic work, and platform work, and its stronger concern with labour exploitation. One of the main focuses for the Commission in relation to employment is the Employers Sanctions Directive – i.e., criminal sanctions for European employers hiring irregularised TCNs – but not so much on the rights of the affected irregularised TCNs. Additionally, it is significant that the highest-ranking result for the Commission in Borders and Migration is ‘mobility’: at the EU level, this term is reserved for speaking about the intra-EU mobility of EU citizens – and not TCNs.

The qualitative analysis shows that, for the Commission, the link between migration and employment was mainly limited to ‘illegal’ employment, exploitation and criminal activities, with a less prominent concern for possible precarious conditions, vulnerability, and rights violations faced by TCNs in these situations. The exclusive focus on ‘talent’ and ‘skills’, and the consequent sidelining of more blue-collar occupations, was particularly evident in the statements analysed. The only exception was a statement by VP Schinas, which expressly stated that ‘legal’ migration is not only about highly-skilled workers. This is however contradictory when one considers the reality of current regular labour migration policies and the personal scope of existing legal instruments, such as the Employers Sanctions Directive and the Platform Workers Directive.

When it comes to the Parliament, once again, very different narratives emerged based on the specific political group under examination. The statement from the EPP appeared cautious about labour migration; it was in support only where it would not create competition with European citizens for jobs and stressed that labour migration should remain under national control with coordination by the EU to avoid the possibility of TCNs' taking advantage of loopholes. The S&D statement valued the contribution of migrants, advocated for labour migration to address skill shortages across sectors and criticised the exploitation of migrant workers. It called for better working conditions, anti-discrimination laws, and a stronger EU role in migration policy. The MEP from the Left advocated for labour migration opportunities for all skill levels, not just highly-skilled workers, supported rights for asylum seekers and undocumented workers, and placed emphasis on human dignity, equity, and the protection of vulnerable groups. Finally, statements from ECR viewed low- and medium-skilled migration as way of 'legalising illegal immigration' and as a source of security threats, and called for more stringent EU border policy, including physical barriers.

Finally, civil society actors – which also includes social partners – placed emphasis on preventing exploitation, supporting regularisation, and access to rights for all migrants, irrespective of migration status. All statements are critical of current EU migration policies and the prioritisation of border security over labour protection. These policies, in their opinion, do not address the real concerns of both migrant and local workers. Civil society is particularly concerned with migrant workers in essential sectors such as agriculture and hospitality, their frequent exploitation and the constant risk of deportation, which hinders reports of abuse. There is also attention paid to the household level of migrant workers, and specifically the rights and living conditions of children, who suffer from lack of basic rights. All of these civil society statements shift the focus from the borders to the actual living and working conditions of irregularised TCNs within the EU territory, the lack of effective protections afforded by Member States and the EU to irregularised workers and their systemic exposure to discrimination, exploitation, and intimidation.

Gender

Another key comparative finding relates to gender and household-related dynamics in the three corpora. For both the Commission and the Parliament, terms connected to femininity are far more common than those related to masculinity in the respective corpora. For the Commission, women are mentioned four times as often as men; for the Parliament, three times as often. Children, on the other hand, are mentioned 14 times more often than men and almost four times more than women for the Commission, and more than five times more than men and almost twice as often as women for the Parliament. This is not the case for civil society actors where the two genders appear with comparable frequency; although children appear almost four times as often as men and women in this corpus too – which is partly due to 'Save the Children' being a recurrent presence in the joint statements.

When it comes to collocations, for both the Commission and the Parliament, women often appear in discussions related to victimhood, vulnerability, exploitation, and violence, while children are more likely to be referred to in connection with protection, education, welfare, and inclusion. Civil society displays some of the same tendencies, but to a lesser extent: women and children often come up in the same statements as men ('men, women, and children') and are associated with characteristics other than 'victim' or 'vulnerable'. Overall, men display less collocation results and are often labelled as 'young' by all three actors. In the civil society corpus, 'men' also appear as perpetrators of violence (either as agents of the State or as non-state actors) against TCNs within Europe, at the external borders or in third countries.

The overall predominance of women and children in the discourse does not indicate that irregularised migration is gendered feminine or overwhelmingly linked to children and minors. Rather, there appears an overall silence surrounding masculinity, with the gender spelt out explicitly only for women. This suggests that the characteristics typically linked to the term ‘migrant’ in the rest of the data sample should be assumed to apply to men. In other words, unless specifically identified as ‘female’ or ‘woman’, a ‘migrant’ is more readily viewed as a subject of control – tied to policing, crime, and concepts of crisis and defence – rather than as a ‘victim’ or someone in need of protection due to gender-specific vulnerabilities (see Hyndman & Giles, 2011; Turner, 2019; Sachseder et al., 2024)³⁶. This pattern suggests that the general institutional discourse sidelines non-gender- and non-age-specific needs which affect categories other than women and children and might still warrant international protection, subsidiary protection, or humanitarian residence permits, such as physical or mental health, sexuality and gender identity (LGBTIQ+ people), etc.. At the same time, it reproduces the notion of ‘*womenandchildren*’ (Enloe, 1993) as inherently passive victims or exemplary models of vulnerability.

The qualitative analysis also showed the European Commission mainly focused on the specific vulnerabilities of women and girls, particularly in the context of human trafficking, where they are predominantly affected by sexual exploitation. This portrayal was vividly framed by the Commission as young, vulnerable girls falling victim to manipulative traffickers who exploit their insecurities. Beyond trafficking, migrant women were highlighted as facing significant employment challenges, such as part-time, low-wage, insecure jobs that do not match their qualifications. The Commission’s broader narrative extended to children and calls for gender-sensitive support in EU victim and anti-trafficking strategies.

In the Parliament, instead, right-wing political groups highlighted the difference between Ukrainian refugees (largely women, children, and other ‘vulnerable’ groups) and male refugees from African and Arab countries. They portrayed Ukrainians as ‘real’ refugees deserving of protection and support and framed male refugees from other regions as a threat, sources of criminality, and as unworthy of protection. This rhetoric shows racial and xenophobic undertones, and gender was used to delegitimise non-European male refugees. Left-leaning political groups also emphasised the particular vulnerabilities of women, children, and LGBTIQ persons but often adopted a more universal framing, acknowledging that violence, exploitation, and death affect all migrants – men, women, and children.

Civil society also tended to highlight the vulnerability of women and children, including pregnant women, their babies and unaccompanied minors, calling for tailored reception and protection measures based on gender and age. However, civil society actors also addressed the experiences of men in these contexts. They emphasised that physical and psychological abuse, violence and human rights violations are experienced by ‘men, women and children’ or ‘children, women, and men’ throughout their journeys. This perspective broadens the understanding of protection in migration contexts, acknowledging gender- and age-specific needs but also not reducing ‘vulnerability’ to only these two categories.

Covid-19

³⁶ In a stakeholder meeting held in the context of the I-CLAIM project, a representative from ENAR noted that their previous research on this topic revealed that, in some countries, the association of femininity/womanhood with vulnerability is only valid as long as the women in question do not wear headscarves. In that case, they are also associated to notions of danger and insecurity.

Given the timeframe selected for the statements analysed in this Report, Covid-19 was selected as one of the key themes to explore. While it did not come up as prominently as expected in the quantitative analysis, the qualitative analysis of selected statements on this topic revealed significant insights on how the three actors did or did not speak about the impacts of the pandemic on irregularised TCNs.

The Commission's statements – particularly by Commissioner Johansson – emphasised the contribution of migrants to European society and economy and their higher exposure to the pandemic's health risks. These statements were however limited to TCNs with regular migration and residence status, with an overall silence surrounding irregularised TCN workers and their rights and wellbeing.

In the Parliament, instead, two opposing narratives surrounding irregularised TCNs and the pandemic were observed. On the one hand, right-wing political groups tied the arrival of TCNs to increased health risks, framing immigration as a public health threat and criticising the 'too lax' approach on new arrivals. In contrast, left-leaning political groups emphasised that Covid-19 affected people regardless of nationality or immigration status. In this context, primary concerns related to the need to safeguard asylum seekers' rights, expanding regular pathways and humanitarian visas, and the pretextual use by Member States of Covid-19 as a justification for restricting access to asylum.

Civil society seemed to be aligned with this second narrative. The statements included in the sample drew attention to how the pandemic amplified the inequalities affecting already marginalised groups, including irregularised migrants, and argued that the public policy efforts mainly benefitted already privileged groups. The pandemic and its effects were therefore portrayed as a broader issue of discrimination, racism, and social injustice. As regards the external borders, civil society actors emphasised that the emergency measures should not excuse countries from their legal responsibilities vis-à-vis asylum seekers, for example in the case of search and rescue in the Mediterranean.

Return

Return is also a highly relevant topic for all three actors. Despite not featuring as a semantic group as frequently as expected in the three corpora (both in terms of general frequency and in correlation with other words and concepts), 'return' as an individual term remains one of the terms with the highest frequency for the Commission. It is presented as one of – if not the main – solution to irregularised migration and, as such, the narratives adopted by the Commission, Parliament, and civil society actors on this topic are extremely relevant for the current analysis.

According to the Commission statements, ensuring returns is key to maintaining the credibility and sustainability of EU migration policy and to ensure legitimacy for the EU's migration framework. However, this focus disregards the significant practical challenges in implementing returns, such as legal, logistical, and diplomatic obstacles, as well as the fact that most irregular migrants are not actually returnable. The prioritisation of return as the preferred response to irregular migration consequently sidelines discussions on the rights, living conditions, and work situations of TCNs who are already present in the EU.

The discourse in the Parliament was extremely polarised on the matter of returns too. While centrist MEPs advocated for agreements with third countries to combat irregular migration by increasing returns, far-right MEPs called for outsourcing asylum and for an immediate entry ban for all TCNs, whom they see as culturally alien and 'unqualified'. Conversely, more left-leaning narratives appeared critical of the Commission and Council's exclusive focus on deportations, arguing that effective returns require peace

and inclusivity. They advocated for respecting cultural and religious diversity, positioning it as a valuable part of European society rather than a threat.

Civil society critiqued the EU's approach to returns and deportations, emphasising the injustice and fundamental rights violations faced by migrants. They argued that deportations should be a last resort but are currently being increasingly prioritised regardless of their fundamental rights impacts. Issues of social justice and racial equality were raised to argue for a re-evaluation of the EU's approach on migration policies. Concerns were also raised about Frontex's overreach and lack of accountability, especially regarding its self-monitoring of deportation operations. Similar criticisms emerged in discussions about the 2022-2024 revision of the Schengen Borders Code, with criticisms on the Commission's proposals for new bilateral agreements and intra-EU transfer procedures. These initiatives were seen as undermining critical protections for TCNs, such as their right to asylum and the principle of non-refoulement. The statement warned of the risks of chain-refoulement and collective expulsions, emphasising the need to adhere to established legal safeguards to protect fundamental rights under EU law and regional human rights instruments.

Crisis and defence

When it comes to crisis and defence, the three actors also show diverging narratives. The Commission's discourse reveals a strong geopolitical focus and a framing of migration as a foreign policy issue. This is particularly – but not only – evident in relation to specific countries like Belarus and Turkey. President von der Leyen framed the cross-border movement of people from Belarus into the EU as a 'hybrid attack' performed by the Belarusian government. This narrative acknowledges the affected migrants as victims but primarily focuses on protecting EU borders from perceived threats. It portrays people on the move as pawns in a political game, adopting defence-like language ('shield', 'instrumentalisation', 'attack', 'threats', and 'crisis') and sidelining the EU's legal obligations to assist and protect those arriving at its borders (see Carrera et al., 2023).

In the same contexts, Commissioner Johansson adopted a less security-dominated and more rights-oriented tone, asserting that migration itself is not a threat but something that should be managed positively. She emphasised the need to welcome migrants through regular pathways while also stressing the need to prevent new unauthorised arrivals. Johansson's crisis narrative was more focused on the TCNs affected: there is no migration crisis, but some of the migrants are in crisis. She expressed support for a humanitarian approach and emphasised the need to avoid people from falling victims of smugglers and traffickers. Previous research has however noted that this type of discourse as another securitising device ('rescue-without-protection'; Moreno-Lax, 2017). The overarching narrative – supported by Commission-wide official statements – remained focused on border protection and control, often depicting migrants as security risks or tools in geopolitical struggles, or, when acknowledged as victims, as lives to be saved but not necessarily as rights-holders.

Crisis and defence language is significant for the Parliament and, particularly, in relation to the events at the borders of Latvia, Lithuania, and Poland with Belarus in 2022-2023. Centre-right political groups framed unauthorised crossings from Belarus as an 'instrument of hybrid warfare' and irregularised migration as a deliberate tactic by the Belarusian and Russian regimes to destabilise the EU. This perspective views the movement of people as a security threat, comparing it to a 'genocide' and calling for increased EU funding to support border states. 'Security' was described as having precedence over all else

– including over the EU being consistent with itself (i.e., with its founding values). In stark contrast, left-wing political actors described that TCNs at the border are treated as ‘real waste’. They condemned the support for the Polish far-right’s repressive actions, including family separations, and accused EU leaders of adopting far-right rhetoric and ‘necropolitics’. Instead of militarised responses, they advocated for humanitarian aid and regularised pathways for TCNs and the provision of aid and support at the border.

Civil society was also vocal in its opposition to military responses at the border and the framing of human mobility in crisis and defence terms. Their narratives mostly focused on the suffering at the borders, arguing that people should not be seen as security threats and that Member States should uphold their legal obligations in such situations. The EU’s militaristic approach was said to undermine fundamental rights, empower authoritarian regimes and incorrectly prioritise physical barriers over human rights. Civil society also raised concerns regarding the overall shift in the narrative surrounding migration and the increasing polarised discourse in Europe on this topic.

7. Concluding remarks

The comparative analysis reveals a nuanced landscape within EU migration discourse, where recurring themes of border control, migration and residence status, and rights and employment are interpreted through divergent lenses.

The actors analysed are by no means unitary actors. Several observations can nonetheless be made based on the statistical relevance of specific trends and relationships between individual words and concepts. Overall, for the European Commission and the European Parliament, ‘migration’ was mainly understood as a phenomenon to be managed through legislation and policy, particularly in the area of border control, security, crime and defence. While also heavily relying on the EU policy and legislation-heavy language due to their field of action, civil society was the only actor that prioritised a rights-based approach to cross-border human mobility and was mostly concerned with human rights and humanitarian issues and the lived experiences of TCNs regardless of status.

The European Commission – particularly President von der Leyen and VP Schinas – largely looked at ‘migration’ through the lens of geopolitics and defence, often in a competing relationship with ‘our values’. Its discourse surrounding irregularity was focused on *reducing, countering, and fighting* against unauthorised border crossings, the need for preventative measures, and alleged links with criminality. The Parliament was extremely polarised, with far-right political groups emphasising discussions related to policing and crime, and crisis and defence, the more moderate political groups prioritising border controls and questions of EU governance, and progressive MEPs focusing on questions of rights, social justice, and discrimination. Civil society employed a rights-based approach which emphasises dignity and protection for all TCNs regardless of their status and advocated for a more inclusive migration policy.

As examined in this Report, these differences are identified across different dimensions. First, different connotations apply to different categories of TCNs, with the term ‘irregular’ associated more with notions of border management, policing and crime, and crisis and defence, while ‘refugee(s)’ more likely to be associated to rights and welfare and wellbeing. This simplistic duality was nonetheless opposed by progressive MEPs and civil society actors calling for respecting the EU and Member States’ legal obligations and the fundamental rights of all TCNs *irrespective of their immigration status*.

Secondly, when it comes to employment, an overwhelming separation between (irregularised) migration- and employment-related discussions was observed. While labour migration was more present in the narratives examined in the qualitative analysis, the rights, wellbeing, and living and working conditions of irregularised migrant workers in Europe were virtually absent from institutional statements, with the exception of left-of-centre political groups in the MEPs. Civil society, which included social partners, instead clearly emphasised the entitlement to social rights and decent working conditions for all workers, without discrimination based on immigration status. It also highlighted the systemic vulnerability of irregularised migrants to labour exploitation, the obstacles they face to report violations of their rights, and their constantly being under threat of being reported to the authorities and facing deportation.

With respect to differences the line of gendered norms and perceptions, the Commission and the Parliament mostly focused on women and children as ‘vulnerable’ subjects or ‘victims’. While the recognition of gender- and age-specific special needs is positive, this was accompanied by an implicit or – in the case of far-right EP political groups – explicit assumption that ‘young men’ are not real refugees and do not deserve protection and specific protection reception/procedural needs and rights. Additionally, the silence surrounding masculinity and the differential treatment noticed in the discourses on femininity and childhood indicate that, when ‘women’ or ‘children’ are not mentioned, a ‘migrant’ should be seen as a subject of control – tied to policing, crime, and concepts of crisis and defence, and not as a ‘victim’ or someone in need of or deserving protection. Non-gender- and non-age-specific needs (e.g., physical and mental health, sexuality, gender identity) which affect categories other than women and children and might still warrant asylum, subsidiary protection, or humanitarian residence permits, but are virtually absent from this narrative. Civil society, instead, acknowledged gender and age-specific needs in migratory contexts, but focused on people’s lived experience and journeys, not limiting the notion of vulnerability to specific gender categories.

The analysis of Covid-19’s impact on irregularised TCNs revealed contrasting narratives among the European Commission, Parliament, and civil society actors. The Commission, through Commissioner Johansson, highlighted migrants’ contributions to Europe and their vulnerability to health risks, but primarily focused on regular TCNs, leaving irregularised migrants largely unaddressed. In Parliament, right-wing groups linked immigration to health risks, while left-leaning groups argued that Covid-19 affected everyone equally, regardless of status, and criticised the use of the pandemic as a pretext for limiting asylum access. Civil society echoed this criticism, emphasising how the pandemic deepened inequalities for marginalised groups and framed it as an issue of social justice, racism, and discrimination.

Regarding ‘returns’, the Commission portrayed these as crucial for maintaining the credibility of EU migration policy, despite practical challenges such as legal and logistical obstacles. The Parliament displayed stark polarisation, with moderate and far-right MEPs favouring stricter returns policies and outsourcing asylum processes, while progressive groups stressed the importance of fundamental rights, inclusivity and cultural diversity. Civil society strongly criticised the prioritisation of deportations, calling for migration policies that respect fundamental rights and social justice.

In the realm of crisis and defence, the Commission’s discourse, especially under President von der Leyen, framed migration as a foreign policy issue, portraying the movement of people, particularly from Belarus and Turkey, as a geopolitical threat or ‘hybrid attack’. This narrative emphasised border protection and control, often sidelining legal obligations to assist migrants. Commissioner Johansson, instead, adopted a more humanitarian tone, advocating for regular migration pathways. The main Commission narrative

remained focused on border protection and control and depicted migrants as security risks or tools in geopolitical struggles. The Parliament was even more divided, with right-of-centre groups describing unauthorised crossings as a tactic by Belarus and Russia to destabilise the EU, while progressive actors condemned militarised responses and advocate for humanitarian aid and regular pathways. Civil society also criticised the militaristic framing of migration, calling for a focus on human rights and opposing the portrayal of people on the move as security risks.

An alternative narrative that emerged is that of migrants as workers and rights-holders. This was primarily voiced by more progressive political groups and civil society organisations, particularly within labour rights contexts. This perspective recognises migrants' heightened systemic vulnerability to exploitation and fundamental rights violations. However, rather than framing them solely as 'victims' or only celebrating their contributions as economic units to the host country, it gives priority to protection, access to rights under international labour, human rights and anti-discrimination standards as legal entitlements. In other words, it shifts the narrative from purely migration-related terms to broader questions of justice, equality and decent living and working conditions, framing the people in questions not only as 'migrants' but as human beings and workers.

List of references

- Boswell, C. (2008). The Political Functions of Expert Knowledge: Knowledge and Legitimation in European Union Immigration Policy, *Journal of European Public Policy*, 15(4), pp. 471-488.
- Carrera, S. (2009). *In search of the perfect citizen? The intersection between integration, immigration, and nationality in the EU*. Martinus Nijhoff Publishers.
- Carrera, S., Colombi, D., Campesi, G., Gori, M., Bianchini, D., Lorenter, R. J., Risoli, M. C., Barbero, I., Bezlov, T., Bieksa, L., Geraki Trimi, A., Gorczynska, M., Karageorgiou, E., Rusev, A., Salte, I., & Szuleka, M. (2023). Proposal for a regulation addressing situations of instrumentalisation in the field of migration and asylum: Substitute impact assessment. European Parliament. Directorate General for Parliamentary Research Services.
- Carrera, S., & Colombi, D. (2024). *Irregularising Human Mobility: EU Migration Policies and the European Commission's Role*. SpringerBriefs in Law. <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-031-74021-3>
- Carrera, S., Hernanz, N., & Parkin, J. (2013). *The 'Lisbonisation' of the European Parliament. Assessing Progress, Shortcomings and Challenges for Democratic Accountability in the Area of Freedom, Security and Justice*. [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/etudes/join/2013/493012/IPOL-LIBE_ET\(2013\)493012_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/etudes/join/2013/493012/IPOL-LIBE_ET(2013)493012_EN.pdf)
- Colombi, D., Näre, L., Palumbo, L., Merikoski, P., & Marchetti, S. (2024). *Irregularised Migration in Europe*. Policy Brief. I-CLAIM. <https://i-claim.eu/project/irregularised-migration-in-europe/>
- de la Baume, M. (2019, October 4). MEPs approve Schinas despite 'protecting European way of life' controversy. *POLITICO Europe*. <https://www.politico.eu/article/meps-approve-margaritis-schinas-despite-protecting-european-way-of-life-controversy-european-commission/>
- Enloe, C. (2014 [1993]). *Bananas, Beaches and Bases: Making Feminist Sense of International Politics* (2nd ed.). University of California Press. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/10.1525/j.ctt6wqbn6>
- Euronews. (2022, October 16). UN 'distressed' after Greece finds scores of 'naked and bruised' migrants on Turkish border. <https://www.euronews.com/2022/10/16/greece-says-it-found-scores-of-naked-and-bruised-migrants-on-its-border-with-turkey>
- European Commission. (2019a). Mission letter from Ursula von der Leyen, President of the European Commission, to Margaritis Schinas, Vice-President for Promoting our European Way of Life. https://commissioners.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-11/president_von_der_leyens_mission_letter_to_margaritis_schinas.pdf
- European Commission. (2019b). Mission letter from Ursula von der Leyen, President of the European Commission, to Ylva Johansson, Commissioner for Home Affairs. https://commissioners.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-11/mission-letter-ylva-johansson_en.pdf
- European Commission. (2020, November 24). *Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions*. Action

plan on Integration and Inclusion 2021-2027 {SWD(2020) 290 final}. COM(2020) 758 final. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0758>

European Commission. (2021, September 29). *Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. A renewed EU action plan against migrant smuggling (2021-2025)*. COM(2021) 591 final. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52021DC0591>

European Commission. (2024). *Pact on Migration and Asylum. A common EU system to manage migration*. https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/migration-and-asylum/pact-migration-and-asylum_en

Fassin, D. (2012). *Humanitarian Reason: A Moral History of the Present* (1st ed.). University of California Press. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/10.1525/j.ctt1pptomk>

Gonzales, R. G., Sigona, N., Franco, M. C., & Papoutsi, A. (2019). *Undocumented Migration*. Polity Press.

Hyndman, J., & Giles, W. (2011). Waiting for what? The feminization of asylum in protracted situations. *Gender, Place & Culture*, 18(3), 361–379. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0966369X.2011.566347>

Human Rights Watch (HRW). (2020, March 17). *Greece: Violence Against Asylum Seekers at Border. Detained, Assaulted, Stripped, Summarily Deported*. <https://www.hrw.org/news/2020/03/17/greece-violence-against-asylum-seekers-border>

I-CLAIM. (2023). *The project*. <https://i-claim.eu/about/>

Kelemen, R.D. & Pavone, T. (2022), 'Where Have the Guardians Gone? Law Enforcement and the Politics of Supranational Forbearance in the European Union', Working Paper, SSRN.

Kofman, E., Phizacklea, A., Raghuram, P., & Sales, R. (2005). *Gender and International Migration in Europe: Employment, Welfare and Politics* (0 ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203976265>

Moreno-Lax, V. (2018). The EU Humanitarian Border and the Securitization of Human Rights: The 'Rescue-Through-Interdiction/Rescue-Without-Protection' Paradigm. *JCMS: Journal of Common Market Studies*, 56(1), 119–140. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcms.12651>

Näre, L., Palumbo, L., Merikoski, P., & Marchetti, S. (2024). *The Legal and Policy Infrastructure of Migrant Irregularity. Comparative Report*. I-CLAIM. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.12564073>

OECD (2020). *What is the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on immigrants and their children? OECD Policy Responses to Coronavirus (COVID-19)*. https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/what-is-the-impact-of-the-covid-19-pandemic-on-immigrants-and-their-children_e7cbb7de-en.html

Pallister-Wilkins, P. (2022). *Humanitarian Borders: Unequal Mobility and Saving Lives*. London: Verso.

Pech, L. & Bárd, P. (2022), 'The Commission's Rule of Law Report and the EU Monitoring and Enforcement of Article 2 TEU Values', Study for the European Parliament's LIBE and AFCO Committees PE 727.551, Brussels, European Parliament.

- PICUM. (2017). *Why “Undocumented” or “Irregular”?* https://picum.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/Words_Matter_Terminology_FINAL_March2017.pdf
- PICUM. (2022, July 18). *Migrant smuggling: Why we need a paradigm shift*. PICUM. <https://picum.org/blog/migrant-smuggling-why-we-need-a-paradigm-shift/>
- PICUM. (2024). *PICUM's inputs to the European Commission consultation on the Facilitation Directive*. <https://picum.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/PICUMs-inputs-to-the-European-Commission-consultation-on-the-Facilitation-Directive.pdf>
- Rehindorf, M. & B. Vollmer (2025). Methodological Note: Corpus-based discourse analysis of migration-related discourses in media, politics and civil society. <https://i-claim.eu/project/methodological-note-corpus-based-discourse-analysis-of-migration-related-discourses-in-media-politics-and-civil-society/>
- Ripoll Servent, A. (2012). Playing the Co-Decision Game? Rules' Changes and Institutional Adaptation at the LIBE Committee. *Journal of European Integration*, 34(1), 55–73. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07036337.2011.566332>
- Sachseder, J., Stachowitsch, S., & Standke-Erdmann, M. (2024). Entangled Vulnerabilities: Gendered and Racialised Bodies and Borders in EU External Border Security. *Geopolitics*, 1–29. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14650045.2023.2291060>
- Sigona, N., Kato, J. & Kuznetsova, I. (2021). 'Migration infrastructures and the production of migrants' irregularity in Japan and the United Kingdom'. *Comparative Migration Studies*, 9(31).
- Teodorescu, L. (2024). Women on the move: Understanding the female face of migration to develop targeted policies. *European View*, 23(1), 55–63. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17816858241246662>
- Turner, L. (2019). Syrian refugee men as objects of humanitarian care. *International Feminist Journal of Politics*, 21(4), 595–616. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616742.2019.1641127>
- United Nations (2000). *Protocol against the Smuggling of Migrants by Land, Sea and Air, Supplementing the United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime*.
- United Nations General Assembly (UNGA, 1976). *Measures to ensure the human rights and dignity of all migrant workers*. A/RES/3449(XXX)
- Walters, W. (2011). Foucault and frontiers: Notes on the birth of the humanitarian border. In U. Bröckling, S. Krasmann, & T. Lemke (Eds.), *Governmentality: Current issues and future challenges* (pp. 138–164). Routledge.

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